

H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program 2023 Annual Report

Volume 1

Executive Summary, Program Level Results, Focal Project Results

Burntwood-Langenkamp, July 2023, Image Captured from Drone Flight.

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Please Cite this Report As: Lake Erie and Aquatic Research Network, Wetlands and Water Quality Group. 2023. H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program: 2023 Annual Progress Report, Vol. 1. Ohio Department of Natural Resources, Office of Coastal Management.

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COLLEGE OF FOOD, AGRICULTURAL,
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Executive Summary

To date, the H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program (hereafter Monitoring Program) has implemented routine monitoring in 24 H2Ohio Wetland Projects (hereafter Projects). Eight Focal Projects received higher frequency sampling, including assessments of water, vegetation, soil, and associated processes. Although they are preliminary, the results in this report indicate early nutrient retention successes at multiple projects and identify opportunities for improved design and management. Wetland nutrient retention changes from year to year depending on precipitation and over time with wetland development; thus, continued monitoring will improve the estimates of longer-term wetland performance, ultimately strengthening insights on how to manage these ecosystems to remain effective.

Nutrient Load Reduction Estimates Are Lower Than Initial ODNR Predictions

Nutrient load reduction estimates in 2023 indicated net P removal by most Projects. Of the completed Projects with sufficient results to estimate nutrient reduction, phosphorus (P) removal ranged from 0 to 108 pounds in 2023 and with three pounds of P removed on average per acre of wetland restored (Table 1.1). The year 2023 was drier than average and more nutrient capture may be possible in wetter years. Transient P release was observed in a minority of projects, demonstrating the importance of continued monitoring to document longer-term changes.

Monitoring Program-derived estimates are lower than some of the ODNR's initial predictions. The greatest uncertainties are associated with floodplain wetlands. Particularly large differences between initial ODNR predictions and Monitoring Program estimates for floodplain wetland types reflect the specific challenges in nutrient load budget calculations in floodplain systems, which rely on adequate sampling of infrequent, but inordinately important, flooding events.

The annual nutrient load reduction estimates presented here estimate the pounds of “new” P loads that were retained in 2023 (except for Oakwoods East and West). Wetlands established on formerly agricultural land prevent P loads associated with agricultural activities over the area of the constructed wetland itself. Future Monitoring Program estimates of load reduction will estimate both P loss prevention due to land use change and “new” P retention.

Refining H2Ohio Wetland Restoration Project Selection and Construction

The Monitoring Program's early results emphasize that **site selection and Project design must balance hydrologic connection and residence time to maximize nutrient removal**. Design often focuses on getting water and associated nutrients to the Project site effectively and keeping the water confined long enough for the wetland to serve its nutrient retention function. Sometimes design plans imply a connection, but the as-built Project may not be as hydrologically connected to nutrient load sources as expected due to on-the-ground changes in construction (e.g., drainage additions to prevent flooding in adjacent properties), unknown water inputs (e.g., tiles and groundwater) and/or weather patterns (i.e., need to account for both drought and flood conditions). Careful consideration of Project plans to ensure adequate connectivity to nutrient load sources will ensure prudent investments that meet H2Ohio Initiative goals. On-the-ground verification of as-built Projects are critical for validating implementation of the design and accurate assessments of function.

Other Management Considerations

Additional management considerations include placement of sediment and selection of plant species at Project sites. Soil capacity to sorb phosphate varies, and if soil sorption capacity is not considered during construction, soil may act as a nutrient source. Similarly, plant selection should consider seasonal growth patterns and plant functional types. Various plant species have different times at which they store nutrients above and below ground. For instance, some emergent plants re-sorb nutrients into their root systems during senescence, retaining them long-term, whereas others do not have long-term storage mechanisms and release nutrients during decomposition.

Nutrient Load Reduction Estimates Are Constrained by Hydrological Uncertainties

Generally, the Monitoring Program assesses nutrient reduction by examining changes in surface water volume and nutrient concentration measurements to calculate the total mass of nutrients removed per project per year. The Monitoring Program will continue to improve accuracy of load reduction estimates through ongoing data collection to fill knowledge gaps around hydrological dynamics, including the following questions:

- How do seasonal changes and precipitation events influence annual estimates of load reduction? For instance, sampling at some time periods only represents a “snapshot” and may miss key functional periods within a wetland (e.g., a high flow event).
- Where are agricultural drain tiles and how much land do they drain into Project sites? Wetlands may capture nutrients entering from unknown sources, changing load reduction estimates.
- Is groundwater a nutrient source or sink at constructed or restored wetlands? This information will identify where and when surface water estimates may not fully represent wetland nutrient removal function.
- What is the as-built topography of a project? Variable elevation influences surface flow, volume, and nutrient inputs.

Long-Term Monitoring & Assessment

Newly restored and constructed wetlands change drastically from season to season and year to year as plants and ecological functions re-establish. In addition, the weather patterns that fundamentally shape wetland hydrology vary from year to year. Centuries of observations have shown that all ecosystems are dynamic, and no single point in time or single year demonstrates the full function of an ecosystem or predicts how it will behave in the future.

The results reported here represent only one to three years of monitoring new H2Ohio Wetland Projects. While early data can indicate the direction a restored ecosystem is heading, continued monitoring is essential. With multiple years of data, certainty in assessments of function will improve, as will the understanding of how wetland design and management can be adjusted to enhance performance. The H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program Annual Monitoring Plan documents specific plans for monitoring in an upcoming year, and the Monitoring Framework explains the Program’s approach to establishing and continuing long-term wetland monitoring.

Table 1.1 Phosphorus (P) load reduction estimates for select H2Ohio Projects in 2023. Positive values indicate net P retention, while negative values indicate net P release to downstream systems. Gaps in hydrological data exist (e.g., location and directional flow of tiles, catchment runoff, and groundwater influence) and known considerations on these estimates are noted. Future refined estimates may change as monitoring continues. All but Tipp City Off-Channel Wetland are Focal Projects. ODNR Predictions are range of values based on drainage area from USGS Stream Stats, nutrient load estimates from SPARROW models, and applying literature-based nutrient removal rates. Monitoring Program Estimates are generally based on surface water nutrients concentrations and surface water volume measurements. St. Joseph’s River Restoration Project values are a range of values based on a range of estimated P inputs and retention estimates. Brooks Park values are mean values \pm standard error across seasons.

Project	Restored Wetland Acres	ODNR Prediction		Monitoring Program Estimate		Considerations
		lbs. P	lbs. P/acre	lbs. P	lbs. P/acre	
Tipp City Off-Channel Wetland	10	148–377	15–38	108	10.8	Connected to the Great Miami River by surface flooding through an inflow notch at high flow and through subsurface exchange between wetland and river through sandy soils.
Oakwoods Nature Preserve Wetland Restoration Project East & West (two Projects)	50	394–1599	7.9–32	82	1.64	Estimated reduction from converting agricultural land to wetland and eliminating fertilizer inputs and associated edge of field losses. Expected floodplain connection to Aurand Run is minimal especially low in 2023 due to relatively dry weather conditions.
St. Joseph's River Restoration Project	33	6–39	0.2–1.2	20–50	0.6–1.5	Possible underestimate: need more discharge and nutrient concentration data, especially from storm events and area drained by tiles.
Burntwood-Langenkamp Wetland Conservation Area	27	125–496	4.6–18	33	1.2	Input to wetland maintained by active pumping during certain periods of the year.
Forder Bridge Floodplain Reconnection	5	7–51	1.4–10	4–45	0.8–9	Possible underestimate: estimating precipitation from 30 mi away and need more discharge data, especially from area drained by tiles.
Redhorse Bend Preserve Wetland Restoration	20	1813–6880	73–275	13	0.65	Assumes most water from the Sandusky River stored in the wetland during and after storms would have drained into the Sandusky River prior to restoration.
Brooks Park Wetland Creation & Water Quality Initiative	5	70–278	14–56	-2 \pm 5	-0.4 \pm 1	Limited P removal because of very small watershed (~1.2 mi ²) and back-flooding during high Buckeye Lake water levels. Higher P removal was estimated in 2021–2022 (16 lbs.) because it was a wetter year than 2023.
Magee Marsh Turtle Creek Bay Wetland Reconnection	173	536–976	3.1–5.6	0	0	Disconnected in 2023 due to dike construction Project. With different management, could have removed up to 85 lbs. P (0.52 lb./acre)
Average lbs./acre:		34.7		3		

Program-Level Results

Overview of Routinely Monitored H2Ohio Wetland Projects

The H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program (hereafter Monitoring Program) routinely monitored **25 H2Ohio Wetland Projects (hereafter Projects) that range in area from 5 to 586 acres and treat from 21 to 8,018 acres of estimated drainage area in 2023** (Figure 1.1). The Projects represent a diverse range of restoration types, features, and geographies (Figure 2.1, Appendix Table 15.1). Before monitoring a Project, researchers characterize wetland features and flow paths via multiple field visits and partner meetings to affirm and/or improve hydrologic classifications provided by the ODNR (Figure 2.1). The Monitoring Program is refining estimates of drainage area for wetland Projects to more accurately account for the source and magnitude of nutrient loads being delivered to each Project (see Appendix, *Improving Wetland Drainage Area Estimation*).

Figure 1.1. Estimated wetland restoration and drainage area for H2Ohio Wetland Projects that were routinely monitored in 2023 (restoration and drainage areas provided by the ODNR). Green diamonds represent the restored wetland acres and blue circles denote the estimated drainage area treated by the wetland. The size of the blue circles denotes the proportion of the total drainage area that is estimated to be treated by the wetland. The area values (in acres) are shown next to the symbols in green and blue font for the restored wetland area and treated drainage area, respectively. Note the break on the x axis. A key connecting the four-letter codes to full Project Names can be found in Appendix Table 15.1.

Wetland Hydrologic Function Informs Monitoring Approach

Projects are generally identified as Floodplain, Coastal, Flow-through, and Isolated, although many projects contain features with multiple kinds of hydrologic function. The hydrologic function of a Project is one prominent feature that guides monitoring efforts and shapes data analysis. **Each kind of hydrologic function requires monitoring approaches appropriate to its unique characteristics.** Below are some specific insights and approaches from the Monitoring Program for each hydrologic function.

Floodplain: The Projects with the largest estimated drainage areas (>3,000 acres) were identified by ODNR as inland floodplain wetlands, i.e., Redhorse Bend (REDB), St. Joseph Confluence (SJCO), Tipp City (TIPC), and Weisgerber-Pohlman (WEIP, Figure 2.1). Based on the ODNR's current primary proxy (drainage area) for nutrient reduction potential, these Projects were predicted to have a large impact. However, they may not perform as expected; topography of as-built wetlands may prevent connection to surface inflows if, for example, a feature that is meant to flood is at an elevation that floods only during extremely high flood events. Surface water connection may also be limited during periods of low water levels and flow, both of which were observed in 2023. ODNR predictions of nutrient removal by floodplain features initially over-estimated the proportion of drainage area that interacts with the wetland system, and the Monitoring Program is adjusting drainage area estimates to more accurately characterize floodplain wetland inflow volumes (see Appendix, *Improving Wetland Drainage Area Estimation*).

Coastal: The three largest routinely monitored Projects (>100 acres) are coastal wetlands: Darby Refuge (DARR), Magee Marsh (MAGM), and Ottawa National Refuge (OTTN, Figure 2.1). Manual storm event sampling is logistically unfeasible at these coastal wetlands because the main mode of access is via roads on dikes that are unsafe to drive on during wet and stormy conditions. Automated water samplers can collect water during storm events, but their high costs restrict their deployment. In-situ water level data collected by sensors can support understanding of hydrologic function.

Flowthrough: Flowthrough wetlands often, though not always, have clearly defined inflows, outflows, surface water flow paths, and structures with known geometry (e.g., weirs), all of which aid “more straightforward” and quicker estimates of nutrient reduction than those in other hydrologic types. Still, surface water-based inflow and outflow load estimates and indices of internal soil processes need to be taken together to provide a comprehensive story of wetland nutrient function. For example, in Burntwood-Langenkamp (BWLK), 2023 surface water monitoring indicated wetland reduction of nutrient loads from the source creek, but the soil's capacity to sorb phosphate declined between the first and second years of post-construction monitoring. Thus, Monitoring Program results provide a snapshot of present function and highlight “what to watch” in future years of wetland ecosystem development.

Isolated: Some wetlands classified by the ODNR as flowthrough during the proposal stage (Figure 2.1) are functioning more as isolated depressional wetlands, e.g., Fruth (FRUW), Oakwoods East (OAKE), and Trumbull Creek (TRUC). In these mis-classified systems, there

Program-Level Results: Wetland Hydrologic Function Informs Monitoring Approach

may be a disconnect between the predicted and actual amount of water expected to be treated. In addition, diffuse structure and intermittent flow make it a more time-consuming effort to monitor and assess nutrient function. In the short-term, researchers can estimate the impact of “land conversion” (i.e., nutrients saved each year by taking land out of agricultural production where relevant). In the longer-term, researchers can use an approach of quantifying soil and vegetation nutrient pools over time.

Across hydrologic functions: Across all hydrologic functions, researchers note the importance of considering wetland water volume storage, connection to landscape, and the role of extreme weather conditions. Some wetland features are designed with relatively low water volume storage capacity in comparison to volumes of water that could flow into the feature. These water volume storage considerations as well as connection to the landscape are partially within design element control and could be more closely examined during the Project proposal stage. Extreme weather conditions or events (such as droughts and deluges) are outside of design control but could be modeled during Project proposal stage and integrated into management decisions.

Figure 2.1. Relationship between the estimated restored wetland acres and the drainage area expected to be treated by the wetland, as estimated by the ODNR. Four-letter codes represent relevant H2Ohio Wetland Projects and colors indicate the broad hydrologic category for each Project, as classified by the ODNR. A key connecting the four-letter codes to full Project names can be found in Appendix Table 15.1.

Weather Patterns in 2023 Shaped Wetland Hydrology and Function

Weather patterns (e.g., precipitation and air temperature) affect wetland dynamics by driving the extent of connectedness of floodplain wetlands to adjacent waterways, drying up of depressional wetland pools, and influence other plant, water, and soil processes. **2023 was a dry year compared to long-term averages, and monitoring results should be considered within this context.** Evidence from the Maumee River streamflow discharge showed low levels in October through December 2022 that rebounded to average levels by April 2023. However, from May through October 2023, the lack of precipitation, coupled with the high temperatures in June, resulted in an especially low accumulation of surface water flow volume (Figure 3.1).

Figure 3.1. Cumulative streamflow discharge volume for the USGS gage Maumee River at Waterville OH - 04193500¹ from 2000–2023. Red line indicates 2023, the bold black line is the mean daily cumulative value from 2000–2022, gray lines indicate individual years. Note: 1 cubic kilometer (km³) is equivalent to 264 billion gallons.

¹ “Maumee River at Waterville OH – 04193500.” [waterdata.usgs.gov](https://waterdata.usgs.gov/monitoring-location/04193500/). U.S. Department of Interior. <https://waterdata.usgs.gov/monitoring-location/04193500/>

Wetland Project Soils Have Capacity to Sorb Phosphate

One way that a wetland can retain phosphorus (P) is through sorption of phosphate ions to soil minerals. Monitoring Program researchers calculate the ratio of soil phosphate to available mineral sorption sites to assess the Soil Phosphate Sorption Capacity (SPSC). Positive SPSC values indicate capacity to sorb phosphate, while negative values indicate that the soil is already loaded with bound phosphate and may be vulnerable to releasing some of that phosphate into the water. When wetland soils release phosphate, the wetland may become (at least temporarily) a source, rather than a sink, for P. Values near zero indicate that the soil has low capacity to sorb additional phosphate, although this does not necessarily indicate that the wetland as a whole will not retain P (i.e., there are other processes at play).

The Monitoring Program collected soil samples from multiple locations within each routinely monitored Project. SPSC values ranged from 0 to over 300 mg P/kg, representing a broad range of phosphate sorption capacities (Figure 4.1). None of the soils had negative SPSC values. Thus, **although capacity varies, all measured soil samples from routinely monitored H2Ohio Projects can sorb some phosphate.**

Figure 4.1. Soil Phosphate Sorption Capacity (SPSC) for H2Ohio Wetland Projects monitored in 2021–2023. Boxplots indicate the distribution of data collected from each Wetland Project in 2021–2023, blue circles indicate observations from individual soil samples, and diamonds represent outlier values. Larger SPSC values indicate a greater capacity for the soil to sorb phosphate. A key connecting the four-letter codes to full Project Names can be found in Appendix Table 15.1.

Nutrient Exchange Between Sediments and Surface Waters Varies

Nutrient exchange, or flux, between sediments and surface water, as measured in field-collected, lab-incubated sediment cores, can be used to estimate whether or not sediments will release nutrients to surface waters (positive values) or retain nutrients from surface waters (negative values). **Across Projects, sediment-surface water nutrient exchange varied.** Some sediments retained dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP) from surface waters while others released DRP into surface waters. Generally, wetland sediments retained nitrate+nitrite (NO_x) from surface waters and released total ammonia (NH₃) to surface waters (Figure 5.1).

Sediment-water DRP fluxes varied in direction but were typically consistent in magnitude, ranging from -11 to 13 mg P/m²/d. Almost all sediments measured had either net zero or negative (retention) flux for NO_x, although the variation in magnitude was greater across sites (-479–7 mg N/m²/d) than observed in DRP rates. Likewise, total ammonia (NH₃) flux varied greatly across all sediments (-27–427 mg N/m²/d) but was typically released from the sediments.

Figure 5.1. Sediment-water nutrient exchange across six H2Ohio Wetland Projects sampled in 2023 measured via intact sediment core incubations. The Project Codes are listed across the top,

Program-Level Results: Vegetation Nutrient Storage Changes as Plants Establish

and wetland features are listed across the bottom. Each row of panels represents a different nutrient measured (DRP = dissolved reactive phosphorus, NO_x = nitrate+nitrite, NH₃ = total ammonia). Bar plots represent mean sediment-water exchange rates within the wetland feature, across measurements from 3–8 sediment cores, each core indicated by black circles. Positive values indicate release of nutrients from the sediment to the surface water. Negative values indicate retention of nutrients from surface water to the sediment. Error bars represent standard error. Note the change in magnitude and direction of the y-axis across the three nutrient panels. Total NH₃-N was not measured for samples from BWLK. A key connecting the four-letter codes to full Project Names can be found in Appendix Table 15.1.

Vegetation Nutrient Storage Changes as Plants Establish

Project-scale vegetation nutrient stock is a metric that aggregates per acre nutrient storage and community composition across the total area of a Project each year. Across Focal Projects, **total nutrient stocks in plant biomass ranged widely from 34 to 10,124 lbs. of phosphorus (P), and from 131 to 40,097 lbs. of nitrogen (N)**, Appendix Table 16.1). The total Project area of the restored or enhanced wetland may explain much of this variability, but not all. Despite having similar area, Oakwoods East and West (OAKE, OAKW) had lower vegetation nutrient stocks than St. Joseph’s River Restoration (SJRE), potentially driven by large differences in the per acre nutrient storage (Figure 6.1).

The wetland restoration approach impacts how vegetation data are interpreted. The coastal wetland reconnection Project, Magee Marsh (MAGM), had 158 acres of well-established wetland vegetation prior to restoration and had the highest vegetation nutrient stock in 2023 (Appendix Table 16.1). Due to a lack of pre-restoration data at Magee Marsh, estimating the impact of restoration on plant biomass nutrient stocks is challenging. On the other hand, wetlands that were created in former farm fields, such as St. Joseph’s River Restoration, vegetation developed following the construction of the wetland pools, thus much of the nutrient stock can be attributed to post-restoration growth. Calculating the difference in vegetation nutrient stocks from year to year is the best way to estimate annual nutrient remediation by wetland plants, including assessment of the relative roles of aboveground and belowground biomass in nutrient storage over time (Appendix Figure 16.3, Appendix Figure 16.4).

Per acre vegetation nutrient storage varied across time and across Projects, ranging from 8 to 101 lbs. of P per acre and 33 to 335 lbs. of N per acre in 2021–2023 (Figure 6.1). The low per acre nutrient storage at some wetlands can be attributed to early restoration conditions in recently completed projects, when vegetation had yet to fill bare areas following construction (e.g., Forder Bridge, FORB, in 2021 and Burntwood-Langenkamp, BWLK in 2023). The St. Joseph’s River Restoration and Magee Marsh Projects had the highest per acre storage of N and P in plant biomass in 2023; the storage at St. Joseph’s River Restoration may be driven by the greater biomass density, whereas the storage at Magee Marsh may be driven by the high vegetation nutrient content (Appendix Figure 16.3, Appendix Figure 16.6, Appendix Figure 16.7). Multi-year monitoring and synthesis of vegetation, water, soil, geophysical, and drone data will aid

Program-Level Results: Vegetation Diversity Observations

understanding of why per acre vegetation nutrient storage is higher at one Project than another and will identify trends across wetland restoration approaches and hydrologic structures.

Low per acre vegetation nutrient storage was observed at Oakwoods East and West across multiple years (Figure 6.1). Oakwoods East and West are composed mostly of isolated wetlands instead of flow-through, floodplain, or coastal wetland hydrologic types. While researchers cannot yet conclude if the low vegetation nutrient storage at these Projects can be attributed to wetland hydrologic type or nutrient inputs, this is an example of a hypothesis that can be tested by comparing species-specific nutrient measures across Projects (Appendix Figure 16.6, Appendix Figure 16.7) and continuing to monitor wetland ecosystems as they develop.

Figure 6.1. Pounds of nitrogen (N) and phosphorus (P) stored in vegetation per acre for routinely monitored H2Ohio Wetland Focal Projects from 2021 to 2023. ND indicates vegetation data were not collected at that Project in that year and the asterisk indicates results for Brooks Park (BROP) in 2022 are in progress. A key connecting the four-letter codes to full Project Names can be found in Appendix Table 15.1.

Vegetation Diversity Observations

Vegetation results suggest an early trend of increasing species richness and increased diversity over time following restoration (Figure 7.1). For many Projects, species richness increased from 2021 to 2022, as wetland-obligate and facultative wetland species established, replacing non-wetland, adventive/early species, as evidenced by increases in the Floristic Quality Assessment Index (FQAI, Figure 7.2). FQAI is calculated using Coefficients of Conservatism (C-values) assigned to individual species by expert analysis for the region of Ohio. Higher C-

Program-Level Results: Vegetation Diversity Observations

values indicate that a species will only be found in relatively undisturbed or high-quality habitats. Species with lower C-values tend to be ruderals or weedy species that briefly colonize the early-restoration habitats, which may be replaced with species of higher C-values as wetland ecosystem development progresses. Decreases in richness and diversity in 2023 might be attributed to it being a drier year than 2022 or to the absence of the non-wetland, ruderal species, highlighting the importance of long-term monitoring to understand trends.

It is notable that St. Joseph’s River Restoration (SJRE) had high diversity and floristic quality (Figure 7.1, Figure 7.2), and was the only Focal Project not dominated by Cattail (*Typha* sp.), instead hosting hosts species such as Soft Rush (*Juncus effusus*), Virginia Wild Rye (*Elymus virginicus*), Blue Vervain (*Verbena hastata*), and Arrowhead (*Sagittaria* sp.). High diversity may contribute to the high biomass density and nutrient storage at this Project (Appendix Figure 16.3, Appendix Figure 16.6, Appendix Figure 16.7).

Figure 7.1. Species Richness and Simpson’s Diversity Index for vegetation in H2Ohio Wetland Focal Projects from 2021 to 2023. Because Richness and Simpson's Diversity are sensitive to sample size, data were rarified by constraining analysis to a standard number of samples across Projects and years corresponding to the minimal number of samples taken at any single Project and year (n = 17). Sampling of Magee Marsh (MAGM) in 2023 targeted diverse vegetation patches making comparison of Species Richness and Diversity metrics to other Projects unsuitable, so Magee Marsh have been removed from Diversity analyses.

Program-Level Results: Vegetation Diversity Observations

Figure 7.2. Floristic Quality Assessment Index (FQAI) values for vegetation in H2Ohio Wetland Focal Projects plotted in regard to time since restoration (construction). In 2022, Forder Bridge was selected for an oversampling study, so FQAI analysis was completed using a subset of data sampled during July.

Focal Project Results

The following sections describe the Project Overview, Nutrient Load Reduction Assessment, Management Considerations, Sampling Approach, and Monitoring Considerations for each Focal Project routinely monitored by the H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program from 2021 to 2023. Where applicable, Hydrology, Three-dimensional (3D) Hydrodynamic model, Sediment-Surface Nutrient Exchange Rates, and Hydrogeophysics results are presented. In each Focal Project section, Sampling Location Water Depths, Surface Water Concentrations, Soil Nutrient Status, and Vegetation results are preliminarily summarized (i.e., values aggregated across sampling locations and season and briefly interpreted by researchers). Unless otherwise noted, all surface water, soil, and vegetation results are presented as mean \pm standard deviation.

In addition to the tables and figures contained in this document, supplemental data are presented in an accompanying **H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program: 2023 Annual Progress Report Appendices** (A–C) document. External appendix figures include letters to represent A) Focal Projects Appendix, B) Non-Focal Projects Appendix, and C) Vegetation Data Appendix. Some elements within this document may be repeated in the Appendix.

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Brooks Park Wetland Creation & Water Quality Initiative (BROP)

Project Overview

Fairfield County | Licking River Watershed | Inland Eastern Ohio

Project size: 1.5 Acres

Partner: ODNR Division of Parks & Watercraft

ODNR Description: “The Buckeye Lake State Park Brooks Park Project will reduce nutrients and pollutants entering Buckeye Lake via Murphy’s Run through the creation of new wetlands at Brooks Park. The Project will accomplish this goal through habitat improvement along Murphy’s Run and establishing connectivity with an off-channel wetland. Stream habitat improvements and creation of wetlands will lead to increased ecological function including nutrient, sediment, and pollutant removal.”²

Nutrient Load Reduction Assessment

In 2023, the Brooks Park Wetland Creation & Water Quality Initiative Project (hereafter Brooks Park Project) may have been a small net source of surface water total phosphorus (Estimated load reduction = -2 ± 5 lbs. P, annual mean \pm standard error across seasons) and effectively retained surface water total nitrogen (385 ± 85 lbs. N, mean \pm standard error across seasons). However, researchers estimate vegetation stocks of 66 lbs. of P and 339 lbs. of N, and a net positive capacity for the soils to sorb phosphate. Sediments across the wetland either retained or did not release dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP) and nitrate+nitrite (NO_x) but released total ammonia (NH₃) into surface waters, based on experiments of field-collected, lab-incubated sediment cores.

Management Considerations

The Brooks Park Project’s primary input source, Murphy’s Run, has a relatively small drainage area (~ 1 mi²), thus the creek is unlikely to be a large contributor to eutrophication of Buckeye Lake. While the Project may treat the nutrient load delivered by Murphy’s Run, it cannot account for nutrient loads that enter Buckeye Lake from other water sources. When lake water levels rise, often during summer, the lake can backflow into wetland pools and there is higher potential for processing of water coming both from Murphy’s Run Inflow and Buckeye Lake. Small quantities (~ 15 gallons per minute) of water are currently pumped from the Main Pool to the West Pool (Figure 8.2). The average annual nitrate+nitrite (NO_x) and total nitrogen (TN) concentrations in the West Pool are approximately 97% and 58% lower than in the Murphy’s Run Inflow (Table 8.1), suggesting the overall nutrient reduction capacity of this Project may be improved by moving more water into the West Pool.

² “Brooks Park Wetland Creation & Water Quality Initiative.” h2.ohio.gov. Ohio Departments of Natural Resources, Agriculture, and Environmental Protection, March 4, 2024. <https://h2.ohio.gov/Project/brooks-park-wetland-creation-water-quality-initiative-phase-2/>

Sampling Approach

Construction of the Brooks Park Project was complete in 2021. Routine monitoring began in 2022. The unique hydrology of this Project influences where water samples are collected.

Murphy’s Run, a small tributary of Buckeye Lake, drains 1.2 square miles of primarily farmland and flows as the main input into the wetland pools of this Project during times of the year when Buckeye Lake water depth is lower (winter drawdown). Greater water depths in Buckeye Lake (summer pool) result in Buckeye Lake back flowing into the wetland, occasionally all the way into Murphy’s Run. Surface water and soil samples are collected from six locations throughout this Project; one in Buckeye Lake, one in Murphy’s Run (“Murphy’s Run Inflow”) and four locations representing key features of the wetland complex (“Main Pool”, “West Pool”, “Mid-wetland Stream”, “Wetland Stream Outflow”, Figure 8.2).

Water depth loggers (Onset HOB0® and Solinst Levellogger 5, Solinst Canada Ltd.) were deployed to measure high temporal resolution water depth at the Mid-wetland Stream and Wetland Stream Outflow sampling locations starting in 2023. These two locations were strategically chosen to help determine when and how far Buckeye Lake is back flowing into the wetland. A water depth logger was also deployed in a groundwater monitoring well nearest to Buckeye Lake to help determine groundwater’s influence on the Project.

Vegetation surveys for community composition occurred at the Brooks Park Project in October 2021, August 2022, and September 2023 (Table C1.2). Sampling of aboveground biomass and nutrient concentration occurred during survey periods for 2022 and 2023. To measure sediment-water nutrient exchange, researchers collected and incubated three intact sediment cores from four locations representative of each major pool at the Brooks Park Project.

Figure 8.1. Installation of water depth loggers at the Brooks Park Project in March 2023.

Focal Project Results: Brooks Park Wetland Creation & Water Quality Initiative (BROP)

Figure 8.2. Aerial image of approximate location of sampling for water and soil samples and discrete manual measurements of water depth and physicochemical measurements at Brooks Park Wetland Creation & Water Quality Initiative Project. The legend provides a brief description of each sampling location.

3D Hydrodynamic Model

A three-dimensional (3D) hydrodynamic model was developed for the Brooks Park Project in 2022 using a 3D modeling approach based on HydroGeoSphere (see Appendix, *3D Hydrodynamic Model*). The model outputs depict simulated water depths (Figure 8.3). The model is useful for visualizing the influence of back flooding that occurs at various levels of Buckeye Lake (Figure 8.4).

Figure 8.3. H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program 3D Hydrodynamic Model Output Example. These figures show how the water depth in the created wetland pools would respond to different

hydrologic and boundary conditions: (a) inflow from Murphy’s run and outflow to Buckeye Lake during normal condition and (b) dominant inflow from Buckeye Lake during a wet and high lake-level condition. Warmer/red colors indicate deeper water, cooler/blue colors indicate shallow water, and arrows indicate direction of water flow.

Hydrology

Higher water depths at the Wetland Stream Outflow sampling location in summer indicate Buckeye Lake summer pool backflow while lower depths in winter indicate Buckeye Lake drawdown (Figure 8.4).

Figure 8.4. Surface water elevation (ft) for Buckeye Lake (left panel) from USGS gage near Watkins Island OH – 395540082291600³. Dashed lines represent the surface water elevations at which Buckeye Lake water can reach certain wetland zones in the Brooks Park Project during backflow events. Wetland zones are indicated in text to the right of the figure and highlighted in respective colors in the aerial image of the Brooks Park Project (right panel). The yellow arrow at the top of the aerial image represents Buckeye Lake backflow into the Brooks Park Project.

³ “USGS gage Buckeye Lake near Watkins Island OH – 395540082291600.” waterdata.usgs.gov. U.S. Department of Interior. <https://waterdata.usgs.gov/monitoring-location/395540082291600>

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Figure 8.5 Average daily depths (ft) in the Wetland Stream channel (blue solid line from late 2023 to 2024), the Mid-Wetland Stream Outflow (orange solid line from early 2023 to 2024), and groundwater monitoring well placed near the Mid-Wetland Stream Outflow (green solid line from late 2023 to 2024). The data gap in December for the Wetland Stream and Mid-Wetland Stream Outflow is due to a sensor malfunction. All data were collected using a Solinst Levelogger 5 (Solinst Canada Ltd.), except for the Mid-Wetland Stream Outflow from Mar–Nov 2023 that was collected using an Onset HOB0®.

Sampling Location Water Depths

Sampling locations are shown above in Figure 8.2. Of all sampling locations, Buckeye Lake had the greatest average water depth (53 cm) and was the most variable across time (Figure 8.6, Table A1.2). Buckeye Lake water depth varied greatly with season as lake levels dropped during winter and increased during summer (0–100 cm). Murphy’s Run Inflow had the second greatest average water depth (50 cm) and was more consistent across time (Figure 8.6, Table A2). There is a persistent water stream that flows from Murphy’s Run Inflow sampling location to Wetland Stream Outflow sampling location. During periods of high flow from Murphy’s Run or Buckeye Lake summer pool back flow, wetland areas beyond the wetland stream may become intermittently inundated.

Manual, discretely measured water depths only represent the water depths from where the water sample was collected and do not indicate depth of the deepest point of each feature, though they were used to verify and calibrate the deployed water depth logger sensors (See above, *Sampling Approach*).

Surface Water Nutrient Concentrations

Total phosphorus (TP) and dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP) varied across surface water sampling locations and season (Figure 8.7). Buckeye Lake had the highest average surface water TP (0.118 mg P/L), similar TP to Wetland Stream Outflow (0.112 mg P/L), and the lowest average DRP concentration (0.006 mg P/L, Table A1.4). Average DRP concentrations were highest in the fall (0.019 mg P/L) while average TP concentrations were highest in the summer (0.13 mg P/L, Table A1.5).

Average nitrate-nitrite (NO_x), and total nitrogen (TN) were highest at the Murphy's Run Inflow surface water sampling location (1.618 and 2.671 mg N/L, respectively, Table 8.1), while this location exhibited a relatively low average DRP concentration (0.014 mg P/L) and the lowest average TP concentration (0.076 mg P/L, Table A1.4). The Wetland Stream Outflow had greater surface water NO_x and TN (1.193 mg and 2.613 mg N/L, respectively, Table 8.1) concentrations than Buckeye Lake NO_x and TN concentrations (0.84 and 2.489 mg N/L, respectively, Table 8.1). Spring had the highest average NO_x, total ammonia (NH₃), and TN concentrations, most likely due to timing of runoff from surrounding agricultural land (Table A1.7).

Soil Nutrient Status

The Main Pool had the lowest Soil Phosphate Sorption Capacity (SPSC), indicating a lower capacity for soils to sorb phosphate (49 mg P/kg). West Pool soils had the greatest capacity to sorb phosphate (>100 mg P/kg, Figure 8.8).

Focal Project Results: Brooks Park Wetland Creation & Water Quality Initiative (BROP)

Figure 8.6. Boxplots displaying variability in discrete, manually measured surface water depths (in centimeters) across sampling locations at the Brooks Park Wetland Creation & Water Quality Initiative Project. Depths were measured approximately monthly from 2021–2023. For each boxplot, the thick line represents the median (middle) surface water depth across all measurements. The boxes indicate the value range for 50% of the measured depths and the whiskers show the spread of depth values that are outside the 50% of the data points. Each overlying point represents individual water depth measurements and colors denote the season in which the measurement was taken, as indicated in the legend.

Focal Project Results: Brooks Park Wetland Creation & Water Quality Initiative (BROP)

Figure 8.7. Time series of dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP, top panel) and total phosphorus (TP, bottom panel) concentrations in surface water samples collected at the Brooks Park Wetland Creation & Water Quality Initiative Project from 2021–2023. Each symbol represents one sample point, colors denote the sampling locations, and shapes indicate the general category of the sampling locations, as indicated in the legend. Values below detection limit were replaced with zero. Connected circles represent samples collected within 30 days of each other.

Focal Project Results: Brooks Park Wetland Creation & Water Quality Initiative (BROP)

Table 8.1. Summarized surface water nitrogen concentrations for the Brooks Park Wetland Creation & Water Quality Initiative Project. Values are reported as mean ± standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Nitrate+Nitrite (NO_x), total ammonia (NH₃) and total nitrogen (TN) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	Nitrate+Nitrite (mg N/L)			Total Ammonia (mg N/L)			Total Nitrogen (mg N/L)		
	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
01. Murphy's Run Inflow	1.618 ± 1.9	56 (6)	0–10.95	0.044 ± 0.1	45 (2)	0–0.61	2.671 ± 2.3	56 (0)	0.28–14.03
02. Main Pool	1.518 ± 2	58 (6)	0–10.58	0.046 ± 0.1	44 (2)	0–0.64	2.523 ± 2.3	56 (0)	0.23–15.13
03. Wetland Stream Outflow	1.193 ± 1.8	61 (10)	0–11.66	0.05 ± 0.1	45 (5)	0–0.65	2.613 ± 2	57 (0)	0.45–13.63
04. Buckeye Lake	0.84 ± 1	56 (16)	0–4.35	0.065 ± 0.1	45 (9)	0–0.6	2.489 ± 1	56 (0)	0.89–6.89
05. West Pool	0.047 ± 0.3	64 (56)	0–2.76	0.005 ± 0	45 (9)	0–0.02	1.125 ± 0.7	60 (0)	0.27–4.05
06. Mid-wetland Stream	0.831 ± 0.7	22 (5)	0–2.22	0.029 ± 0	11 (0)	0.01–0.06	1.613 ± 0.8	22 (0)	0.35–3.35

Focal Project Results: Brooks Park Wetland Creation & Water Quality Initiative (BROP)

Figure 8.8. Soil Phosphate Sorption Capacity (SPSC) throughout the Brooks Park Wetland Creation & Water Quality Initiative Project. Each circle denotes an approximate sampling location and is annotated with the mean SPSC for spatially clustered soil samples (0–5 cm). The number of samples in each cluster is shown in white font below the circles. The color of the circle indicates the range of SPSC values, as indicated in the legend. Negative SPSC values indicate potential for soils to release phosphate, while positive values indicate soils have capacity to sorb phosphate, based on Mehlich 3 extractions of P, Fe, and Al.

Vegetation

Nutrient Storage

Vegetation nutrient stocks have decreased from 2021 to 2023 at the Brooks Park Project; from 92 lbs. to 66 lbs. of P, and from 365 lbs. of N to 339 lbs. of N (Figure 8.10, Figure 8.10). While this Project is smaller in area than other Projects, the per acre vegetation nutrient storage is comparable to that of larger Projects (Figure 6.1). Biomass of Cattail (*Typha sp.*) had among the lowest tissue nutrient concentrations across species at this Project (Figure 8.11), but had among the highest plant biomass P density (~3.75 g P/ m², Figure 8.12) and N density (~15 g N/ m², Figure 8.13) because it makes up the highest biomass per unit area (~ 2000 g/m², Figure C1.2). Cattail tends to grow in monotypic stands crowding out other species, whereas two other wetland plant types, Sedges (*Carex sp.*) and Softstem Bulrush (*Schoenoplectus tabernaemontani*), also stored substantial quantities of nutrients at this Project in 2021–2023 and are more likely to coexist with other species in higher diversity patches.

Plant Diversity

In 2023, 82% of the observed plant species were species native to Ohio, up from 20% in 2021 (Figure 8.14). Almost half of the observed plant species in 2023 were wetland obligate species. Although the total number of species observed has decreased over time, the Floristic Quality Assessment Index (FQAI) at the site has increased (Figure 8.14). This likely reflects the establishment of stable patches dominated by wetland species as opposed to upland or adventive species. High FQAI results from abundant species with high Coefficients of Conservatism (C-values). Higher C-values indicate that a species will only be found in relatively undisturbed or high-quality habitats, indicating that in the second- and third-years post restoration the Brooks Park Project is able to support more species that are sensitive to disturbance than in its early restoration state.

Planting Details

Following construction at the Brooks Park Project, seeding took place in spring 2021. Seed mixes were based on the Ohio Prairie Moist Meadow seed mix (NEOMM01), the Ohio Prairie Nursery True Colors - Dry by 18 Tall Native seed mix (D18T01). Seeded species were observed at low abundances in the 2021 sampling year and higher abundances in later sampling years (Table C1.3).

2023 Vegetation Patches at Brooks Park Wetland Creation & Water Quality Initiative

Figure 8.9. Drone imagery of Brooks Park Wetland Creation & Water Quality Initiative taken in 2023 with outlined vegetation patches. Patches are used to calculate wetland vegetation nutrient storage estimates.

Focal Project Results: Brooks Park Wetland Creation & Water Quality Initiative (BROP)

Figure 8.10. (a) Tentative initial estimates of nutrient stocks stored in wetland vegetation at Brooks Park Wetland Creation & Water Quality Initiative from 2021 and 2023. Nutrient stocks for 2022 and confidence intervals for these estimates are still in progress. (b) Estimate of total vegetated wetland area made using Expert Patch Maps (see Figure 8.9) is shown in acres.

Figure 8.11. Boxplots showing measurements of vegetation nutrient concentration (%) for each species collected in sampling year 2022 at Brooks Park Wetland Creation & Water Quality Initiative. Boxplots show the first quartile, median, and third quartile. A key for Wetland Indicator Status (WIS) codes can be found in Table C1.1.

Focal Project Results: Brooks Park Wetland Creation & Water Quality Initiative (BROP)

Figure 8.12. Estimated mean species P density (g/m^2) from vegetation biomass and nutrient concentration data collected at Brooks Park Wetland Creation & Water Quality Initiative for sampling year 2022. Error bars represent standard error and are only present when more than one sample of a given species was taken. A key for Wetland Indicator Status (WIS) codes can be found in Table C1.1.

Figure 8.13. Estimated mean species N density (g/m^2) from vegetation biomass and nutrient concentration data collected at Brooks Park Wetland Creation & Water Quality Initiative for sampling year 2022. Error bars represent standard error and are only present when more than one sample of a given species was taken. A key for Wetland Indicator Status (WIS) codes can be found in Table C1.1.

Focal Project Results: Brooks Park Wetland Creation & Water Quality Initiative (BROP)

Figure 8.14. Calculated measures of diversity and descriptive statistics for vegetation at Brooks Park Wetland Creation & Water Quality Initiative including (a) species richness (number of species encountered), (b) the Simpson's Index of Diversity (0–1; higher numbers indicate increased diversity), (c) the Floristic Quality Assessment Index (FQAI) which uses the coefficient of conservatism of observed species to quantify habitat quality, (d) Wetland Indicator Status (WIS) in the Midwest region and (e) Ohio vegetation status. Morphospecies fell into the NA or ND category when identifications were not at the species taxonomic level (e.g., when they are immature) or because that species was not defined for either the WIS or OH Status in the Ohio EPA species list. A key for WIS codes can be found in Table C1.1 and further information on these metrics can be found in the Appendix, *Vegetation Method Overview*.

Sediment-Surface Water Nutrient Exchange Rates

Sediments at the Brooks Park Project typically retained dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP) and nitrate+nitrite (NO_x) from the water column but released total ammonia (NH₃) from into the surface water 2023. Researchers measured sediment-surface water nutrient exchange rates using three replicate intact cores collected from four sampling locations within the Project and incubated in flow-through systems. Three sediment core sampling locations aligned with surface water sampling locations (Main Pool, “Stream Channel” near Mid-wetland Stream, and West Pool, Figure 8.2) and one was adjacent to the Mid-wetland Stream location (“Floodplain Pools”). The fastest rate of DRP and NO_x uptake occurred in the sediments of the Floodplain Pools, adjacent to the Stream Channel (Figure 8.15). At most times and locations, NO_x retention, removal through denitrification (reduction of NO_x to nitrogen gas), was greater than total NH₃ release, indicating net N sinks. The West Pool sediments had little to no exchange of all three nutrients with the overlying water.

Currently, the intact sediment core incubation protocol is only equipped to sample sediment from inundated areas of the Project. Future development of the methods will expand researchers’ ability to estimate nutrient exchange in upland or intermittently dry areas of the Project.

Monitoring Considerations & Future Efforts

Currently, the Buckeye Lake water sample is taken nearby the Wetland Stream Outflow water sample. During winter flooding, this can cause the Buckeye Lake sample to be more representative of the Wetland Stream Outflow sample than Buckeye Lake, due to low lake water depths. In 2024, a new water sampling location will be collected from Buckeye Lake off the tip of Castle Island near the wetland. With nutrient data from the new water sample, average wetland pool nutrient concentrations can be better compared to Buckeye Lake concentrations.

Figure 8.15. Sediment-water nutrient exchange in four pools of the Brooks Park Project measured via intact sediment core incubations. Bar plots represent nutrient flux at each pool averaged between flux measurements from three cores (black circles) taken within the wetland area in May 2023. Positive values indicate release of nutrients from the sediment to the surface water. Negative values indicate retention of nutrients from surface water to the sediment. Error bars represent standard error. Note the change in magnitude and direction of the y-axis across the three nutrient panels.

Nutrient Load Calculation

Result- In 2023, total nitrogen (TN) loads from Murphy’s Run were reduced by 385 ± 85 lbs. N (annual mean \pm seasonal standard error), but total phosphorus (TP) loads were not reduced. A small net export of 2 ± 5 lbs. P (annual mean \pm seasonal standard error) was estimated from the Brooks Park Project in 2023.

Estimation Method- To estimate nutrient load reductions for this Project, researchers estimated volumes of water entering and leaving the wetland from a nearby USGS gage and used directly measured values of surface water nutrient concentrations from weekly water sampling.

Volume- The volume of water in Murphy’s Run was calculated using a combination of directly measured flow rates for a portion of the monitoring period and watershed weighting estimates from a nearby USGS gage South Fork Licking River near Hebron OH – 03145000⁴ to fill gaps in data. The ratio of the drainage area of Murphy’s Run (1.2 mi^2) to the drainage area of the gage station (133 mi^2) was used as a multiplication factor of 0.00902 to weight the USGS gage flow and estimate discharge for the Murphy’s Run watershed. Discharge estimated from watershed weighting was further corrected using the relationship between the watershed weighting estimated discharge and measured discharge from the areal velocity sensor over the sensor deployment period. The discharge from Murphy’s Run (as the sole surface inflow) was assumed to account for the entire volume of the wetland inflows and outflows.

Cumulative discharge was calculated by adding up watershed weighted average daily discharge values for periods between water sampling events. For load calculations, backflow from Buckeye Lake was assumed to be minimal, not affecting the total volume of water entering and leaving the wetland overall.

Concentration- Biweekly nutrient loads were determined by the difference between outflow and inflow concentrations multiplied by the cumulative water discharge from the biweekly time period since the last samples. Change in concentrations was obtained by subtracting the “outflow” from the “inflow” concentrations based on field-collected surface water concentration data. “Inflow” data came from the Murphy’s Run Inflow sampling location. The “outflow” sampling location chosen was contingent on lake and wetland water depths, as Buckeye Lake periodically back flows into the wetland during periods of summer pool. Buckeye Lake backflow events were detected using conductivity and other surface water physicochemical parameters. During times when the lake back flowed, the “outflow” concentration used in the calculation was taken from a location further upstream where the lake water had minimal influence (the Main Pool surface water sampling location, Figure 8.2), whereas when it was clear that the lake was not back flowing, the “outflow” concentration came from the Wetland Stream Outflow sampling location.

⁴ “South Fork Licking River near Hebron OH - 03145000.” [waterdata.usgs.gov](https://waterdata.usgs.gov/monitoring-location/03145000/). U.S. Department of Interior.
<https://waterdata.usgs.gov/monitoring-location/03145000/>

Burntwood-Langenkamp Wetland Conservation Area (BWLK)

Project Overview

Mercer County | Coldwater Creek Watershed | Inland Western Ohio

Project size: 90 Acres

Partner: Division of Parks & Watercraft and Lake Facilities Authority

ODNR Description: “The Burntwood-Langenkamp Wetland Conservation Area is the fourth treatment train associated with nutrient reduction efforts at Grand Lake St. Marys. The Lake Facilities Authority purchased property in Butler Township with Clean Ohio grant funding. Following acquisition, the H2Ohio program funded construction of a passive wetland treatment train featuring three created wetlands, several acres of planted trees, and a large buffer area of planted grasses/forbs.”⁵

Nutrient Load Reduction Assessment

Monitoring indicates that in 2023, the 27 acres of wetlands at Burntwood-Langenkamp Wetland Conservation Area (hereafter Burntwood-Langenkamp Project) retained at least 33 lbs. of total phosphorus (TP), at approximately 1.2 lbs. P per acre, and at least 5,900 lbs. of total nitrogen (TN). Although it was at certain times, a net source of TP (–6.81 lbs. P), the overall annual balance indicates net retention of nutrients. Plant biomass in 2023 was relatively low in this newly constructed ecosystem, indicating potential for plant growth in future years to store nutrients. Soils throughout the wetland have an enhanced capacity to sorb phosphate in comparison to pre-construction soils, which had the potential to release phosphate. However, soil phosphate sorption capacity declined between the first and second years of post-construction monitoring. Based on experiments of field-collected, lab-incubated sediment cores, there was variability across sampling locations in dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP) exchange between sediment and surface waters; two retained DRP from surface waters, one did not retain or release DRP, and one released DRP. Sediments from all four sediment sampling locations retained or did not release nitrate+nitrite (NO_x).

Management Considerations

Based on surface water nutrient concentration estimates, the young (< 3 years old) Burntwood-Langenkamp Project wetland is functioning as a nutrient sink. There is likely potential to process more nutrients by bringing more water through the Project via increased pumping of water from Burntwood Creek. Plans for the coming year include digging out a sump (hole to allow for deeper water depths) to allow increased water depth for pumping longer into the summer than was previously possible given water depth limitations during dry periods.

The Burntwood-Langenkamp Project’s outflow control structure allows researchers to monitor flow and allows managers to control the volume of water that leaves the wetland. With this

⁵ “Burntwood-Langenkamp Wetland Conservation Area.” h2.ohio.gov. Ohio Departments of Natural Resources, Agriculture, and Environmental Protection, March 4, 2024. <https://h2.ohio.gov/Project/burntwood-langenkamp-wetland-conservation-area/>

Focal Project Results: Burntwood-Langenkamp Wetland Conservation Area (BWLK)

Project's relatively well-defined inflow/outflow structure and the use of a pump, active management in response to changing hydrologic conditions can optimize nutrient removal. Wetland managers can be notified when volume control should be altered by looking at hydrology and surface water nutrient data. For example, increased volumes of water can be pumped into the wetland during the growing season to stimulate plant growth and increase retention time of water in the wetland pools.

Sampling Approach

Construction of the Burntwood-Langenkamp Project was completed in January 2022. Routine monitoring began in 2022. Water from Burntwood Creek can enter the wetland through an inflow notch when water reaches a discharge rate in the adjacent creek (Burntwood Creek), or when it is actively pumped into the wetland. The discharge rate at which water flows through the notch is estimated to be approximately 11 cubic feet per second, depending on the water level in the settling pool. Once in the wetland, the water flows into a deep settling pool then through over a mile of meandering marsh flats to the outflow at Coldwater Creek. Water depths are monitored manually at sampling locations and at standardized fixed staff gages. Samples are collected from Burntwood Creek (inflow), the Settling Pool, other locations throughout the wetland, and the Outflow (which flows out to Coldwater Creek, Figure 9.2)

Vegetation surveys and sampling of above- and belowground plant biomass at Burntwood-Langenkamp Project took place in July 2023 (Table C2.1). To measure sediment-water nutrient exchange at the Burntwood-Langenkamp Project, researchers collected and incubated triplicate sediment cores from four locations representative of the inflow and outflow of the wetland, along with the upper and lower sections of the meandering marsh stream and flats.

Figure 9.1. Burntwood-Langenkamp Project (Left) Staff gage installation in February 2023 and (Right) Intact core sediment sampling in June 2023.

Focal Project Results: Burntwood-Langenkamp Wetland Conservation Area (BWLK)

- Sampling Locations**
- 01. Burntwood Creek
 - 02. Settling Pool
 - 03. Overland Drainage
 - 04. 1st Flat
 - 05. Outflow
 - 06. Overland Pool A

Figure 9.2. Aerial image of approximate location of sampling for water and soil samples and discrete manual measurements of water depth and physicochemical measurements at Burntwood-Langenkamp Wetland Conservation Area Project. The legend provides a brief description of each sampling location.

Hydrology

The wetland is a single flow path that is fully inundated during Burntwood Creek high flow events or when the pump is on during summer. During low flow events/no pump, the wetland exists as a series of pools (depth > 1m) separated by intermittently flooded flats (depth < 1m). Water depth loggers (Onset HOBO[®]) were deployed in two locations: the Inflow Culvert and the Outflow, to determine respective discharge. The sensor measuring inflow is placed near the Settling Pool to capture discharge from the pump and inflow notch. and the second sensor was placed in the outflow AgriDrain water control structure where outflow discharge can be calculated using a simple flat weir equation (Figure 9.3).

Focal Project Results: Burntwood-Langenkamp Wetland Conservation Area (BWLK)

Figure 9.3. Average daily water depth (ft) and discharge (gallons per day or GPD) at the wetland outflow of the Burntwood-Langenkamp Project (i.e., sampling location 5). Water depth at the Outflow was measured using an Onset HOBO® (MX2001) in an AgriDrain and translated to discharge. On days when the outflow discharge is zero, the inflow discharge was equivalent (0 GPD), meaning no water from Burntwood Creek was entering or being treated by the wetland. The different stoplog heights (7, 14 or 21 inches) in the AgriDrain throughout the year are indicated by the colors in the legend. Note that the overflow discharge (secondary y-axis) is represented in millions (M) of gallons per day.

Sampling Location Water Depths

Among routinely sampled surface water locations (Figure 9.2), Burntwood Creek had the highest average and greatest range of discrete, manually measured surface water depths (Figure 9.4). The Overland Drainage sampling location had the lowest average water depth, as expected, due to water only being present during infrequent storm runoff events (Figure 9.4). Manual, discretely

measured water depths are not representative of true depths at the site. Water depths measured at sampling locations only represent the water depths from where the water sample was collected. Average water depths are likely greater due to not being able to reach the middle of certain wetland features.

Surface Water Nutrient Concentrations

Outflow DRP concentrations (0.029 ± 0.1 mg P/L) were 78% lower than Burntwood Creek inflow concentrations (0.134 ± 0.2 mg P/L) indicating the DRP load was being reduced throughout the wetland (Table A2.4, Figure 9.5). Among routinely sampled surface water locations, average DRP and TP concentrations were lowest for the 1st Flat (0.1 and 0.149 mg P/L, respectively), a sampling location three fourths of the way through the series of wetland pools (Table A2.4, Figure 9.2).

Weekly sampling revealed that TP and DRP concentrations were highly variable in Burntwood Creek source water and locations within the wetland (TP: 0.013–1.429 mg P/L, DRP: 0–1.01 mg P/L), and were punctuated by high concentrations associated with high flow events (Figure 9.3, Figure 9.5). Average DRP concentrations were the highest in the fall (0.109 mg P/L) and average TP concentrations were highest in winter (0.36 mg P/L), coinciding with high-flow, large storm events delivering P from the surrounding agricultural landscape during fall and winter (Table A2.5).

Average NO_x and TN concentrations (6.43 and 8.53 mg N/L, respectively) were greater in Burntwood Creek (near Project inflow) than in any sampling location within the Project. Comparing Burntwood Creek to the Outflow, average NO_x and TN concentrations were 75% and 49% lower at the Outflow (Table 9.1). Average NO_x and TN concentrations were the greatest in the spring (5.569 and 8.112 mg N/L, respectively) and lowest in the fall (0.037 and 2.34 mg N/L, respectively, Table A2.7).

Soil Nutrient Status

Average Mehlich 3-extractable phosphorus (M3-P) iron (M3-Fe), and aluminum (Al) concentrations were greatest at the Outflow (58.408 mg P/kg, 164.588 mg Fe/kg, and 524.787 mg Al/kg, Table A10). The 1st Flat had a low average of M3-P (1.878 mg P/kg) while also having low M3-Fe and M3-Al concentrations (30.069 mg Fe/kg and 197.161 mg Al/kg). phosphate sorption capacity (SPSC) values throughout the wetland were positive, indicating soils had the capacity to sorb phosphate (Figure 9.6). The 1st Flat had the lowest soil SPSC of all sampling locations (22.424 mg P/kg, Table A2.10).

Focal Project Results: Burntwood-Langenkamp Wetland Conservation Area (BWLK)

Figure 9.4. Boxplots displaying variability in discrete, manually measured surface water depths (in centimeters) across sampling locations at the Burntwood-Langenkamp Wetland Conservation Area Project. Depths were measured approximately monthly from 2021–2023. For each boxplot, the thick line represents the median (middle) surface water depth across all measurements. The boxes indicate the value range for 50% of the measured depths and the whiskers show the spread of depth values that are outside the 50% of the data points. Each overlying point represents individual water depth measurements and colors denote the season in which the measurement was taken, as indicated in the legend.

Focal Project Results: Burntwood-Langenkamp Wetland Conservation Area (BWLK)

Figure 9.5. Time series of dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP, top panel) and total phosphorus (TP, bottom panel) concentrations in surface water samples collected at the Burntwood-Langenkamp Wetland Conservation Area Project from 2021–2023. Each symbol represents one sample point, colors denote the sampling locations, and shapes indicate the general category of the sampling locations, as indicated in the legend. Values below detection limit were replaced with zero. Connected circles represent samples collected within 30 days of each other.

Focal Project Results: Burntwood-Langenkamp Wetland Conservation Area (BWLK)

Table 9.1. Summarized surface water nitrogen concentrations for the Burntwood-Langenkamp Wetland Conservation Area Project. Values are reported as mean ± standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Nitrate+Nitrite (NO_x), total ammonia (NH₃) and total nitrogen (TN) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	Nitrate+Nitrite (mg N/L)			Total Ammonia (mg N/L)			Total Nitrogen (mg N/L)		
	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
01. Burntwood Creek	6.43 ± 8.2	88 (22)	0–35.34	0.09 ± 0.1	60 (0)	0–0.61	8.53 ± 9.4	88 (0)	0.62–65.75
02. Settling Pool	1.971 ± 3.7	79 (34)	0–15.75	0.051 ± 0.1	53 (0)	0–0.43	4.655 ± 4.8	79 (0)	0.65–24.57
03. Overland Drainage	1.102 ± 2.4	14 (7)	0–6.85	0.029 ± 0	9 (0)	0–0.08	3.605 ± 2.7	14 (0)	0.85–9.78
04. 1st Flat	1.507 ± 2.9	40 (14)	0–12.77	0.023 ± 0	14 (0)	0–0.06	3.879 ± 4.1	40 (0)	1.1–22.9
05. Outflow	1.62 ± 2.7	56 (19)	0–12.16	0.097 ± 0.1	31 (0)	0–0.54	4.33 ± 3.6	58 (0)	0.46–19.8
06. Overland Pool A	0.561 ± 1.6	26 (9)	0–6.12	0.039 ± 0	11 (0)	0–0.16	2.506 ± 1.7	26 (0)	0.73–7.77

Focal Project Results: Burntwood-Langenkamp Wetland Conservation Area (BWLK)

Figure 9.6. Soil Phosphate Sorption Capacity (SPSC) throughout the Burntwood-Langenkamp Wetland Conservation Area Project. Each circle denotes an approximate sampling location and is annotated with the mean SPSC for spatially clustered soil samples (0–5 cm). The number of samples in each cluster is shown in white font below the circles. The color of the circle indicates the range of SPSC values, as indicated in the legend. Negative SPSC values indicate potential for soils to release phosphate, while positive values indicate soils have capacity to sorb phosphate, based on Mehlich 3 extractions of P, Fe, and Al.

Vegetation

Nutrient Storage

When the Burntwood-Langenkamp Project was first surveyed for vegetation in 2023, one year after Project completion, there was relatively little plant biomass ($238.4 \pm 240.31 \text{ g/m}^2$, Table C2.3). Other restoration Projects averaged five times this amount of biomass by the second or third year of restoration, so biomass is likely to increase over time at this Project as well. These low biomass values were one reason for the relatively low nutrient storage in vegetation in the first year following construction, but low biomass is typical of early restoration vegetation storage values at other Focal Projects (49 lbs. P and 161 lbs. N, Appendix Table 15.1). Consistent with many other Focal Projects, the high biomass of Cattail (*Typha sp.*) contributed to significant phosphorus (Figure 9.9) and nitrogen storage (Figure 9.10), despite its low nutrient concentration (Figure 9.8). Wetland species that have been important to nutrient storage in other wetlands were largely absent or only found in relatively low abundances at this early stage of restoration (Table C2.2) but may develop in subsequent years.

Plant Diversity

Because of the age of the Burntwood-Langenkamp Project and potentially due, in part, to the low water depths in the Project during year 2023, many species sampled were upland plants (Figure 9.11, Figure 9.8) which will likely decrease as the Project progresses. In the first year of wetland restoration, researchers generally expect to observe non-native, adventive annual species colonize Projects. Moving into years two, three, and beyond, the seeded native perennial species will start to establish themselves and make more distinct vegetation patches.

Planting Details

Following construction, the Burntwood-Langenkamp Project was seeded in spring 2022 with seed mixes sourced from Star Seed Inc. Mixes included a Diverse Species mix (CRB # 10 CP 42), a Muck mix (IN Mix 3), and a Floodplain mix (IN Mix 5). Bulbs were planted in fall 2022. During the 2023 vegetation survey, species seeded at the site were observed at low abundances (Table C2.2) and are expected to become more abundant in the coming years.

Table 9.2 Tentative initial estimates of nutrient stocks stored in wetland vegetation at Burntwood-Langenkamp Wetland Conservation Area in 2023. Confidence intervals for these estimates are still in progress.

Nutrient	Wetland Vegetation Stock Estimate (lbs.)
P	49
N	161

Figure 9.7. Drone imagery of Burntwood-Langenkamp Wetland Conservation taken in 2023 with outlined vegetation patches. Patches are used to calculate wetland vegetation nutrient storage estimates.

Focal Project Results: Burntwood-Langenkamp Wetland Conservation Area (BWLK)

Figure 9.8. Boxplots showing measurements of vegetation nutrient concentration (%) for each species collected in 2022 at Burntwood-Langenkamp Wetland Conservation. Boxplots show the first quartile, median, and third quartile. A key for Wetland Indicator Status (WIS) codes can be found in Table C1.1.

Figure 9.9. Estimated mean species P density (g/m²) from vegetation biomass and nutrient concentration data collected at Burntwood-Langenkamp Wetland Conservation Area in 2023. Error bars represent standard error and are only present when more than one sample of a given species was taken. A key for Wetland Indicator Status (WIS) codes can be found in Table C1.1.

Focal Project Results: Burntwood-Langenkamp Wetland Conservation Area (BWLK)

Figure 9.10. Estimated mean species N density (g/m²) from vegetation biomass and nutrient concentration data collected at Burntwood-Langenkamp Wetland Conservation Area in 2023. Error bars represent standard error and are only present when more than one sample of a given species was taken. A key for Wetland Indicator Status (WIS) codes can be found in Table C1.1.

Table 9.3. Calculated measures of diversity in vegetation at Burntwood-Langenkamp Wetland Conservation Area including (a) species richness (number of species encountered), the Simpson’s Index of Diversity (0–1; higher numbers indicate increased diversity), and (b) the floristic quality assessment index (FQAI) which uses the coefficient of conservatism of observed species to quantify habitat quality. Further information on these metrics can be found in the Vegetation Method Overview.

Diversity Metric	2023 Result
Species Richness	25
Simpson’s Index of Diversity	0.266
FQAI	11

Figure 9.11. Descriptive statistics for vegetation community composition at Burntwood-Langenkamp Wetland Conservation Area in 2023 including (a) Wetland Indicator Status (WIS) in the Midwest region and (b) Ohio vegetation status. Categories are defined using the Ohio EPA Flora List. Morphospecies may fall into the NA or ND category when identifications are not at the species taxonomic level (e.g., when they are immature) or because that species is not defined for either the WIS or OH Status in the Ohio EPA species list. A key for Wetland Indicator Status (WIS) codes can be found in Table C1.1.

Sediment-Surface Water Nutrient Exchange Rates

Measurements of nutrient exchange within representative sediment cores can be used to estimate nutrient retention or release rates across a pool or Project where applicable. The sediments nearest the wetland inflow of Burntwood-Langenkamp retained Dissolved Reactive Phosphorus (DRP) and nitrate+nitrite (NO_x) at the highest rates of all sampling locations (Figure 9.12). The sediments near the wetland outflow, however, had minimal nutrient exchange with the overlying water. The Upper Stream (upper portion of meandering marsh) sediments released DRP, but the magnitude of DRP flux was small relative to other Projects and more variable across replicates (0.14–1.52 mg P/m²/day) compared to the Lower Stream, Wetland Inflow, and Wetland Outflow features.

Researchers measured sediment-surface water nutrient exchange rates using triplicate intact cores collected from four representative locations within the Project: Wetland Inflow, Lower Stream, Wetland Outflow, and Upper Stream incubated in flow-through systems following the

approach of McCarthy et al., 2015⁶. Currently, the intact sediment core incubation protocol is only equipped to sample sediment from inundated areas of the Project. Future development of the methods will expand researcher’s ability to estimate nutrient exchange in upland or intermittently dry areas of the Project as well.

Figure 9.12. Sediment-water nutrient exchange in four areas of Burntwood-Langenkamp measured via intact sediment core incubations. Bar plots represent nutrient flux at each pool averaged between flux measurements from three cores (black circles) taken within the respective pool. Positive values indicate release of nutrients from the sediment to the surface water. Negative values indicate retention of nutrients from surface water to the sediment. Error bars represent standard error. Note the change in magnitude and direction of the y-axis across the two nutrient panels.

Nutrient Load Calculation

Result- In 2023, the Burntwood-Langenkamp Wetland Conservation Area reduced loads of all major measured nutrients before moving to Grand Lake St. Marys. From January to September

⁶ McCarthy, M. J., Newell, S. E., Carini, S. A., & Gardner, W. S. (2015). Denitrification Dominates Sediment Nitrogen Removal and Is Enhanced by Bottom-Water Hypoxia in the Northern Gulf of Mexico. *Estuaries and Coasts*, 38(6), 2279–2294. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12237-015-9964-0>

Focal Project Results: Burntwood-Langenkamp Wetland Conservation Area (BWLK)

2023, DRP and TP loads from Burntwood Creek were reduced by approximately 20 and 33 lbs. of P, respectively. NO_x and TN loads from Burntwood Creek were reduced by approximately 5,500 and 5,900 lbs. N, respectively. Seasonally, NO_x and TN load reductions were greatest in the winter compared to spring and summer. There was a slight net export of TP (–6.81 lbs. P) in the spring, but overall, net TP loads were reduced annually.

Estimation Method- Nutrient load reduction estimations for SRP, NO_x, TP, and TN were calculated using continuous depth measurements at the outflow and nutrient concentrations from weekly surface water samples.

Volume- A continuously logging sensor (Onset HOB0[®]) deployed in an AgriDrain at the outflow records water depth every 30 mins. An average daily depth is calculated and translated to discharge using a simple flat weir equation:

For 24” control structures,

$$\text{if } H \leq 0.27W: Q = 3.19924 \cdot (W - 0.74 \cdot H) \cdot H^{1.48}$$

$$\text{or if } H > 0.27W: Q = 3.0318 \cdot W \cdot H^{1.37},$$

where H is the height of water above the stop log in inches, W is the width of the weir in inches, and Q is the flow rate over the weir in gallons per minute. Researchers conservatively estimate the inflow discharge is equal to the measured outflow discharge (Figure 9.3), which may be underestimating nutrient load reduction because actual inflow discharge is likely greater than the outflow discharge.

Concentration- Surface water samples were collected weekly all year round from the six sampling locations (Figure 9.2). Difference in nutrient concentration between Burntwood Creek (inflow) and Outflow sampling locations was multiplied by average daily discharge to get reduction of nutrient load. This approach assumes the concentrations remained the same between approximately weekly sampling events.

Monitoring Considerations & Future Efforts

To improve monitoring surface water inflow and outflow discharges for water balance and nutrient budgeting, researchers will target direct measures of flow rates during high flow events to predict discharge volumes more accurately from water depth measurements. Starting in 2024, groundwater will be monitored from three groundwater monitoring wells. Groundwater monitoring will include water depth monitoring and sampling for nutrient concentrations. As of now, it is assumed the influence of groundwater on the site is negligible due to the surrounding land being tile drained agricultural field. If groundwater is present, the nutrient load reduction calculations can be refined to reflect the impact of groundwater on the Project.

Forder Bridge Floodplain Reconnection (FORB)

Project Overview

Paulding County | Maumee River Watershed

Project size: 54 Acres

Partners: Black Swamp Conservancy

ODNR Description: “This Project involves wetland restoration on a 54-acre parcel adjacent to the Maumee State Scenic River in Paulding County. Restoration actions include installing a series of passive treatment wetlands along an agricultural drainage, recontouring stream banks to reconnect the Maumee River to its floodplain and installing riffle grade control structures to reduce nearby streambank erosion. As a result of this Project, water quality will be improved, and wildlife habitat will be expanded.”⁷

Nutrient Load Reduction Assessment

Monitoring in 2023 indicates the Forder Bridge Floodplain Reconnection Project (hereafter Forder Bridge Project) retained an estimated 4–45 lbs. P of total phosphorus (TP) and 22–290 lbs. N of total nitrogen (TN). Newly established plants in the system stored an estimated total of 274 lbs. of P and 1050 lbs. of N. Soils throughout the Project have capacity to sorb phosphate, except for samples from a single location on the banks of the Maumee River. Some soil collected from the wetland retained dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP) from surface waters, while others released DRP into surface waters. Sediments either had no net effect on nitrate+nitrite (NO_x) or retained NO_x, and either had minimal effect on surface water total ammonia (NH₃) or released NH₃ into surface waters, based on experiments of field-collected, lab-incubated soils cores.

Management Considerations

The Forder Bridge Project primarily removes nutrients from a subsurface tile drain that drains agricultural fields. The Maumee River rarely, if ever, floods this wetland, and thus the project does not function as a floodplain wetland. The amount of precipitation needed to generate flow into the wetland through the tile drain depends on previous soil moisture.

Researchers are not certain of the total nutrient load removed by the Forder Bridge Project because it is difficult to estimate the area of land that drains into the wetland. Estimates of the area draining into the wetland area differ depending on if they are based on surface topography or assessment by drainage engineers (see below, *Forder Bridge Wetland Nutrient Budget Calculation*).

Aside from the main central treatment train of wetland pools, other features in this Project receive minimal, if any, nutrient-laden source water to treat. Two sets of depressional wetland pools receive only surface runoff from within the Project boundaries. A third set of wetland

⁷ “Forder Bridge Floodplain Reconnection.” h2.ohio.gov. Ohio Departments of Natural Resources, Agriculture, and Environmental Protection, March 4, 2024. <https://h2.ohio.gov/Project/forder-bridge/>

pools adjacent to the Maumee River are intended as floodplain pools but are positioned at a relatively high elevation (~6 feet above the river). These pools are flooded only when the Maumee is near its highest stage (~19 feet at the USGS gage Maumee River at Antwerp OH - 04183500⁸), which was observed only once in 2023.

Sampling Approach

Construction at the Forder Bridge Project was completed in 2021. Routine Monitoring began in 2022. There are four pool complexes at this Project, all sampled monthly for surface water when water was present, with some variation depending on hydrologic structure, as outlined below. The Maumee River is also sampled, including physicochemical measurements to compare the river to the wetland features.

Depressional Pools- Wetland Complex 1 and Wetland Complex 3 (Sampling locations 01–03 and 05–08, Figure 10.1) consist of isolated depressional pools. Complex 1 has three pools on the north side of the Project at an elevation above the Maumee River floodplain, and surface runoff from the meadow at a higher elevation sloping down to these pools is expected to be their primary source of water. Complex 3 is a set of four isolated depressional pools east of Stream 1 that are likely to receive surface runoff from the meadow to the east which slopes down to these pools and may be influenced by groundwater. Water samples are collected from each pool.

Floodplain Wetland- Wetland Complex 2 (Sampling location 04, Figure 10.1), west of Complex 1 is expected to function as a floodplain wetland but rarely floods due to its high elevation about 6 feet above the bank of the Maumee River. It only has standing water when the Maumee River is above about 19 feet at the USGS gage Maumee River at Antwerp OH – 04183500.

Treatment Train- Wetland Complex 4 (Sampling locations 09–14, Figure 10.1) is a set of four wetland pools in a treatment train flow path connected in series starting with a pool that receives agricultural drainage from outside the Project area from the SW Tile Outlet. Water flows from pool to pool and exits the fourth pool into Stream 1. Stream 1 meanders through woods north and northeast, ultimately flowing into the Maumee River. There are two other somewhat isolated pools in this complex, Pools E and F (Sample locations 13–14), that likely receive surface runoff from the surrounding area. Water samples and physicochemical parameters are measured at the inlets and outlets of each of the Wetland Complex 4 pools. Samples are collected, and water velocity and water depth are measured in the culvert (SW Tile Outlet) when water is present.

Vegetation surveys for community composition occurred at the Forder Bridge Project in August 2021, June and July 2022, and August 2023 (Table C3.1). Sampling of vegetation for above- and belowground biomass and nutrient concentrations occurred in August 2021 and July 2022. For the sampling year 2022, the vegetation team surveyed and sampled Forder Bridge intensively to better understand species richness and diversity and determine an ideal sampling strategy for this Project and other Projects in the H2Ohio program.

⁸ “Maumee River at Antwerp OH - 04183500.” [waterdata.usgs.gov](https://waterdata.usgs.gov/monitoring-location/04183500). U.S. Department of Interior.
<https://waterdata.usgs.gov/monitoring-location/04183500>

Focal Project Results: Forder Bridge Floodplain Reconnection (FORB)

To measure sediment-water nutrient exchange at the Forder Bridge Project, researchers collected and incubated four intact sediment cores from locations representative of each major pool system.

The Forder Bridge Project was surveyed in 2022 for hydrogeophysical measurements to characterize subsurface soil and water characteristics, including Ground Penetrating Radar, Electromagnetic Induction, Electrical Resistivity Tomography, and soil moisture content, pH, soil organic matter, and porosity.

Sampling Locations

01. Wetland Complex 1 Pool A
02. Wetland Complex 1 Pool B
03. Wetland Complex 1 Pool C
04. Wetland Complex 2
05. Wetland Complex 3 Pool A
06. Wetland Complex 3 Pool B
07. Wetland Complex 3 Pool C
08. Wetland Complex 3 Pool D
09. Wetland Complex 4 Pool A
10. Wetland Complex 4 Pool B
11. Wetland Complex 4 Pool C
12. Wetland Complex 4 Pool D
13. Wetland Complex 4 Pool E
14. Wetland Complex 4 Pool F
15. SW Tile Outlet
16. Maumee River
17. Stream 1
18. Stream 2

Figure 10.1. Aerial image of approximate location of sampling for water and soil samples and discrete manual measurements of water depth and physicochemical measurements at Forder Bridge Floodplain Reconnection Project. The legend provides a brief description of each sampling location.

3D Hydrodynamic Model

Hydrodynamic model development for the Forder Bridge Project began in 2023. Based on the preliminary tests, the three-dimensional (3D) model being developed captures key hydrologic processes that drive the water and nutrient movement along the stream channels at the Project (Figure 10.2). The preliminary results allow us to draw tentative surface water flowlines (Figure 10.3), which provide information about the flow patterns and drainage features of the Project.

Figure 10.2. (Left) Overview of the four wetland complexes at the Forder Bridge Project. (Right) Hydrodynamic and transport preliminary test results, illustrating (Top) how water depth may change across the Project’s primary flow path through time and (Bottom) how solute concentration changes as water moves across the Project’s primary flow path. Cooler/blue colors indicate smaller values, warmer/red colors indicate larger values.

Figure 10.3. Surface water flowlines (lines in black with arrowheads) at the Forder Bridge Project derived from a preliminary model run. Note that the flowlines (directions and paths)

could change under different hydrologic conditions. Hydraulic head (Head) indicates the potential energy for water movement (in meters above sea level); cooler/blue colors indicate lower head values and warmer/red colors indicate higher potential for water movement.

Sampling Location Water Depths

Floodplain Pools- Water was rarely present in the floodplain Complex 2 wetland (0–10 cm) because it only receives significant water when the Maumee River rises at least 6 feet above its usual bank, which occurred only once in 2023 (Figure 10.5, Table A3.2).

Depressional Pools and Treatment Train- The wetland pools at this Project were generally seasonally inundated; they filled with water over winter (up to 50 cm in the treatment train) and spring then became dry (0 cm in many pools, average 7 cm overall) through the summer and fall (Table A3.3), experiencing drastic changes in depth and inundation extent in relatively short time periods (see photos, Figure 10.4). 2023 was an especially dry year, so some pools that would otherwise have remained inundated year-long became dry (i.e., treatment train wetland Complex 4, which had wide variability of water depth values (0–50 cm across time, Figure 10.5).

Water depth measurements were taken at sampling locations within pools, not always at the deepest point within pools until fall 2023 when markers were installed at the deepest locations for measuring water depths.

Figure 10.4. Images of Pool D in the treatment train of Wetland Complex 4 at Forder Bridge in May (left) and June (right) of 2023, showing drastic changes in water depth in just one month.

Focal Project Results: Forder Bridge Floodplain Reconnection (FORB)

Figure 10.5. Boxplots displaying variability in discrete, manually measured surface water depths (in centimeters) across sampling locations at the Forder Bridge Floodplain Reconnection Project. Depths were measured approximately monthly from 2021–2023. For each boxplot, the thick line represents the median (middle) surface water depth across all measurements. The boxes indicate the value range for 50% of the measured depths and the whiskers show the spread of depth values that are outside the 50% of the data points. Each overlying point represents individual water depth measurements and colors denote the season in which the measurement was taken, as indicated in the legend.

Surface Water Nutrient Concentrations

Depressional Pools- Water in the depressional pools of Complexes 1 and 3 consisted primarily of surface runoff from the meadow to the south and east; the P content of this water was relatively low (DRP: 0.02–0.08 mg P/L, TP: 0.1–0.7 mg P/L, Table A3.4), as was the N content

(NO_x: 0.05–0.2 mg N/L, NH₃: 0.01–0.04 mg N/L, TN: 0.8–1.8 mg N/L,...). Because the concentrations of total nutrients (TP, TN) were higher than dissolved (DRP, NH₃, NO_x), this suggests that organic or particulate forms of N and P were potentially important contributors of nutrients.

Floodplain Pools-Water was only collected once from the rarely flooded floodplain pools in Complex 2 (February 2023). Average surface water TP from the floodplain pool (0.4 mg P/L) was similar to concentrations in the episodic source water, the Maumee River (~0.2 mg P/L) and greater than all other sampling locations (average ~0.1 mg P/L across all other locations).

Treatment Train- Researchers expected elevated nutrient concentrations in the water of the SW Tile Outlet sampling locations, given drainage of agricultural land. However, only about half of the sampling visits during the monitoring period occurred when there was sufficient water flow to sample the SW Tile Outlet (sample size = 6 for SW Tile Outlet, sample size = ~15 for the subsequent treatment train pools in Complex 4). Relative to the SW Tile Outlet, treatment train Complex 4 pools had similar DRP concentrations (~0.05 mg P/L, Table A4) and similar TP concentrations (~0.5 mg P/L, Table A3.4). Though there was little difference in concentrations across locations for each P surface water metric, load at the start and end of the treatment train pools may vary due to differences in water volume.

Comparing the isolated wetland pools (sampling locations from Complex 1 and Complex 3) to the treatment train pools (Complex 4), there was a general trend of similar DRP across all pools (~0.05 mg P/L, Table A3.4), whereas TP concentrations were higher in the treatment train pools (~0.5 mg P/L) than in the isolated wetland pools (~0.3 mg P/L). The differences in TP may be related to differences in source water, as treatment train pools receive water from the SW Tile Outlet and each other, but isolated pools receive only surface water runoff from within the Project.

Soil Nutrient Status

Soils throughout this Project had the capacity to sorb phosphate, as indicated by Soil Phosphate Sorption Capacity (SPSC, Figure 10.7). Soil in the isolated Wetland Complexes 1 and 3 had high Soil Phosphate Storage Capacity (SPSC, 94–159 mg P/kg, Figure 10.7). Complexes 1 and 3 receive primarily surface water runoff from the meadow in this Project, so the capacity to sorb phosphate may remain high, as researchers expect low nutrient concentrations in the water that enters these pools. On the other hand, the treatment train wetlands had moderate SPSC (57–114 mg P/kg), and soils at the SW Tile Outlet had low (16 mg P/kg) SPSC, consistent with these sampling locations receiving nutrient-rich tile drainage water (in times of high flow, which again were relatively few in 2023). It is notable that the capacity to sorb phosphorus generally increases with distance from the SW Tile Outlet (Figure 10.7).

Focal Project Results: Forder Bridge Floodplain Reconnection (FORB)

Figure 10.6. Time series of dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP, top panel) and total phosphorus (TP, bottom panel) concentrations in surface water samples collected at the Forder Bridge Floodplain Reconnection Project from 2021–2023. Each symbol represents one sample point, colors denote the sampling locations, and shapes indicate the general category of the sampling locations, as indicated in the legend. Values below detection limit were replaced with zero. Connected circles represent samples collected within 30 days of each other.

Focal Project Results: Forder Bridge Floodplain Reconnection (FORB)

Table 10.1. Summarized surface water nitrogen concentrations for the Forder Bridge Floodplain Reconnection Project. Values are reported as mean ± standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Nitrate+Nitrite (NO_x), total ammonia (NH₃) and total nitrogen (TN) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	Nitrate+Nitrite (mg N/L)			Total Ammonia (mg N/L)			Total Nitrogen (mg N/L)		
	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
01. Wetland Complex 1 Pool A	0.07 ± 0.1	15 (6)	0–0.39	0.012 ± 0	17 (12)	0–0.11	0.804 ± 0.5	15 (0)	0.16–1.84
02. Wetland Complex 1 Pool B	0.06 ± 0.1	11 (3)	0–0.14	0.02 ± 0	11 (7)	0–0.13	0.847 ± 0.6	11 (0)	0.3–1.9
03. Wetland Complex 1 Pool C	0.042 ± 0.1	24 (9)	0–0.19	0.01 ± 0	24 (20)	0–0.08	0.783 ± 0.7	24 (0)	0.04–3.77
04. Wetland Complex 2	0.106 ± NA	1 (0)	0.11–0.11	0.051 ± NA	1 (0)	0.05–0.05	0.79 ± NA	1 (0)	0.79–0.79
05. Wetland Complex 3 Pool A	0.053 ± 0.1	12 (5)	0–0.16	0.013 ± 0	12 (9)	0–0.07	0.948 ± 0.6	11 (0)	0.04–2.31
06. Wetland Complex 3 Pool B	0.056 ± 0.1	8 (4)	0–0.15	0.042 ± 0.1	8 (6)	0–0.29	0.932 ± 0.5	7 (1)	0–1.62
07. Wetland Complex 3 Pool C	0.072 ± 0.1	10 (4)	0–0.21	0.01 ± 0	10 (7)	0–0.07	1.572 ± 2.4	8 (0)	0.08–7.37
08. Wetland Complex 3 Pool D	0.106 ± 0.2	19 (6)	0–0.99	0.445 ± 1.9	19 (12)	0–8.21	1.773 ± 4	16 (0)	0.05–16.63
09. Wetland Complex 4 Pool A	0.181 ± 0.4	16 (5)	0–1.58	0.019 ± 0	16 (12)	0–0.12	2.279 ± 1.3	14 (0)	0.11–5.86
10. Wetland Complex 4 Pool B	0.285 ± 0.6	16 (6)	0–2.11	0.036 ± 0.1	16 (10)	0–0.19	2.017 ± 1.3	14 (0)	0.11–4.87

Focal Project Results: Forder Bridge Floodplain Reconnection (FORB)

Sampling Location	Nitrate+Nitrite (mg N/L)			Total Ammonia (mg N/L)			Total Nitrogen (mg N/L)		
	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
11. Wetland Complex 4 Pool C	0.783 ± 1.9	18 (7)	0–6.99	0.016 ± 0	18 (12)	0–0.08	2.017 ± 1.4	16 (0)	0.07–5.05
12. Wetland Complex 4 Pool D	0.744 ± 1.4	19 (7)	0–5.09	0.757 ± 2.1	19 (9)	0–8.79	3.863 ± 6.3	17 (0)	0.42–27.28
13. Wetland Complex 4 Pool E	0.888 ± 1.3	6 (1)	0–2.82	0 ± 0	6 (6)	0–0	1.985 ± 1.6	6 (0)	0.12–4.34
14. Wetland Complex 4 Pool F	0.069 ± 0.1	11 (4)	0–0.16	0.102 ± 0.3	11 (7)	0–0.91	1.617 ± 1.1	10 (0)	0.58–4.44
15. SW Tile Outlet	1.092 ± 1.2	6 (2)	0–3.15	0.232 ± 0.4	6 (2)	0–0.94	2.301 ± 1.8	6 (0)	0.02–5.29
16. Maumee River	3.538 ± 3.1	17 (0)	1.08–14.31	0.037 ± 0.1	17 (9)	0–0.23	4.357 ± 3.8	16 (0)	0.12–16.1
17. Stream 1	0.876 ± 1.3	27 (4)	0–5.07	0.068 ± 0.1	27 (13)	0–0.66	1.832 ± 1.6	26 (0)	0.07–6
18. Stream 2	0.097 ± 0.1	2 (1)	0–0.19	0.08 ± 0.1	2 (0)	0.03–0.13	0.555 ± 0.2	2 (0)	0.42–0.69

Focal Project Results: Forder Bridge Floodplain Reconnection (FORB)

Figure 10.7. Soil Phosphate Sorption Capacity (SPSC) throughout the Forder Bridge Floodplain Reconnection Project. Each circle denotes an approximate sampling location and is annotated with the mean SPSC for spatially clustered soil samples (0–5 cm). The number of samples in each cluster is shown in white font below the circles. The color of the circle indicates the range of SPSC values, as indicated in the legend. Negative SPSC values indicate potential for soils to release phosphate, while positive values indicate soils have capacity to sorb phosphate, based on Mehlich 3 extractions of P, Fe, and Al. A general sketch map of the wetland pools and Complexes is located on the side of the map for reference.

Vegetation

Nutrient Storage

An estimated 78 lbs. of P and 300 lbs. of N were stored in wetland plants at the Forder Bridge Project during the 2023 growing season. There was an increase of 229 lbs. of P and 877 lbs. of N stored in wetland plants at the Forder Bridge Project between the 2021 and 2022 growing seasons (Figure 10.9). This corresponded partially to the increased vegetated wetland area due to plants spreading into unvegetated areas following the construction of the Project. The large increase in 2022 was followed by a large decrease in 2023 (–749 lbs. of N and –197 lbs. of P) making the net nutrient stock increase from 2021–2023 approximately 32 lbs. of P and 128 lbs. of N. The vegetation nutrient stock decrease in 2023 may be related to the low water year but continued monitoring will need to be conducted before conclusions may be made.

Cattail (*Typha sp.*) had the highest N and P density (mean g/m²) of any sampled morphospecies at Forder Bridge Project (Figure 10.11, Figure 10.12) despite its lower nutrient concentration relative to other species (Figure 10.10, Figure 10.10). However, Cattail (*Typha sp.*) tends to crowd out all other species, so it may not be desirable across large areas. Black-Eyed Susan (*Rudbeckia hirta*), Hairy White Oldfield Aster (*Symphotrichum pilosum*), Smartweed (*Persicaria sp.*), and Partridge Pea (*Chamaecrista fasciculata*) also had high N and P densities (Figure 10.11, Figure 10.12). These species tend to occur at lower percent cover values along with multiple other species.

Plant Diversity

Simpson's Diversity Index greatly increased from 2021 to 2022 and then declined somewhat in 2023 (Figure 10.13 b). The Floristic Quality Assessment Index (FQAI) followed a similar trend (Figure 10.13 c). FQAI was calculated using Coefficients of Conservatism (C-values) assigned to individual species by expert analysis for the region of Ohio. Higher C-values indicate that a species will only be found in relatively undisturbed or high-quality habitats (see **Vegetation Method Overview** for further information on Simpson's Diversity Index and FQAI). These metrics likely show the change of the Project as it matures from a newly seeded Project to one where species assemblages are self-sorting based on local environmental conditions. There was a consistent increase in the number of species that could be categorized according to their habitat associations over time as they matured, and this included an increase in obligate and facultative wetland species (Figure 10.13 d).

Planting Details

Following construction at Forder Bridge Project, seeding took place in late spring of 2021. Seeds were sourced from OPN Seed and Ernst Conservation Seeds. Mixes included the Mesic Tall Grass (OPNM: MTG01), Ohio Floodplain Native Seed Mix (OPNM: OFLPM02), Ernst Seeds/OBL Wetland Mix, Moist Meadow Mix (OPNM: NEOMM01), Native Short Grass Seed Mix (OPNM: MSG03), and Woodland Edge (OPNM: MWE05). Species in the seed mixes were observed during surveys starting in 2022 (Table C3.2).

Vegetation Patches at Forder Bridge Floodplain Reconnection in 2023

- Wetland Study Area Boundary
- Cattail
- Barnyard Grass
- Partridge Pea and Beggarticks
- Reed Canary Grass
- Sedges, Beggarticks, Grasses
- Smartweed and Beggarticks
- Smartweed, Beggarticks, Grasses
- Wet Meadow Mix
- Beggarticks
- Scrub
- Teasel Mix
- Tree
- Open Water

Figure 10.8. Drone imagery of Forder Bridge Floodplain Reconnection taken in 2023 with outlined vegetation patches. Patches are used to calculate wetland vegetation nutrient storage estimates.

Focal Project Results: Forder Bridge Floodplain Reconnection (FORB)

Figure 10.9. (a) Tentative initial estimates of nutrient stocks stored in wetland vegetation at Forder Bridge Floodplain Reconnection from 2021–2023. (b) Estimates of total vegetated wetland area made using Expert Patch Maps (see Figure 10.8) are shown in acres.

Figure 10.10. Boxplots showing measurements of vegetation nutrient concentration (%) for each species collected in 2022 at Forder Bridge Floodplain Reconnection. Boxplots show the first quartile, median, and third quartile. A key for Wetland Indicator Status (WIS) codes can be found in Table C1.1.

Focal Project Results: Forder Bridge Floodplain Reconnection (FORB)

Figure 10.11. Estimated mean species P density (g/m^2) from vegetation biomass and nutrient concentration data collected at Forder Bridge Floodplain Reconnection in 2022. Error bars represent standard error and are only present when more than one sample of a given species was taken. A key for Wetland Indicator Status (WIS) codes can be found in Table C1.1.

Figure 10.12. Estimated mean species N density (g/m^2) from vegetation biomass and nutrient concentration data collected at Forder Bridge Floodplain Reconnection in 2022. Error bars represent standard error and are only present when more than one sample of a given species was taken. A key for Wetland Indicator Status (WIS) codes can be found in Table C1.1.

Focal Project Results: Forder Bridge Floodplain Reconnection (FORB)

Figure 10.13. Calculated measures of diversity and descriptive statistics for vegetation at Forder Bridge Floodplain Reconnection including (a) species richness (number of species encountered), (b) the Simpson's Index of Diversity (0–1; higher numbers indicate increased diversity), (c) the Floristic Quality Assessment Index (FQAI) which uses the coefficient of conservatism of observed species to quantify habitat quality, (d) Wetland Indicator Status (WIS) in the Midwest region and (e) Ohio vegetation status. Morphospecies fell into the NA or ND category when identifications were not at the species taxonomic level (e.g., when they are immature) or because that species was not defined for either the WIS or OH Status in the Ohio EPA species list. A key for WIS codes can be found in Table C1.1 and further information on these metrics can be found in the Vegetation Method Overview.

Sediment-Surface Water Nutrient Exchange Rates

Measurements of nutrient exchange within representative sediment cores can be used to estimate nutrient retention or release rates across a pool or Project where applicable. Researchers measured sediment-surface water nutrient exchange rates using four replicate intact cores collected from four pools within each of three representative complexes within the Project (Complexes 1 and 3, isolated depressional pools along with the treatment train, Complex 4) incubated in flow-through systems following the approach of McCarthy et al., 2015. While the sediment at isolated depressional Complex 3 had DRP retention, Complex 1 neither retained nor released DRP), and treatment train Complex 4 released DRP (Figure 10.14). Although the treatment train sediments from Complex 4 had higher rates of DRP and total NH_3 release than sediments from other areas at Forder Bridge, NO_x was retained more in these complexes than other areas. Complex 4 is located near the SW Tile Outlet, which delivers agriculture runoff to the Forder Bridge Project. These sediments have the ability to take up NO_x from the surface water, but legacy DRP and total NH_3 may be driving the higher net release rates.

Currently, the intact sediment core incubation protocol is only equipped to sample sediment from inundated areas of the Project. Future development of the methods will expand researchers' ability to estimate nutrient exchange in upland or intermittently dry areas of the Project as well.

Hydrogeophysics

Hydrogeophysical data help delineate spatial variability and zones across the Forder Bridge Project and may inform a 3D hydrodynamic model. Five groundwater monitoring wells were installed in 2022 at the Forder Bridge Project.

Soil electrical conductivity varied along elevational and flow path gradients (Figure 10.15). Lower soil electrical conductivity (ECa) at the southwest tile inlet is likely due to deposition of larger sediment particles, which tend to have lower ECa than finer particles (Figure 10.15). The northern portion of the Project site is dominated by clay rich topsoil while the southern portion is dominated by sandier topsoil, and groundwater monitoring well logs from the hydrogeophysics team confirmed these results (Figure 10.16). Electrical Resistivity Tomography scans reveal that wetland pools at the Forder Bridge Project are generally underlain by coarse materials (sand and gravel), suggesting potential for meaningful interactions between surface and groundwater (Figure 10.17).

Soil samples for hydrogeophysical characterization were collected from 10 different locations across the site and at three depths. Of the 30 analyzed by the geophysical team, bulk density, soil organic matter, porosity, and soil moisture content were all shown to be moderate predictors of ECa, with R^2 values ranging from 0.32–0.61. pH was found to influence ECa with an R^2 value of 0.67 (Figure 10.18). These results show that ECa can be used to create maps showing distributions of these parameters throughout the site.

Figure 10.14. Sediment-water nutrient exchange in three main feature Complexes at the Forder Bridge H2Ohio Project measured via intact sediment core incubations. Bar plots represent nutrient flux at each wetland complex averaged between flux measurements from four cores (black circles), one taken within each pool (A–D, or A–C for Complex 1) in respective complexes. Positive values indicate release of nutrients from the sediment to the surface water. Negative values indicate retention of nutrients from surface water to the sediment. Error bars represent standard error. Note the change in magnitude and direction of the y-axis across the three nutrient panels.

Focal Project Results: Forder Bridge Floodplain Reconnection (FORB)

Figure 10.15. Soil electrical conductivity (ECa) map of the Forder Bridge Project ranging from 1–63.7 mS/m. Generally, soil conductivities were higher (denoted by warmer colors) in the upland areas except where water was flowing through constructed Wetland Complex 4. In the lowland areas near the river, conductivities were lower (denoted by cooler colors).

Focal Project Results: Forder Bridge Floodplain Reconnection (FORB)

Figure 10.16. Ground Penetrating Radar (GPR) lines 20 (top) and 15 (bottom) at the Forder Bridge Project. Line 20 near the northern portion of the site indicates three layers in the subsurface, interpreted to be clay, oxidized clay, and clay till. These interpretations were based on Monitoring Program geophysical groundwater well #4. Line 15 in the mid to southern portion of the site also showed three different layers, however their composition is slightly different. The first layer in this line was silt and oxidized clay, the next layer was slightly less oxidized silt and clay, and the third layer was clay till. Monitoring Program geophysical groundwater well #1 was used to make these interpretations. These two lines agree with the ODNR well logs surrounding the Forder Bridge Project (#435936, #208306, and #812188⁹), which show sediments coarsening towards the southern portion of the site.

⁹ “Water Well Database.” waterwells.ohiodnr.gov. Ohio Department of Natural Resources Division of Geological Survey. <https://waterwells.ohiodnr.gov/>

Figure 10.17. Select Electrical Resistivity Tomography (ERT) profiles (#5 and #6) from the Forder Bridge Project showing subsurface resistivity changes with depth. Review of ODNR well logs in the area provided valuable insight into the subsurface structure given those were much deeper boreholes. Based on these logs, it is estimated that the limestone bedrock is not visible on the ERT sections. The higher resistivity portions beginning around 12 meters (m) are more likely to be sand and gravel sediments identified in the ODNR logs (#435936, #208326¹⁰). A third ODNR log showed that the sand and gravel layer likely thinned toward the river and eventually disappeared (#812188).

¹⁰ “Water Well Database.” waterwells.ohiodnr.gov. Ohio Department of Natural Resources Division of Geological Survey. <https://waterwells.ohiodnr.gov/>

Focal Project Results: Forder Bridge Floodplain Reconnection (FORB)

Figure 10.18. Select soil sample analysis results from the Forder Bridge Project, graphed to assess the relationship between soil conductivity and (A) soil moisture content, (B) soil pH, (C) bulk density, (D) soil organic matter, (E) porosity, and (F) pore water conductivity. Since ECa is a bulk measurement of conductivity, the values on the y-axis for A, C, D, E, and F are averaged for sampling depths between 0–50cm. Porosity (B) was correlated with ECw, which is conductivity based on salinity of the water within the sample.

Table 10.2. Hydrogeophysics Sampling at Forder Bridge Project. Yellow indicates sampling has begun and is not complete, green indicates sampling is complete. X indicates a survey of respective survey-transect-collected data for Ground Penetrating Radar (GPR) and Electromagnetic Induction (EMI).

	2022	2023	2024
Ground Penetrating Radar	X		
Electrical Resistivity Tomography	8		Planned
Electromagnetic Induction	X		
Soil Samples	40		
Groundwater Monitoring Wells	5		

Nutrient Load Calculation

Result- In 2023, the Forder Bridge Project retained an estimated 4–45 lbs. of P and 22–290 lbs. of N, preventing these loads from entering the Maumee River. Researchers used multiple

approaches to estimate drainage area and estimate load reduction of the three main hydrologic structures (*Treatment Train, Depressional Pools, Floodplain*). For a detailed technical summary of the nutrient load estimate calculations, see Forder Bridge Wetland Nutrient Budget Calculation.

Treatment Train Method- The nutrient load reduction of the treatment train (Complex 4) was calculated by estimating the amount of rainfall that flowed as surface runoff and subsurface drainage through the four flow-through pools and multiplying that volume of water by concentrations taken every month at the inlet of the treatment train, and at the stream where the wetland flows into the Maumee River. Input volume estimates were based on data collected by the closest rain gage with available data (Fort Wayne Weather station, accessed via weatherunderground.com¹¹)

Uncertainties in present estimates mainly are due to 1) uncertainty in the area of land that drains into the Project, which is difficult to quantify because of the complexities of tile drainage and 2) gaps in other hydrologic data (e.g., water depths and flow rates at key locations) indicating flooding and flow rates in the different hydrologic structures of this Project.

Depressional Pool Method- Nutrient load reduction by Complexes 1 and 3 were conservatively estimated using bulk measurements of P in the water column while pools were inundated, estimating these pools removed between 1 and 2 lbs. of P in 2023. The nutrient load reduction of the isolated depressional pools represents current runoff that would have made it to the river if it were not captured by the pools. This estimate does not include the effect of the pools relative to land use change from farmlands.

Floodplain Method- Because Complex 2, the floodplain wetland, is at a high elevation and only receives water during the highest levels of the Maumee River, it is expected to have a negligible effect on P and N retention, and thus researchers assumed its contribution to net load reduction to be zero in the present calculations.

Monitoring Considerations & Future Efforts

In 2024, researchers will install water sensors and a weather station to measure the amount of water and concentration of nutrients flowing from the SW Tile Outlet culvert through the treatment train complex with higher temporal resolution than the manual measurements thus far. The land contributing runoff to that culvert has recently (January 2023) been identified by the Paulding County Soil and Water Conservation District, and researchers will use this information along with other approaches to improve drainage area delineation (see *Improving Wetland Drainage Area Estimation*). When 3D hydrodynamic modeling is complete, more accurate estimates of surface runoff volumes entering depressional pools in Complexes 1 and 3 will improve estimates of nutrient load reduction contributed by these features.

¹¹ <https://www.wunderground.com/history/daily/us/in/fort-wayne/KFWA>

Magee Marsh Turtle Creek Bay Wetland Reconnection (MAGM)

Project Overview

Ottawa County | Turtle Creek Watershed | Coastal

Project Size: 173 Acres

Partner: Erie Soil & Water Conservation District

ODNR Description: “This Project reconnected the 165-acre Turtle Creek Bay wetland within Magee Marsh to Lake Erie, with construction completed in late 2021. Structures to control the amount and depth of water in the wetland were installed to manage agricultural runoff when lake levels rise. During high flow events, upstream flow from Turtle Creek can be diverted into the wetland where excess sediments and nutrients will be captured, keeping them from flowing directly into Lake Erie.”¹²

Nutrient Load Reduction Assessment

Researchers estimate that the Magee Marsh Turtle Creek Bay Reconnection Project (hereafter Magee Marsh Project) could have retained as much as 85 lbs. P of total phosphorus (TP) and 33 lbs. P of dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP) per filling/discharge cycle (see below, *Nutrient Load Calculation*) the Turtle Creek watershed in 2023. However, the Magee Marsh Project was disconnected from nutrient sources in 2023 due to dike construction and thus did not contribute to net nutrient load reduction during this year. Plants in the wetland store as much as 10,124 lbs. of P and 40,097 lbs. of N, and soils on the margins of the wetland have capacity to sorb phosphate (Figure 10.8). Based on experiments of field-collected, lab-incubated soil cores, some sediments retained DRP from surface waters while others released DRP from soils into surface waters. Net flux of nitrate+nitrite (NO_x) was also variable. None of the sediments collected removed total ammonia (NH₃) from surface waters.

Management Considerations

The Ohio Department of Natural Resources manages the Magee Marsh Project with primary goal to provide waterfowl habitat by lowering the surface water level to <0.2 m in July and increasing to 1 m by November. Thus, water levels are highest in early spring and late fall and lowest in mid-summer. Water depth management associated with waterfowl habitat preservation and a nearby dike construction project meant that the system was not receiving inflow waters or discharging any water from the surrounding watershed with the intent of nutrient sequestration. Thus, the Magee Marsh Project Wetland was effectively isolated from Turtle Creek in 2023. The wetland could be managed more intentionally for nutrient sequestration by “cycling” Creek water through the wetland once or a few times per year, especially in spring when nutrient sequestration is most impactful for preventing harmful algal blooms in nearby Lake Erie. However, there may be trade-offs between nutrient sequestration actions and wildlife habitat

¹² “Magee Marsh Turtle Creek Bay Wetland Reconnection.” h2.ohio.gov. Ohio Departments of Natural Resources, Agriculture, and Environmental Protection, March 4, 2024. <https://h2.ohio.gov/Project/magee-marsh-turtle-creek-bay-wetland-reconnection/>

considerations. In future years, accurate and punctual reporting of management actions (e.g., Survey123, emails) is critical to elucidate nutrient retention within the wetland complex. Notification of upcoming planned management actions would be especially useful because it would allow the field team to collect data just before the action. Ideally, bathymetry is needed to determine the volume and water exchange of the entire wetland (hydrogeophysics data pending).

Sampling Approach

Routine monitoring at the Magee Marsh Project began in 2022. The objective of the sampling approach is to give researchers an understanding of nutrient gradients from west to east as Turtle Creek flows into Lake Erie and to compare surface water nutrients in Turtle Wetland and Turtle Creek (Figure 11.2). Three water control structures (WCS) are the primary connections between the diked Wetland and the surrounding watershed. Groundwater connection to the adjacent creek is assumed to be negligible.

Eight sampling locations (Figure 11.2) exist across the two main bodies of water at the Magee Marsh Project: Turtle Creek and Magee Marsh Wetland (hereafter Creek and Wetland, respectively).

- WCS1 (Locations 01 and 02) and WCS2 (Locations 06 and 07) reconnect the Creek and the Wetland under the southern dike and have sampling locations on either side (one in the Creek, one in the Wetland).
- Two sampling locations are midway between WCS1 and WCS2 (Location 03 the Creek, Location 04 in the Wetland).
- One sampling location is in the open water “center” of the wetland (Location 05).
- On the north side of the Wetland, Wetland Pump (Location 08) is used to move water into adjacent, non-H2Ohio project wetland pools.

Samples are collected from as many locations as possible on a given day twice a month. Some locations like Wetland Center (Figure 11.2) are difficult and dangerous to access and their collection is subject to personnel availability and aquatic vegetation densities. As a result, sample sizes for some locations (e.g., Wetland Center, Wetland Pump, Table 11.1) are limited.

The drone and vegetation specialty crews collaborated at Magee Marsh Project to produce a drone-classified vegetation map (Figure 11.7). This was especially important due to the large size of the Project and the difficulty of access. Methods for sampling vegetation had to be adapted to the constraints of coastal wetland sampling from a boat. Researchers surveyed only the western portion of the site in 2023. Vegetation community composition data were collected along a transect in June 2023 (Table C4.1) with simultaneous collection of drone imagery and a low-altitude flight across the vegetation transect. Community composition and aboveground biomass were subsequently sampled in August 2023 using the stratified random sampling.

To measure sediment-water nutrient exchange at the Magee Marsh Project, researchers collected and incubated intact sediment cores from locations representative of different vegetation patches found throughout the wetland. The number of cores collected from each patch varies from 3–8 based on the areal coverage of the patch (e.g., floating vegetation covers most of the wetland so

Focal Project Results: Magee Marsh Turtle Creek Bay Wetland Reconnection (MAGM)

eight cores were collected across that patch type).

In 2023, the Magee Marsh Project was outfitted with a complete sensor system network intended to provide real-time, continuous water quality and atmospheric data. These sensors have the chief objectives of reporting surface water quality (pH, dissolved oxygen, specific conductance, water temperature, and turbidity) and water level data within Turtle Wetland and Turtle Creek to supplement nutrient load calculations and support hydrologic models. Physicochemical and water depth sensors were installed at Wetland WCS1 and at a downstream site near Lake Erie while Wetland WCS2 only received physicochemical sensors. A site upstream in Turtle Creek received a water depth sensor. Upstream and downstream water depth sensors within Turtle Creek elucidate flow regimes such as seiche events or storm events with high run-off. The sensors within the Wetland are strategically placed near water control structures to investigate effluent and influent water quality and volume as the water control structures are used. Data are retrieved online in real-time and can be used by researchers to monitor and compare Wetland and Creek conditions.

Figure 11.1. (Left) WCS1 set to drain the Wetland into the Creek. To drain, the Wetland must have a greater water level than the Creek (Sep 1, 2023). (Right) Water depth sensor at WCS1 (Oct 13, 2023).

Figure 11.2. Aerial image of approximate location of sampling for water and soil samples and discrete manual measurements of water depth and physicochemical measurements at Magee Marsh Turtle Creek Bay Wetland Reconnection Project. The legend provides a brief description of each sampling location.

Hydrology

The near-continuous, automatic water depth sensor installed in June 2023 at the Wetland WCS1 sampling location shows water depths ranging from roughly 60–86 cm (Figure 11.3). In 2023, WCS1 and WCS2 were set to discharge water from the Wetland into the Creek, however, this is under the assumption that the Wetland’s water depth is greater than the Creek’s. Water depth near WCS1 was mainly influenced by precipitation and evapotranspiration until the Creek water depths surpassed Wetland water depths in October.

Focal Project Results: Magee Marsh Turtle Creek Bay Wetland Reconnection (MAGM)

Figure 11.3. Recently installed automatic sensors measure daily water depth at Wetland WCS1, shown in blue. Daily accumulated precipitation is shown in green.

Sampling Location Water Depths

Of discrete sampling locations, Wetland Center (68 ± 18 cm) and Wetland Pump (65 ± 30 cm) had deepest water, with shallower water depths (23–46 cm) near the water control structures and Half locations (Table A4.2, Figure 11.4). In both Wetland and Creek, water depths were highly variable ranging from 15–128 cm with standard deviations reaching 30 cm at Wetland Pump (Table A4.2, Figure 11.4).

It is important to note two considerations. First, these measurements are not representative of water depths within the Wetland or Creek as a whole. Manual measurements are most frequently taken near the dike road, whereas the deepest locations, such as Wetland Pump and Wetland Center, are infrequently sampled due to safety hazards. Second, manual, discrete measurements prior to the installation of water depth sensors in June 2023 must be interpreted with caution due to location imprecision, because sampling locations near the water control structures are characterized by a rocky, uneven substrate and microtopography.

Focal Project Results: Magee Marsh Turtle Creek Bay Wetland Reconnection (MAGM)

Figure 11.4. Boxplots displaying variability in discrete, manually measured surface water depths (in centimeters) across sampling locations at the Magee Marsh Turtle Creek Bay Wetland Reconnection project. Depths were measured approximately monthly from 2021–2023. For each boxplot, the thick line represents the median (middle) surface water depth across all measurements. The boxes indicate the value range for 50% of the measured depths and the whiskers show the spread of depth values that are outside the 50% of the data points. Each overlying point represents individual water depth measurements and colors denote the season in which the measurement was taken, as indicated in the legend.

Water Nutrient Concentration Results

Of all sampling locations, Wetland Center had the lowest DRP and TP concentrations (0.003 and 0.055 mg P/L respectively), but a small sample size restricts further inference and analysis (sample size = 5, Table A4.4). The highest concentrations of DRP and TP occurred in summer (0.032 and 0.144 mg P/L respectively), but differences in sample size between seasons should be noted (Table A4.5, Figure 11.5).

In 2023, it is interesting to note low concentrations of DRP and TP in surface water at the Wetland Center sampling location. The Wetland Center is likely most indicative of wetland biogeochemical processes such as sedimentation, sorption, and vegetative uptake. Other sampling locations within the Wetland skirt the perimeter where the water is shallower, and it is possible that sediments and other constituents have not yet settled out.

Creek sampling locations showed the highest mean and maximum NO_x concentrations (0.913 and 6.32 mg N/L respectively), whereas Wetland Half had the lowest mean NO_x concentration (0.033 mg N/L, Table 11.1, Table A4.6). Creek sampling locations had the greatest maximum TN concentrations (9.041 mg N/L, Table 11.1, Table A4.6). Creek WCS1 (1.988 mg N/L) and Creek Half (1.7699 mg N/L) had the highest mean TN concentrations, yet some wetland sampling locations had higher TN than Creek WCS2 (Table 11.1, Table A4.6). Besides Wetland Center and Wetland Half, there were little differences in total NH₃ concentrations across sampling locations. Wetland Half (0.04 mg N/L) and Wetland Center (0.03 mg N/L) had the lowest mean total NH₃ concentration (Table 11.1, Table A4.6). Surface water nitrogen metrics were similar in spring and summer and varied in fall (Table A4.7).

Soil Nutrient Status

Soil pH (7.2–7.5) and soil conductivity (2257–3066 μS/cm) were similar across the three Wetland sampling locations (Table A4.8). Soil phosphate sorption capacity (SPSC) values were consistently positive, indicating capacity to sorb phosphate, but on average were at the lower end of expected values (<50 mg P/kg) suggesting surveillance is important in the near-term (Figure 11.6). Wetland WCS1 had the highest SPSC (63 ± 51.2 mg P/kg), and higher Mehlich 3-extractable iron (1274.25 ± 1169.3 mg Fe/kg) compared to Wetland Half and Wetland WCS2 (Table A10). Wetland Half (9.725 ± 6.8 mg P/kg) and Wetland WCS2 (and 23.475 ± 23.3 mg P/kg) had less soil P than Wetland WCS1 (26.475 ± 23.9 mg P/kg, Figure 11.6, Table A4.10). Soil water-extractable total phosphorus was similar across Wetland sampling locations. Wetland WCS1 showed a higher concentration of water-extractable phosphate (2.153 ± 2.5 mg P/kg) compared to the other Wetland sampling locations (Table A4.12). All three Wetland sampling locations showed similar soil total nitrogen and ammonia, but Wetland WCS1 showed average soil nitrate+nitrite concentrations (11.124 ± 10.1 mg N/kg) twice that of Wetland Half (5.426 ± 5 mg N/kg) and Wetland WCS2 (4.287 ± 3.4 mg N/kg).

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Figure 11.5. Time series of dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP, top panel) and total phosphorus (TP, bottom panel) concentrations in surface water samples collected at the Magee Marsh Turtle Creek Bay Wetland Reconnection Project from 2021–2023. Each symbol represents one sample point, colors denote the sampling locations, and shapes indicate the general category of the sampling locations, as indicated in the legend. Values below detection limit were replaced with zero. Connected circles represent samples collected within 30 days of each other.

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Table 11.1. Summarized surface water nitrogen concentrations for the Magee Marsh Turtle Creek Bay Wetland Reconnection Project. Values are reported as mean ± standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Nitrate+Nitrite (NO_x), total ammonia (NH₃) and total nitrogen (TN) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	Nitrate+Nitrite (mg N/L)			Total Ammonia (mg N/L)			Total Nitrogen (mg N/L)		
	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
01. Creek WCS1	0.913 ± 1.5	25 (0)	0.02–6.15	0.101 ± 0.1	25 (0)	0.02–0.25	1.988 ± 1.8	25 (0)	0.56–8.21
02. Wetland WCS1	0.2 ± 0.8	26 (0)	0–4.12	0.08 ± 0.1	26 (0)	0.01–0.27	1.231 ± 0.9	26 (0)	0–5.43
03. Creek Half	0.827 ± 1.5	23 (0)	0.01–6.32	0.09 ± 0.1	23 (0)	0.02–0.22	1.769 ± 1.9	23 (0)	0.57–9.04
04. Wetland Half	0.033 ± 0	21 (0)	0–0.1	0.04 ± 0	21 (0)	0.02–0.14	1.325 ± 0.7	21 (0)	0–3.37
05. Wetland Center	0.043 ± 0	5 (0)	0.01–0.07	0.03 ± 0	5 (0)	0.02–0.05	1.133 ± 0.4	5 (0)	0.8–1.9
06. Creek WCS2	0.65 ± 1	23 (0)	0.02–4.04	0.084 ± 0.1	23 (0)	0.03–0.21	1.293 ± 1.2	23 (0)	0–5.44
07. Wetland WCS2	0.374 ± 0.8	31 (0)	0–3.23	0.114 ± 0.1	31 (0)	0.02–0.36	1.171 ± 0.9	31 (0)	0–4.18
08. Wetland Pump	0.092 ± 0.2	15 (0)	0–0.77	0.075 ± 0.1	15 (0)	0.01–0.18	1.081 ± 0.5	15 (0)	0.51–2.45

Focal Project Results: Magee Marsh Turtle Creek Bay Wetland Reconnection (MAGM)

Figure 11.6. Soil Phosphate Sorption Capacity (SPSC) throughout the Magee Marsh Turtle Creek Bay Wetland Reconnection project. Each circle denotes an approximate sampling location and is annotated with the mean SPSC for spatially clustered soil samples (0–5 cm). The number of samples in each cluster is shown in white font below the circles. The color of the circle indicates the range of SPSC values, as indicated in the legend. Negative SPSC values indicate potential for soils to release phosphate, while positive values indicate soils have capacity to sorb phosphate, based on Mehlich 3 extractions of P, Fe, and Al.

Vegetation

Nutrient Storage

The Magee Marsh Project stored a maximum of 40,097 lbs. of N and 10,124 lbs. of P during peak biomass in 2023 (Figure 11.8). This high stock of nutrients in the biomass is likely a combination of its large size (158 acres) and pre-established vegetation. As such, estimates of the contribution of vegetation for nutrient removal from the watershed will need to be made once there are multiple years of observations of vegetation stocks to track net change over time. Submerged aquatic vegetation (e.g., Coon’s Tail (*Ceratophyllum demersum*)) and deeply rooted aquatic vegetation (e.g., American White Waterlily (*Nymphaea odorata*)) had the highest mean biomass (Figure C4.2) observed at the Project as well as some of the highest percent

Focal Project Results: Magee Marsh Turtle Creek Bay Wetland Reconnection (MAGM)

concentrations of nutrients in their tissues (Figure 11.9). This resulted in high nutrient density for many of the wetland species in the site (Figure 11.10).

Plant Diversity

Species richness (18) was lower at this Project compared to other H2Ohio Projects (Table 11.2, Figure 7.1). This result is likely due to the limited sample size at Magee Marsh Project and possibly related to the nature of coastal wetlands which establish large monotypic patches of single species in highly inundated areas. The Floristic Quality Assessment Index (FQAI) also was the lowest of all monitored Projects (Figure 7.2) most likely because constant inundation excluded non-hydrophytic species thereby reducing diversity. More obligate vegetation was observed than any other wetland vegetation status (Figure 11.12 a), and about 44% of the species observed were native species, compared to 11% identified as adventive species (Figure 11.12 b). Using monitoring data collected in 2023 for direct comparisons of species richness and diversity between this Project and other Projects is not currently recommended as the sampling locations were limited at Magee Marsh (due to the challenges of sampling from a boat) and sampling targeted diverse vegetation patches for the purposes of collecting nutrient data about multiple species. As such, Magee Marsh Project is not included in the Program-Level vegetation diversity observations (Figure 7.1).

Planting Details

The Project at Magee Marsh Turtle Creek Bay Wetland Reconnection had well-established vegetation prior to reconnection with Turtle Creek. No seeding occurred as part of the H2Ohio wetland restoration activity.

Figure 11.7. Drone imagery of Magee Marsh Turtle Creek Bay Wetland Reconnection taken in 2023 with classified vegetation patches. Patches are used to calculate wetland vegetation nutrient storage estimates.

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Figure 11.8. Tentative initial estimates of nutrient stocks stored in wetland vegetation at Magee Marsh Turtle Creek Bay Wetland Reconnection for 2023. Confidence intervals for these estimates are still in progress. Total vegetated area for the project is estimated at 158 acres using drone-classified imagery taken in 2023 (see Figure 11.7).

Figure 11.9. Boxplots showing measurements of vegetation nutrient concentration (%) for each species collected in sampling year 2023 at Magee Marsh Turtle Creek Bay Wetland Reconnection. Boxplots show the first quartile, median, and third quartile. A key for Wetland Indicator Status (WIS) codes can be found in Table C1.1.

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Figure 11.10. Estimated mean species P density (g/m^2) from vegetation biomass and nutrient concentration data collected at Magee Marsh Turtle Creek Bay Wetland Reconnection for sampling year 2023. Error bars represent standard error and are only present when more than one sample of a given species was taken. A key for Wetland Indicator Status (WIS) codes can be found in Table C1.1.

Figure 11.11 Estimated mean species N density (g/m^2) from vegetation biomass and nutrient concentration data collected at Magee Marsh Turtle Creek Bay Wetland Reconnection for sampling year 2022. Error bars represent standard error and are only present when more than one sample of a given species was taken. A key for Wetland Indicator Status (WIS) codes can be found in Table C1.1.

Table 11.2. Calculated measures of vegetation diversity at Magee Marsh Turtle Creek Bay Wetland Reconnection; species richness (number of species encountered), the Simpson’s Index of Diversity (0–1; higher numbers indicate increased diversity), and floristic quality assessment index (FQAI) which uses the coefficient of conservatism of observed species to quantify habitat quality. Further information on these metrics can be found in the **Vegetation Method Overview**.

Diversity Metric	2023
Species Richness	18
Simpson’s Index of Diversity	0.664
FQAI	11

Figure 11.12. Descriptive statistics for vegetation community composition at Magee Marsh Turtle Creek Bay Wetland Reconnection in 2023 including (a) Wetland Indicator Status in the Midwest region and (b) Ohio vegetation status. Categories are defined using the Ohio EPA Flora List. Morphospecies may fall into the NA or ND category when identifications are not at the species taxonomic level (e.g., when they are immature) or because that species is not defined for either the WIS or OH Status in the Ohio EPA species list. A key for WIS codes can be found in Table C1.1.

Sediment-Surface Water Nutrient Exchange Rates

Measurements of nutrient exchange within representative sediment cores can be used to estimate nutrient retention or release rates across a pool or Project where applicable. The exchange of DRP and NO_x between Magee Marsh Project sediment and overlying surface water varied in direction and magnitude across different vegetation patches sampled throughout the Project (Figure 11.13). Higher rates of DRP and NO_x release were typical in patches of Hardwoods compared to other vegetation; however, Hardwoods covered a relatively small area compared to Floating and Submerged Vegetation. Both Submerged and Emergent Vegetation patches had net zero or negative fluxes of DRP and NO_x indicating equilibrium between the sediment and

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surface water or nutrient retention (respectively). Sediments across the Project either had a net zero exchange or positive (release) rate of total NH_3 , regardless of overlying vegetation.

Sampling locations for intact sediment coring were selected based on vegetation patches qualitatively mapped via remote sensing and field observations. Although intact sediment core sampling locations do match routine monitoring sample locations, the general areas were similar. For instance, “02. Wetland WCS1” was captured in “Floating Veg.” patch, “05. Wetland Center” was captured in “Submerged Veg.” patch, and “07. Wetland WCS2” was captured in “Hardwoods” patch.

Currently, the intact sediment core incubation protocol is only equipped to sample sediment from inundated areas of the Project. Future development of the methods will expand researchers’ ability to estimate nutrient exchange in upland or intermittently dry areas of the Project as well. Researchers measured sediment-surface water nutrient exchange rates using three replicate intact cores collected from five representative patches within the Project incubated in flow-through systems following the approach of McCarthy et al., 2015.

Figure 11.13. Sediment-water nutrient exchange in five vegetation patches of Magee Marsh Turtle Creek Bay Wetland Reconnection measured via intact sediment core incubations. Bar

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plots represent nutrient flux at each patch averaged between flux measurements from 3–8 cores (black circles) taken within the respective patch. Positive values indicate release of nutrients from the sediment to the surface water. Negative values indicate retention of nutrients from surface water to the sediment. Error bars represent standard error. Note the change in magnitude and direction of the y-axis across the three nutrient panels.

Figure 11.14. Magee Marsh Turtle Creek Bay Wetland Reconnection intact sediment core sampling locations for 2022 and 2023. Wetland qualitatively delineated into patches based on dominant vegetation type via remote sensing and field observations.

Nutrient Load Calculation

Results- In 2023, the Magee Marsh Project did not reduce nutrient loads from Turtle Creek. Researchers estimated the Project could retain up to 33 lbs. of DRP and 85 lbs. of TP per filling/discharge cycle if it had been connected to the Creek during times of peak P loads. A filling/discharge cycle is defined as a sequence of filling the Wetland from the Creek when Creek nutrients are high, allowing the wetland to treat the water for a period of time until nutrient concentrations are diminished through particulate settling, phosphate sorption, and N processing, and then releasing lower-nutrient water back into the Creek. Nutrient load estimates are calculated using water depth and surface water nutrient concentration data collected throughout 2023.

Volume- Differences in water depths allow researchers to calculate a volume of water: land managers estimate that the water depth in the Wetland fluctuates 1 foot when water control structures are used for habitat management and vegetative control purposes. This difference was multiplied by the surface area of the wetland (164.6 acres) to produce a hypothetical volume of 53,644,275 gallons, which would be hypothetically diverted from the Creek and into the Wetland if they had been connected. Since the Wetland area is large and walls are steep-sided, researchers assumed that the surface area change is minimal with change in depth, and assumed water depths are not lowered enough to expose the sediments.

Focal Project Results: Magee Marsh Turtle Creek Bay Wetland Reconnection (MAGM)

Concentrations- To assign a nutrient concentration to this volume of water, researchers compared the difference between two data points: the most nutrient dense Creek water and the least nutrient dense Wetland water observed in 2023. Theoretically, it is therefore possible for Creek water with a concentration of 0.22 mg P/L TP and 0.075 mg P/L DRP to be let into the Wetland via water control structures, and after biogeochemical processes, released as “clean” Wetland water into the Creek with concentrations as low as 0.02 mg P/L TP and 0.001 mg P/L DRP (Table A4.4). The difference between the Creek and Wetland water concentrations is 0.19 mg P/L TP and 0.074 mg P/L DRP, which represents the estimated nutrient load reduced.

Assigning 0.19 mg P/L TP and 0.074 mg P/L DRP to 53,644,275 gallons of water produces a load reduction estimate of 85 lbs. of P for TP and 33 lbs. of P for DRP.

Monitoring Considerations & Future Efforts

The Wetland Center is likely the most representative of surface water quality in the wetland, however the Center is the most difficult and hazardous location to access due to soft sediments, shallow water, and dense vegetation. Frequent sampling at Wetland Center could provide a better representation of average Wetland surface water conditions and because nutrient concentrations in the Center tend to be lower, would likely result in an increase in the estimated potential for the Wetland to reduce nutrient loads from Turtle Creek. However, routine sampling at Wetland Center would require construction of a boardwalk to allow sample collection at least 100 meters out into the water from the dike.

Starting in 2024, researchers use rebar and/or driveway markers to mark exact locations to record water depth measurements, as researchers identified from 2022–2023 that uneven bottom topography led to unreliable manual water depth measurements. The installation of a water surface level sensor near WCS1 drastically improved the accuracy and precision of these measurements due to the near-continuous frequency of water surface level measurement and the stationary location. However, this sensor was installed late in the water season (June 2023), thus a critical portion of the 2022–2023 water depth dataset is missing and must be supplemented with manual water depth measurements.

Future analysis of continuously monitored water quality indicators (e.g., turbidity) to predict nutrient concentrations (particularly phosphorus) will help fill gaps in nutrient concentration data because of the lack of access to the site during storm events.

Oakwoods Nature Preserve East (OAKE) and Oakwoods Nature Preserve West (OAKW)

Overview

Hancock County | Blanchard River Watershed

OAKE Project size: 65 Acres

OAKW Project size: 77 Acres

Partners: Hancock Park District

ODNR Description: “The Oakwoods Nature Preserve East is located in a former agricultural field. The area has been primarily converted into wetlands and the remaining portion will be planted as a native prairie. The Project includes restoring natural water flow to the landscape and capturing excess nutrients and sediment from nearby farmland. This is a component of a larger restoration at Hancock Park District’s Oakwoods Nature Preserve. The Oakwoods Nature Preserve Aurand Run Project [Oakwoods Nature Preserve West] is creating and restoring wetlands, woodlands and prairie in a previously farmed floodplain. Aurand Run crosses the Project area and will be reconnected to its floodplain, allowing nutrient-rich water to be treated through three acres of forested wetlands. Other Project efforts include removing underground drain tiles, enhancing wooded habitat along Aurand Run, and restoring wooded streamside habitat to expand and protect 15 acres of an existing high-quality forested wetland.”^{13,14}

Nutrient Load Reduction Assessment

Oakwoods Nature Preserve East and West (hereafter Oakwoods East and West Projects) primarily prevent nutrient export by retaining water. By evaluating the effect of converting formerly agricultural land to wetlands (assuming similar pre-wetland nutrient losses to published edge-of-field studies), researchers estimated that the Oakwoods East and West Projects annually prevent 82 lbs. P of total phosphorus (TP) from being exported to the Aurand Run watershed based on this land use change. Across both the Oakwoods East and West Projects, an estimated 4,746 lbs. of N and 1,728 lbs. of P were stored in wetland plants during the 2022 growing season. Sediments across the Oakwoods East Project had either net zero exchanges or net release of nutrients between the sediment and overlying water, as estimated using field-collected, lab-incubated soil cores. All soils measured throughout both the Oakwoods East and West Project indicated variable but positive capacity to sorb phosphate.

Management Considerations

The majority of the Oakwoods East and West Project wetland pools do not receive surface inflows, and thus are sequestering relatively small amounts of “new” nutrient loads due to a

¹³ “Oakwoods Nature Preserve Wetland Restoration Project, East.” h2.ohio.gov. Ohio Departments of Natural Resources, Agriculture, and Environmental Protection, March 4, 2024. <https://h2.ohio.gov/Project/oakwoods-nature-preserve-east/>

¹⁴ “Oakwoods Nature Preserve Wetland Restoration Project, West.” h2.ohio.gov. Ohio Departments of Natural Resources, Agriculture, and Environmental Protection, March 4, 2024. <https://h2.ohio.gov/Project/oakwoods-nature-preserve-aurand-run/>

combination of the geomorphology of the as-built Project and dryer-than-average conditions (Figure 3.1). However, after conversion to wetlands, no new nutrients are being added to the land as fertilizer, and these pools all prevent surface runoff and tile drain disruption limits subsurface runoff that occurred when this Project's site was previously agricultural land. In the Oakwoods West Project, Pool 1 was designed to function as a floodplain wetland, but as-built has a small water holding capacity relative to the flow volume of Aurand Run. Additionally, the elevation of Pool 1 is such that it is estimated to only receive water from Aurand Run at its highest levels of about six to eight feet, which was only observed once in 2023. Water depths during the last two years have been so low that there has been very little connection between Pool 1 and Aurand Run. Modifications to enhance the connection between Aurand Run and the Pool 1 floodplain wetland could potentially increase treatment of nutrient loads from Aurand Run. Four pools in the Oakwoods East Project contain direct tie drain inputs but lack discrete surface outflow, and thus essentially retain all of the nutrients delivered to them, which was estimated to be less than 1 lb. of P in 2023, due to low rainfall and clogged tiles, and their relatively small size (< 0.2 acre).

Sampling Approach

Oakwoods East and Oakwoods West are two Projects essentially sampled as one Project by the Monitoring Program. Construction was completed in 2021. Routine monitoring began in 2021 before construction of the West side was complete and before planting of vegetation.

Oakwoods East Routine Sampling

The Oakwoods East Project contains 24 constructed depressional wetland pools (Figure 12.1). Researchers sample surface water for nutrients and measure water depth monthly at fixed locations within representative pools. Pools 30, 31, 36, and 42 receive inputs from subsurface agricultural drainage. Base Crew researchers classify these pools as "Flow-In/No-Flow-Out" (FINFO). Surface water samples are collected approximately monthly from pools with standing water and surface soil samples are collected twice a year from each wetland pool. Because the tile inflows are at the bottom of the pools, direct measures of flow are challenging, therefore tile flow coming into the pool is estimated by measuring changes in water depth over discrete periods of time.

Oakwoods West Routine Sampling

Pool 1 at the Oakwoods West Project was designed as a floodplain wetland and is connected to Aurand Run, a tributary of the Blanchard River (Figure 12.2). Pool 1 also receives water from an 8-inch tile drain that delivers subsurface agricultural runoff from outside the Project. Nutrient concentration sampling and water depth measurements occur monthly in Pool 1, in addition to flood event sampling. Researchers note any surface connections to Aurand Run and any management via a water control structure connecting Pool 1 and Aurand Run. The remaining pools (Pools 2–Pool 19) are isolated depressional pools, and the sampling approach is the same as in the Oakwoods East Project.

Focal Project Results: Oakwoods Nature Preserve East (OAKE) and Oakwoods Nature Preserve West (OAKW)

Sampling Locations

- 01. Wetland Pool 20
- 02. Wetland Pool 21
- 03. Wetland Pool 22
- 04. Wetland Pool 23
- 05. Wetland Pool 24
- 06. Wetland Pool 25
- 07. Wetland Pool 26
- 08. Wetland Pool 27
- 09. Wetland Pool 28
- 10. Wetland Pool 29
- 11. Wetland Pool 30
- 12. Wetland Pool 31
- 13. Wetland Pool 32
- 14. Wetland Pool 33
- 15. Wetland Pool 34
- 16. Wetland Pool 35
- 17. Wetland Pool 36
- 18. Wetland Pool 37
- 19. Wetland Pool 38
- 20. Wetland Pool 39
- 21. Wetland Pool 40
- 22. Wetland Pool 41
- 23. Wetland Pool 42
- 24. Wetland Pool 43

Figure 12.1 Aerial image of approximate location of sampling for water and soil samples and discrete manual measurements of water depth and physicochemical measurements at Oakwoods Nature Preserve Wetland Restoration, East Project. The legend provides a brief description of each sampling location.

Sampling Locations

- 01. Wetland Pool 1
- 02. Wetland Pool 2
- 03. Wetland Pool 3
- 04. Wetland Pool 4
- 05. Wetland Pool 5
- 06. Wetland Pool 6
- 07. Wetland Pool 7
- 08. Wetland Pool 8
- 09. Wetland Pool 9
- 10. Wetland Pool 10
- 11. Wetland Pool 11
- 12. Wetland Pool 12
- 13. Wetland Pool 13
- 14. Wetland Pool 14
- 15. Wetland Pool 15
- 16. Wetland Pool 16
- 17. Wetland Pool 17
- 18. Wetland Pool 18
- 19. Wetland Pool 19
- 20. Aurand Run downstream
- 21. Aurand Run connection to P1
- 22. Aurand Run upstream

Figure 12.2 Aerial image of approximate location of sampling for water and soil samples and discrete manual measurements of water depth and physicochemical measurements at Oakwoods Nature Preserve Wetland Restoration, West Project. The legend provides a brief description of each sampling location.

Hydrology Monitoring

Considerable monitoring attention is paid to Pool 1 because it is connected to the primary watershed collection body, Aurand Run, via a cut in a berm. Across two years of monitoring, researchers have adjusted sampling and sensor deployment to respond to the drastic water level changes that can occur within and across years (Figure 12.3). Multiple water depth sensors and gages have been deployed in Pool 1 because of the need to measure depths that can change over six feet. Across the Oakwoods East and Oakwoods West Projects, staff gages have been installed for standardized water depth measurements in several pools, including a “Crowd Hydrology” collaboration with H2Ohio Students Take Action and local area schools (Figure 12.4). Most gages were added to the Crowd Hydrology website in November 2023, and citizen scientists, students, and researchers can use this tool to record changes in water depth at the Project.

Specialty Crew Sampling

Vegetation community composition surveys occurred at the Oakwoods East and West Projects in August 2021, August 2022, and July 2023 (Table C5.1, Table C6.1). Above- and belowground biomass and nutrient sampling occurred in 2022 and 2023. ‘

To measure sediment-water nutrient exchange at the Oakwoods East Project, researchers collected and incubated triplicate intact sediment cores from locations representative of two isolated depressional pools (Pool 39, Pool 40) and two “flow in - no flow out” wetland pools (Pool 30, Pool 42).

Both the Oakwoods East and West Project were surveyed in 2023 for hydrogeophysical measurements of subsurface soil and water characteristics, including Ground Penetrating Radar, Electromagnetic Induction, Electrical Resistivity Tomography, and soil infiltration tests. Hydrogeophysics data help delineate spatial variability and zones across the Project and inform a 3D hydrodynamic model. Two groundwater monitoring wells were installed in 2023.

Figure 12.3. (Left) Pool 1 facing east on September 21, 2022, showing water depths when pool is almost completely filled. (Right) Pool 1 facing north, showing extremely low water depth and newly installed staff gage on October 19, 2023 at the Oakwoods West Project.

Focal Project Results: Oakwoods Nature Preserve East (OAKE) and Oakwoods Nature Preserve West (OAKW)

Figure 12.4 Locations of Crowd Hydrology staff gages installed at Oakwoods East and Oakwoods West Projects. Source: <http://www.crowdhydrology.com/location/ohio/>

Figure 12.5. Researchers collecting soil samples in Pool 40 at the Oakwoods East Project on October 27, 2022. Also visible are stakes that mark the location of future water depth sensors and sonde deployment.

3D Hydrodynamic Model

Three-dimensional (3D) hydrodynamic models developed in 2023 for the Oakwoods East and West Projects were used to simulate dynamic changes in flooding, groundwater interactions, and nutrient transport over space and time under wet and dry climate conditions. Under these simulations, as the depth of flooding changes, the pool inundation extent and shapes change as well. Some restored depressional ponds expand and coalesce during wetter conditions and shrink and separate during drier conditions (Figure 12.6). The degree of predicted exchange between surface and groundwater also varies with climate variability, with greater predicted inputs of groundwater into pools under wetter conditions (Figure 12.7). Finally, 3D hydrodynamic models

Focal Project Results: Oakwoods Nature Preserve East (OAKE) and Oakwoods Nature Preserve West (OAKW)

can simulate the movement of nutrients through the wetland Project pools that receive agricultural drainage from seven tiles (Figure 12.8). Continued data collection, integration, and model calibration will support more accurate modeling scenarios, integrating as-monitored hydrologic and meteorological conditions.

Figure 12.6. Comparison of simulated water depths and water-body occurrence at the Oakwoods East and West Projects during (a) wet and (b) dry climatic conditions.

Figure 12.7. Comparison of simulated groundwater and surface-water interaction (i.e., flux exchange) at Oakwoods East and West Projects under (a) wet and (b) dry conditions. Note that a positive value of exchange flux indicates groundwater flow to surface domain whereas a negative value indicates surface-water outflow to groundwater.

Figure 12.8. Simulated nutrient transport at the Oakwoods East and West Project. Panel (a) shows simulated solute concentrations (e.g., DRP) shortly after the nutrients are released from the seven tiles at the Oakwoods East Project (righthand side of map), whereas panel (b) reveals how the nutrients would migrate and spread after months of continuous release of nutrients.

Sampling Location Water Depths

Water depths and water retention varied considerably among the 42 wetland pools at the Oakwoods East and West Projects (0–62 cm East, 0–350 cm West, Table A5.2, Table A6.2) across space and through time. Overall, the Project experienced a seasonal flooding regime with annual wet and dry seasons, although some pools were permanently inundated. Pools 40 and 26 had relatively deep water year-round (40 cm, 28 cm, respectively) while others held very little water at any given time (e.g., Pools 20, 23, 24 averaged 1–5 cm), and some held large amounts of water in winter and spring but gradually lost their water and became dry throughout summer and fall (e.g., Pools 30 and 39 ranged from 0–62 cm, Figure 12.9, Figure 12.10).

Three of the pools receiving tile drainage at the Oakwoods East Project (Pools, 30, 31, 42) generally had deeper water (20–50 cm) in the spring and variable water in the summer (0–50 cm, Figure 12.9). The floodplain pool, Pool 1 had the greatest variation in water depth within a single pool (0–350 cm), and it is notable two of the greatest water depths occurred in summer (Figure 12.10).

Of the isolated depressional wetland pools that do not receive tile drainage, Pools 4, 9, and 18 had higher average water depths than other pools (24 cm, 25 cm, 31 cm respectively), indicating that they held more water and for longer periods of time. Pools 2, 3, 7, 10, 15, and 17 had very low average water depths (1–3 cm), which indicated they do not hold much water or do not retain water for very long (Figure 12.9, Figure 12.10). The differences in water retention among these pools are currently ascribed to differences in shape, size, and subsurface geology.

Water depth measurements were generally taken adjacent to surface water sampling locations within pools at the start of monitoring (2021–2022). As of February 2023, water depth at Oakwoods East and West Project pools were measured at the deepest point within each pool at a consistent and marked location.

Focal Project Results: Oakwoods Nature Preserve East (OAKE) and Oakwoods Nature Preserve West (OAKW)

Figure 12.9. Boxplots displaying variability in discrete, manually measured surface water depths (in centimeters) across sampling locations at the Oakwoods Nature Preserve Wetland Restoration, East project. Depths were measured approximately monthly from 2021–2023. For each boxplot, the thick line represents the median (middle) surface water depth across all measurements. The boxes indicate the value range for 50% of the measured depths and the whiskers show the spread of depth values that are outside the 50% of the data points. Each overlying point represents individual water depth measurements and colors denote the season in which the measurement was taken, as indicated in the legend. Note: Pools 30, 31, 36, and 42 = tile drain pools

Focal Project Results: Oakwoods Nature Preserve East (OAKE) and Oakwoods Nature Preserve West (OAKW)

Figure 12.10. Boxplots displaying variability in discrete, manually measured surface water depths (in centimeters) across sampling locations at the Oakwoods Nature Preserve Wetland Restoration, West project. Depths were measured approximately monthly from 2021–2023. For each boxplot, the thick line represents the median (middle) surface water depth across all measurements. The boxes indicate the value range for 50% of the measured depths and the whiskers show the spread of depth values that are outside the 50% of the data points. Each overlying point represents individual water depth measurements and colors denote the season in which the measurement was taken, as indicated in the legend. Note: Pool 1 = “Floodplain” feature.

Surface Water Nutrient Concentrations

Surface water nutrients concentrations were very low throughout the Oakwoods East and West Projects and in most samples dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP) was <0.087 mg P/L, nitrate+nitrite (NO_x) was <0.4 mg N/L, and total ammonia (NH₃) was <0.15 mg N/L (Figure 12.11, Figure 12.12, Table 12.1, Table 12.2).

Low nutrient concentrations are typical of isolated depressional wetlands where low-nutrient precipitation is the primary water source and was similar to other projects with depressional wetlands (e.g., Fruth Nature Preserve). One notable exception, Pool 16, was due to a single spuriously high value likely due to spot contamination of a water sample by small animal activity (Figure 12.12). Total phosphorus (TP) and total nitrogen (TN) concentrations were often an order of magnitude higher than dissolved which indicated particulate and organic fractions were dominant N and P sources in these pools (Table A5.4, Table 12.1, Table A6.4, Table 12.2). .
DRP and NO_x concentrations increased following rain events in the four pools that have drainage tile inflows (maximum concentrations in pools 30, 31, 36, and 42 were 0.047–0.118 mg P/L for DRP and 0.149–0.805 mg N/L for NO_x, Table A5.4, Table A6.4).

Average TP concentrations were similar upstream and downstream of Pool 1's connection to Aurand Run (0.016 mg P/L and 0.018 mg P/L, respectively) and notably lower than Pool 1 concentrations (0.206 mg P/L, Table A6.4), and there was rarely a connection between these two water bodies. Pool 1 TP concentrations were higher than Aurand Run likely because the inflow of agricultural drainage from the tile outlet into this pool whereas Aurand Run drains primarily forested and urban land use areas (Table A6.4).

Focal Project Results: Oakwoods Nature Preserve East (OAKE) and Oakwoods Nature Preserve West (OAKW)

Figure 12.11. Time series of dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP, top panel) and total phosphorus (TP, bottom panel) concentrations in surface water samples collected at the Oakwoods Nature Preserve Wetland Restoration, East project from 2021–2023. Each symbol represents one sample point, colors denote the sampling locations, and shapes indicate the general category of the sampling locations, as indicated in the legend. Values below detection limit were replaced with zero. Connected circles represent samples collected within 30 days of each other.

Focal Project Results: Oakwoods Nature Preserve East (OAKE) and Oakwoods Nature Preserve West (OAKW)

Figure 12.12. Time series of dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP, top panel) and total phosphorus (TP, bottom panel) concentrations in surface water samples collected at the Oakwoods Nature Preserve Wetland Restoration, West project from 2021–2023. Each symbol represents one sample point, colors denote the sampling locations, and shapes indicate the general category of the sampling locations, as indicated in the legend. Values below detection limit were replaced with zero. Connected circles represent samples collected within 30 days of each other.

Focal Project Results: Oakwoods Nature Preserve East (OAKE) and Oakwoods Nature Preserve West (OAKW)

Table 12.1. Summarized surface water nitrogen concentrations for the Oakwoods Nature Preserve Wetland Restoration, East Project. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Nitrate+Nitrite (NO_x), total ammonia (NH₃) and total nitrogen (TN) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	Nitrate+Nitrite (mg N/L)			Total Ammonia (mg N/L)			Total Nitrogen (mg N/L)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
01. Wetland Pool 20	0.042 \pm NA	1 (0)	0.04–0.04	0 \pm NA	1 (1)	0–0	1.665 \pm NA	1 (0)	1.67–1.67
02. Wetland Pool 21	0.026 \pm 0	4 (2)	0–0.06	0 \pm 0	4 (4)	0–0	1.614 \pm 0.7	4 (0)	0.73–2.38
03. Wetland Pool 22	0.199 \pm 0.3	3 (0)	0.04–0.5	0.015 \pm 0	3 (2)	0–0.04	2.624 \pm 2.3	3 (0)	0.73–5.18
05. Wetland Pool 24	0.058 \pm NA	1 (0)	0.06–0.06	0 \pm NA	1 (1)	0–0	4.193 \pm NA	1 (0)	4.19–4.19
06. Wetland Pool 25	0.042 \pm 0.1	5 (3)	0–0.13	0.025 \pm 0	6 (3)	0–0.11	1.473 \pm 0.8	6 (0)	0.68–2.5
07. Wetland Pool 26	0.05 \pm 0.1	9 (6)	0–0.28	0.011 \pm 0	10 (8)	0–0.06	1.776 \pm 0.8	11 (0)	0.72–3.65
08. Wetland Pool 27	0.032 \pm 0	2 (1)	0–0.06	0.032 \pm 0	2 (1)	0–0.06	5.866 \pm 1.3	2 (0)	4.97–6.76
09. Wetland Pool 28	0.025 \pm 0	2 (1)	0–0.05	0 \pm 0	2 (2)	0–0	5.86 \pm 1.1	2 (0)	5.05–6.67
10. Wetland Pool 29	0.014 \pm 0	5 (4)	0–0.07	0.051 \pm 0.1	5 (4)	0–0.25	6.951 \pm 3.8	5 (0)	3.12–11.1
11. Wetland Pool 30	0.133 \pm 0.2	11 (4)	0–0.8	0.081 \pm 0.3	11 (9)	0–0.87	2.381 \pm 2.2	11 (0)	0.54–8.23
12. Wetland Pool 31	0.09 \pm 0.1	6 (1)	0–0.15	0.04 \pm 0.1	6 (3)	0–0.17	3.007 \pm 2.8	6 (0)	0.84–6.76
13. Wetland Pool 32	0.631 \pm 0.7	2 (0)	0.13–1.14	0.154 \pm 0.2	2 (1)	0–0.31	1.795 \pm 1.3	2 (0)	0.87–2.72

Focal Project Results: Oakwoods Nature Preserve East (OAKE) and Oakwoods Nature Preserve West (OAKW)

Sampling Location	Nitrate+Nitrite (mg N/L)			Total Ammonia (mg N/L)			Total Nitrogen (mg N/L)		
	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
14. Wetland Pool 33	0.04 ± 0	4 (2)	0–0.1	0 ± 0	4 (4)	0–0	4.191 ± 2.6	4 (0)	1.14–7.08
15. Wetland Pool 34	0.044 ± 0.1	9 (5)	0–0.16	0.042 ± 0.1	9 (6)	0–0.2	2.522 ± 0.9	9 (0)	0.9–3.94
16. Wetland Pool 35	0.033 ± 0	7 (4)	0–0.12	0.025 ± 0.1	7 (6)	0–0.17	2.085 ± 0.9	7 (0)	0.93–3.1
17. Wetland Pool 36	0.262 ± 0.2	4 (0)	0.05–0.57	0.485 ± 1	4 (3)	0–1.94	1.973 ± 2.2	4 (0)	0.67–5.31
18. Wetland Pool 37	0.077 ± 0	3 (0)	0.04–0.12	0.059 ± 0.1	3 (2)	0–0.18	2.465 ± 3.2	3 (0)	0.63–6.12
19. Wetland Pool 38	0.059 ± 0.1	4 (1)	0–0.13	0.037 ± 0.1	4 (2)	0–0.14	3.014 ± 2	4 (0)	0.69–4.97
20. Wetland Pool 39	0.019 ± 0	8 (6)	0–0.12	0.002 ± 0	8 (7)	0–0.01	1.794 ± 0.9	8 (0)	0.51–2.8
21. Wetland Pool 40	0.049 ± 0.1	31 (12)	0–0.26	0.008 ± 0	32 (26)	0–0.06	1.364 ± 0.5	32 (0)	0.73–2.72
22. Wetland Pool 41	0.028 ± 0	3 (2)	0–0.08	0 ± 0	3 (3)	0–0	7.288 ± 3.2	3 (0)	4.12–10.54
23. Wetland Pool 42	0.057 ± 0.1	11 (5)	0–0.15	0.014 ± 0	11 (7)	0–0.09	3.546 ± 3.5	11 (0)	0.83–13.3
24. Wetland Pool 43	2.164 ± 4.6	5 (1)	0–10.47	0.152 ± 0.3	5 (3)	0–0.69	4.836 ± 4.9	5 (0)	0.82–13.07

Focal Project Results: Oakwoods Nature Preserve East (OAKE) and Oakwoods Nature Preserve West (OAKW)

Table 12.2. Summarized surface water nitrogen concentrations for the Oakwoods Nature Preserve Wetland Restoration, West Project. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Nitrate+Nitrite (NO_x), total ammonia (NH₃) and total nitrogen (TN) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	Nitrate+Nitrite (mg N/L)			Total Ammonia (mg N/L)			Total Nitrogen (mg N/L)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
01. Wetland Pool 1	0.388 \pm 1.4	31 (8)	0–8.06	0.076 \pm 0.4	31 (28)	0–2.27	2.332 \pm 2.6	31 (0)	0.63–11.94
02. Wetland Pool 2	0.113 \pm 0	3 (0)	0.06–0.16	0 \pm 0	3 (3)	0–0	4.097 \pm 3	3 (0)	0.69–6.27
03. Wetland Pool 3	0.125 \pm NA	1 (0)	0.12–0.12	0 \pm NA	1 (1)	0–0	0.564 \pm NA	1 (0)	0.56–0.56
04. Wetland Pool 4	0.086 \pm 0.1	13 (6)	0–0.27	0.035 \pm 0.1	13 (8)	0–0.2	1.959 \pm 1	13 (0)	0.42–4.47
05. Wetland Pool 5	0.056 \pm 0	3 (0)	0.05–0.07	0.085 \pm 0.1	3 (2)	0–0.26	3.705 \pm 2.6	3 (0)	0.76–5.2
06. Wetland Pool 6	0.111 \pm 0.1	5 (2)	0–0.24	0.012 \pm 0	5 (4)	0–0.06	2.656 \pm 2	5 (0)	0.82–5.86
07. Wetland Pool 7	0.086 \pm 0.1	2 (0)	0.05–0.12	0 \pm 0	2 (2)	0–0	1.39 \pm 1.1	2 (0)	0.65–2.13
08. Wetland Pool 8	0.077 \pm 0.1	6 (2)	0–0.18	0.244 \pm 0.5	6 (4)	0–1.22	2.857 \pm 2.2	6 (0)	0.5–6.46
09. Wetland Pool 9	0.079 \pm 0.1	12 (5)	0–0.24	0.046 \pm 0.1	12 (10)	0–0.3	2.867 \pm 2.2	12 (0)	0.7–9.26
10. Wetland Pool 10	0.094 \pm 0.1	2 (0)	0.04–0.14	0 \pm 0	2 (2)	0–0	1.098 \pm 0.6	2 (0)	0.67–1.53
11. Wetland Pool 11	0.091 \pm 0.1	3 (1)	0–0.14	0 \pm 0	3 (3)	0–0	1.515 \pm 1.3	3 (0)	0.74–2.96
12. Wetland Pool 12	0.084 \pm 0.1	9 (2)	0–0.19	0.133 \pm 0.4	9 (7)	0–1.19	3.308 \pm 3.9	9 (0)	0.56–12.95

Focal Project Results: Oakwoods Nature Preserve East (OAKE) and Oakwoods Nature Preserve West (OAKW)

Sampling Location	Nitrate+Nitrite (mg N/L)			Total Ammonia (mg N/L)			Total Nitrogen (mg N/L)		
	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
13. Wetland Pool 13	0.086 ± 0.1	5 (1)	0–0.2	0.011 ± 0	5 (3)	0–0.03	1.657 ± 1.1	5 (0)	0.46–2.85
14. Wetland Pool 14	0.08 ± 0	2 (0)	0.07–0.09	0.025 ± 0	2 (0)	0.02–0.03	3.633 ± 4	2 (0)	0.78–6.49
15. Wetland Pool 15	0.062 ± 0	3 (0)	0.06–0.06	0.022 ± 0	3 (2)	0–0.07	2.129 ± 1.3	3 (0)	0.59–3.08
16. Wetland Pool 16	0.233 ± 0.3	3 (0)	0.03–0.62	0.014 ± 0	3 (2)	0–0.04	3.17 ± 3.2	3 (0)	0.81–6.84
17. Wetland Pool 17	0.052 ± NA	1 (0)	0.05–0.05	0.011 ± NA	1 (0)	0.01–0.01	0.691 ± NA	1 (0)	0.69–0.69
18. Wetland Pool 18	0.08 ± 0.1	14 (6)	0–0.25	0.036 ± 0.1	14 (10)	0–0.39	1.562 ± 0.7	14 (0)	0.48–3.02
19. Wetland Pool 19	0.069 ± 0.1	10 (4)	0–0.21	0.067 ± 0.2	10 (9)	0–0.67	8.555 ± 20.6	10 (0)	0.12–67.12
20. Aurand Run downstream	1.419 ± 2.1	11 (0)	0.09–6.42	0.036 ± 0	11 (5)	0–0.11	1.732 ± 2.2	11 (0)	0.22–7.27
21. Aurand Run conn. to P1	2.315 ± 3.2	10 (0)	0.11–9.37	0.052 ± 0.1	10 (3)	0–0.26	2.908 ± 3.8	10 (0)	0.21–11.79
22. Aurand Run upstream	2.096 ± 4.4	11 (2)	0–13.95	0.076 ± 0.1	11 (2)	0–0.23	2.591 ± 4.8	11 (0)	0.21–15.57

Soil Nutrient Status

At the Oakwoods East Project, soil pH ranged from just below to just over neutral (6.2–7.4), and soil conductivity ranged from 28–315 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ (Table A5.8). Soil pH (7.4–7.5) and conductivity (358–551 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$) were higher in Aurand Run than any other sampling locations (Table A6.8). Soil pH in the isolated Oakwoods West Project wetland pools were rarely above neutral (5.7–6.7) and slightly lower than the Oakwoods East Project wetland pools, and soil conductivity (9.83–120 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$, Table A6.8) was similar to Oakwoods East Project pools.

Soil Phosphate Sorption Capacity (SPSC) across the Oakwoods East and Oakwoods West Projects was fairly high and always positive (49–120 mg P/kg, Figure 12.13, Figure 12.14), indicating a high capacity for phosphate sorption to soils. Mehlich 3 P (M3-P) was relatively low throughout the Oakwoods East Project (0.8–21.6 mg P/kg, Table A5.10,) and was somewhat higher at the Oakwoods West Project (0.8–70.1 mg P/kg, Table A6.10). A majority of soil throughout the Oakwoods East and Oakwoods West Projects were below typical agronomic levels (M3-P: 30 mg P/kg). Mehlich 3 iron (M-3 Fe), and Mehlich 3 aluminum (M-3 Al) were variable and high across both projects (M-3 Fe: 40–1372 mg Fe/kg, M-3A: 17–1397 mg Al/kg, Table A5.10, Table A6.10), likely contributing to the high SPSC.

Focal Project Results: Oakwoods Nature Preserve East (OAKE) and Oakwoods Nature Preserve West (OAKW)

Figure 12.13. Soil Phosphate Sorption Capacity (SPSC) throughout the Oakwoods Nature Preserve Wetland Restoration, East project. Each circle denotes an approximate sampling location and is annotated with the mean SPSC for spatially clustered soil samples (0–5 cm). The number of samples in each cluster is shown in white font below the circles. The color of the circle indicates the range of SPSC values, as indicated in the legend. Negative SPSC values indicate potential for soils to release phosphate, while positive values indicate soils have capacity to sorb phosphate, based on Mehlich 3 extractions of P, Fe, and Al.

Focal Project Results: Oakwoods Nature Preserve East (OAKE) and Oakwoods Nature Preserve West (OAKW)

Figure 12.14. Soil Phosphate Sorption Capacity (SPSC) throughout the Oakwoods Nature Preserve Wetland Restoration, West project. Each circle denotes an approximate sampling location and is annotated with the mean SPSC for spatially clustered soil samples (0–5 cm). The number of samples in each cluster is shown in white font below the circles. The color of the circle indicates the range of SPSC values, as indicated in the legend. Negative SPSC values indicate potential for soils to release phosphate, while positive values indicate soils have capacity to sorb phosphate, based on Mehlich 3 extractions of P, Fe, and Al.

Vegetation

Nutrient Storage at Oakwoods East- An estimated 470 lbs. of P and 1,399 lbs. of N were stored via wetland plant nutrient stock at the Oakwoods East Project during the 2023 growing season, covering approximately 41.5 acres of wetland area (Figure 12.15). This was a net decrease of 27 lbs. P and 300 lbs. N from 2021 and almost half of what the maximum total vegetation stock was in 2022 (Appendix Table 16.1). Cattail (*Typha* sp.) had the largest mean biomass of any morphospecies across 2021–2023 monitoring (Figure C5.2), and the largest nutrient density (~1.5 g P/m², ~10 g N/m², Figure 12.18, Figure 12.19) despite having the the lowest nutrient concentrations for N and P (Figure 12.17.). Cattail (*Typha* sp.) grows in wet or intermittently wet areas and tends to crowd out all other species, so the species may be less desirable across large areas. Alternative wetland species that were observed at lower abundance but occur in multi-species patches, stored comparable amounts of P and N per unit area, and are less likely to crowd out other species include Softstem Bulrush (*Schoenoplectus tabernaemontanii*), American Water Plantain (*Alisma subcordatum*), Woolgrass (*Scirpus cyperinus*), and Canada Goldenrod (*Solidago altissima*).

Nutrient Storage at Oakwoods West- An estimated 413 lbs. of P and 1,385 lbs. of N were stored in wetland plants at the Oakwoods West Project during the 2023 growing season, covering approximately 24.4 acres of wetland area (Figure 12.21). This was a net increase of 191 lbs. of P and 532 lbs. N from 2021 but a decrease by almost half of the storage seen in summer 2022 (Appendix Table 16.1). Woolgrass (*Scirpus cyperinus*) had the largest mean biomass of any morphospecies across the 2021–2023 sampling seasons (Figure C5.2). *Typha* sp. had the highest mean P and N density (~ 2.5 g P/m², ~10 g N/m², Figure 12.24, Figure 12.25) although Woolgrass (*Scirpus cyperinus*) had similar P density. Broadleaf Arrowhead (*Sagittaria latifolia*), Pickerelweed (*Pontederia cordata*), and Woolgrass (*Scirpus cyperinus*) also stored large amounts of P and occur in multi-species assemblages.

Planting Details- Following construction at Oakwoods Nature Preserve Wetland Restoration Projects, seeding occurred in spring 2021. Seed mixes were obtained from Spence Restoration Nursery, Ohio Prairie Nursery, and Ernst Conservation Seeds. Mixes include the Spence Basic Prairie, Emergent Wetland, OPN Wet Prairie, Sedge Meadow (LSMM01), and unspecified upland and wet prairie mixes. Seeded species were observed in low abundance in the 2022 and 2023 vegetation surveys (Table C5.2, Table C6.2).

Plant Diversity at Oakwoods East- Simpson's Diversity Index increased consistently across the three sampling season at the Oakwoods East Project, and Floristic Quality Assessment Index (FQAI) was higher in 2022 than in 2021, with a slight decrease in 2023 (Figure 12.20). These metrics likely show how the project changed as it matured from a newly seeded project dominated by Barnyard Grass (*Echinochloa* sp.) to one where a more diverse assemblage of both annual and perennial species has been filtered by local environmental conditions. There was a consistent increase in the number of obligate wetland species and native species at the Oakwoods East Project from the years 2021 through 2023 (Figure 12.20).

Focal Project Results: Oakwoods Nature Preserve East (OAKE) and Oakwoods Nature Preserve West (OAKW)

Plant Diversity at Oakwoods West- Simpson's Diversity Index peaked in 2022 at the Oakwoods West Project, declining slightly in 2023, but was still higher than in 2021, and the Floristic Quality Assessment Index (FQAI) increased each sampling season from 2021 through 2023 (Figure 12.26). FQAI was calculated using Coefficients of Conservatism (C-values) assigned to individual species by expert analysis for the region of Ohio. Higher C-values indicate that a species will only be found in relatively undisturbed or high-quality habitats. There was a consistent increase in the number of obligate wetland species at the Oakwoods West Projects from the years 2021 through 2023 (Figure 12.26). This was consistent with the increase in FQAI in the same timeframe.

Overall, data suggest that the diversity and quality of the wetland vegetation habitats steadily increased each year from 2021–2023 at the Oakwoods East and West Project.

Figure 12.15. (a) Tentative initial estimates of nutrient stocks stored in wetland vegetation at Oakwoods Nature Preserve Wetland Restoration Project, East from 2022. Error bars show standard deviation across patch types. (b) Estimates of total vegetated wetland area made using Expert Patch Maps (see Figure 12.16) are shown in acres.

2023 Vegetation Patches at Oakwoods Nature Preserve, East

Figure 12.16. Drone imagery of Oakwoods Nature Preserve Wetland Restoration Project, East taken in 2023 with outlined vegetation patches. Patches are used to calculate wetland vegetation nutrient storage estimates.

Focal Project Results: Oakwoods Nature Preserve East (OAKE) and Oakwoods Nature Preserve West (OAKW)

Figure 12.17. Boxplots showing measurements of vegetation nutrient concentration (%) for each species collected at Oakwoods Nature Preserve Wetland Restoration Project, East summarized across 2021–2023. A key for Wetland Indicator Status (WIS) codes can be found in Table C1.1.

Focal Project Results: Oakwoods Nature Preserve East (OAKE) and Oakwoods Nature Preserve West (OAKW)

Figure 12.18. Estimated mean species P density (g/m^2) from vegetation biomass and nutrient concentration data collected at Oakwoods Nature Preserve Wetland Restoration Project, East between 2021 and 2023. Error bars represent standard error and are only present when more than one sample of a given species was taken. A key for Wetland Indicator Status (WIS) codes can be found in Table C1.1.

Figure 12.19. Estimated mean species N density (g/m^2) from vegetation biomass and nutrient concentration data collected at Oakwoods Nature Preserve Wetland Restoration Project, East between 2021 and 2023. Error bars represent standard error and are only present when more than one sample of a given species was taken. A key for Wetland Indicator Status (WIS) codes can be found in Table C1.1.

Focal Project Results: Oakwoods Nature Preserve East (OAKE) and Oakwoods Nature Preserve West (OAKW)

Figure 12.20. Calculated measures of diversity and descriptive statistics for vegetation at Oakwoods Nature Preserve Wetland Restoration Project, East including (a) species richness (number of species encountered), (b) the Simpson's Index of Diversity (0–1; higher numbers indicate increased diversity), (c) the Floristic Quality Assessment Index (FQAI) which uses the coefficient of conservatism of observed species to quantify habitat quality, (d) Wetland Indicator Status (WIS) in the Midwest region and (e) Ohio vegetation status. Morphospecies fell into the NA or ND category when identifications were not at the species taxonomic level (e.g., when they are immature) or because that species was not defined for either the WIS or OH Status in the Ohio EPA species list. A key for WIS codes can be found in Table C1.1 and further information on these metrics can be found in the Vegetation Method Overview.

Focal Project Results: Oakwoods Nature Preserve East (OAKE) and Oakwoods Nature Preserve West (OAKW)

Figure 12.21. (a) Tentative initial estimates of nutrient stocks stored in wetland vegetation at Oakwoods Nature Preserve Wetland Restoration Project, West from 2021–2023. Error bars show standard deviation of patch types. (b) Estimates of total vegetated wetland area made using Expert Patch Maps (see Figure 12.22) are shown in acres.

2023 Vegetation Patches at Oakwoods Nature Preserve, West

Figure 12.22. Drone imagery of Oakwoods Nature Preserve Wetland Restoration Project, West taken in 2023 with outlined vegetation patches. Patches are used to calculate wetland vegetation nutrient storage estimates.

Focal Project Results: Oakwoods Nature Preserve East (OAKE) and Oakwoods Nature Preserve West (OAKW)

Figure 12.23. Boxplots showing measurements of vegetation nutrient concentration (%) for each species collected during the 2021–2023 period at Oakwoods Nature Preserve Wetland Restoration Project, West. Boxplots show the first quartile, median, and third quartile. A key for Wetland Indicator Status (WIS) codes can be found in Table C1.1.

Focal Project Results: Oakwoods Nature Preserve East (OAKE) and Oakwoods Nature Preserve West (OAKW)

Figure 12.24. Estimated mean species P density (g/m^2) from vegetation biomass and nutrient concentration data collected at Oakwoods Nature Preserve Wetland Restoration Project, West between 2021 and 2023. Error bars represent standard error and are only present when more than one sample of a given species was taken. A key for Wetland Indicator Status (WIS) codes can be found in Table C1.1.

Figure 12.25. Estimated mean species N density (g/m^2) from vegetation biomass and nutrient concentration data collected at Oakwoods Nature Preserve Wetland Restoration Project, West between 2021 and 2023. Error bars represent standard error and are only present when more than one sample of a given species was taken. A key for Wetland Indicator Status (WIS) codes can be found in Table C1.1.

Focal Project Results: Oakwoods Nature Preserve East (OAKE) and Oakwoods Nature Preserve West (OAKW)

Figure 12.26. Calculated measures of diversity and descriptive statistics for vegetation at Oakwoods Nature Preserve Wetland Restoration Project, West including (a) species richness (number of species encountered), (b) the Simpson’s Index of Diversity (0–1; higher numbers indicate increased diversity), (c) the Floristic Quality Assessment Index (FQAI) which uses the coefficient of conservatism of observed species to quantify habitat quality, (d) Wetland Indicator Status (WIS) in the Midwest region and (e) Ohio vegetation status. Morphospecies fell into the NA or ND category when identifications were not at the species taxonomic level (e.g., when they are immature) or because that species was not defined for either the WIS or OH Status in the Ohio EPA species list. A key for WIS codes can be found in Table C1.1 and further information on these metrics can be found in the Vegetation Method Overview.

Sediment-Surface Water Nutrient Exchange Rates

Measurements of nutrient exchange within representative sediment cores can be used to estimate nutrient retention or release rates across a pool or Project where applicable. Sediments across Oakwoods East had either net zero exchanges or net releases of DRP, NO_x, and total NH₃ between the sediment and overlying water (Figure 12.27). Wetland Pools 30 and 42 both receive tile drain effluent but differ in magnitude of DRP and total NH₃ flux rates, with Pool 42 sediments on average releasing more DRP and total NH₃ than Pool 30 sediments. Wetland Pools 39 and 40 are isolated pools yet differ mainly in NO_x release rates. Pool 40 sediments release NO_x faster than Pool 39 sediments.

Currently, the intact sediment core incubation protocol is only equipped to sample sediment from inundated areas of the Project. Future development of the methods will expand researchers' ability to estimate nutrient exchange in upland or intermittently dry areas of the Project as well.

Figure 12.27. Sediment-water nutrient exchange in four pools of Oakwoods East measured via intact sediment core incubations. Bar plots represent nutrient flux at each pool averaged between

flux measurements from three cores (black circles) taken within the respective pool. Positive values indicate release of nutrients from the sediment to the surface water. Negative values indicate retention of nutrients from surface water to the sediment. Error bars represent standard error. Note the change in magnitude and direction of the y-axis across the three nutrient panels.

Hydrogeophysics

Hydrogeophysical data help delineate spatial variability and zones across the Oakwoods East and West Projects and inform a 3D hydrodynamic model.

The combined geophysical data, validated with ground-truth well logs and soil samples show that the entire Oakwood wetland site is underlain by a thin (2–4 m) layer of clay-rich soil overlying limestone bedrock. Considering the thin overburden and the relatively low infiltration capacities of clay-rich at the site, the integrity of the bedrock will play a critical role in the surface-subsurface water interaction in assessing nutrient retention. Hence, it is important to explore the nature, frequency, and extent of discontinuities in the limestone bedrock in assessing the functioning of the Oakwood wetland.

2023 Hydrogeophysical Data Collection

2023 was the first year in which hydrogeophysical data were collected from Oakwoods East and West Projects, including apparent conductivity at the middle portion of the Oakwoods East Project, four electrical resistivity tomography (ERT) and ground penetrating radar (GPR) profiles each (200–300 meters long), two groundwater monitoring well installations, three viable infiltration experiments, and soil samples taken from two locations (Figure 12.28).

Soil Physical Properties: Soil Electrical Conductivity

Apparent conductivity (ECa) of the subsurface soil (75 cm below surface) was higher in the middle portion of the Oakwoods East Project where wetland pools were constructed than the in upland areas (Figure 12.29). In addition to soil information, a tile drain connecting two of the major pools is visible in the ECa data (Figure 12.29). Groundwater monitoring well logs observed from the Oakwoods East Project showed clay-rich soils from 61 cm to 139 cm (Figure 12.30). Generally, clay-rich soils have low infiltration capacities, which allow water to pool at the wetland's surface for longer periods.

Soil Structure: Ground Penetrating Radar and Electrical Resistivity Tomography

All the GPR profiles showed three distinct layers between 0–3.5 meters below the soil surface. Comparing these signatures detected by GPR with the groundwater monitoring well logs, the layers were identified as a silty clay loam at the surface, followed by a clay layer with large shale fragments in the middle, and lastly a very wet sandy clay layer with large shale fragments (Figure 12.30). Electrical resistivity tomography results showed a thin (2–4 m) layer of lower resistivity material underlain by a much thicker (about 30 m) higher resistivity material with an

Focal Project Results: Oakwoods Nature Preserve East (OAKE) and Oakwoods Nature Preserve West (OAKW)

undulating surface (Figure 12.31). ODNR well logs #848592 and #310834¹⁵ and hydrogeophysical groundwater monitoring well logs confirm the top layer as clay, and the bottom layer as very shallow limestone bedrock.

Figure 12.28. Map of geophysical data collected at OAKW/E for the 2023 field season and planned data collection for the 2024 field season. Note: three of the five infiltration test locations yielded viable experiment results.

¹⁵ “Water Well Database.” waterwells.ohiodnr.gov. Ohio Department of Natural Resources Division of Geological Survey. <https://waterwells.ohiodnr.gov/>

Figure 12.29. Soil conductivity (ECa) map of OAKE ranging from 1–61 mS/m. Higher conductivity zones (denoted by warmer colors) indicate more clay-rich soils capable of holding water while lower conductivity zones (denoted by cooler colors) indicate more sandy soils with higher water infiltration rates. Red and orange areas show where water could be pooled during wet periods, and green “pockets” within the wetland are islands which are rarely covered with water.

Figure 12.30. Ground penetrating radar (GPR) profile OAKE P1. All the GPR profiles show three distinct layers between 0–3.5m below the surface. Since it is impossible to know the geologic characteristics from GPR alone, interpretations must be based on comparing radar results with logs taken during Monitoring Program geophysical groundwater well installation. OAKE P1 shows layer one as silty clay, layer two as clay with shale fragments, and layer three as sandy clay with pebbles. OAKW P1 shows a similar three-layer structure, and Monitoring Program geophysical groundwater well logs show a clay matrix with shale fragments that coarsens downwards.

Focal Project Results: Oakwoods Nature Preserve East (OAKE) and Oakwoods Nature Preserve West (OAKW)

Figure 12.31. Resistivity profile OAKW P1 up to 50 meters (m) depth (Top) and up to 5 m depth (Bottom). All four ERT profiles show shallow depth to bedrock (generally less than 5 m) that slopes down toward the north of the site. Overlying the bedrock is a lower resistivity layer that is a clay/silt/sand mix between the depth of 0–3.5 m, confirmed by Monitoring Program geophysical groundwater well OAKW P1. Note: elevation and topographic correction are relative values and not referenced to meters above sea level.

Table 12.3. Hydrogeophysics Sampling at Oakwoods East and Oakwoods West (OAKE/W). Red indicates no sampling, yellow indicates sampling has begun and is not complete. X indicates a survey of respective survey-transect-collected data for Ground Penetrating Radar (GPR) and Electromagnetic Induction (EMI).

	2022	2023	2024
Ground Penetrating Radar		X	Planned
Electrical Resistivity Tomography		4	Planned
Electromagnetic Induction		X	Planned
Soil Samples		2	Planned
Groundwater Monitoring Wells		2	Planned
Infiltration Tests		5	Planned

Nutrient Load Calculation

Researchers estimate that the conversion of the Oakwoods East and West areas from agricultural land use to wetlands annually prevented 82 lbs. of P from being exported to the Aurand Run watershed. In 2023, researchers estimated that wetland features connected to nutrient sources at the Oakwoods Project removed up to 1–2 lbs. of “new” P loads.

P Loss Prevention Due to Land Conversion

To estimate the average annual P loss prevented by land conversion of agricultural land to wetlands at the Oakwoods East and Oakwoods West Projects, researchers used published values from edge-of field studies of average annual P export from farm fields (0.74 lb. P/acre) that had similar soil type, P content, and topological slope as Oakwoods. The average export by area was applied to the area of the Oakwoods Project (110 acres) to produce the value reported above of 82 lbs. of P annually. The 10 and 90 percentiles values of the annual P export from similar fields were used to calculate the range of this estimate as ± 49 lbs. Monitoring Program observations and hydrologic monitoring data indicated no appreciable loss of surface runoff from areas of this wetland project, thus nutrients that would have been lost from these 110 acres when they were farmed are no longer being exported downstream each year.

Reduction of “New” P loads in 2023

Five pools at Oakwoods East and West receive drainage from agricultural areas: Pool 1, which also connects with Aurand Run as a floodplain pool, a tile drain outlet, and four pools have tile drain outlets and no constrained surface outflow (“Flow-In/No-Flow Out”, FINFO). Researchers estimated that in 2023, these pools removed minimal, if any, “new” nutrient loads because dry conditions and sediment clogging of tiles reduced the amount of flow that might occur normally.

Volume- Pool volumes were calculated by measuring area at different depths and calculating the volumes of each of those layers assuming rectangular prism geometry and summing them. Areas were determined using the design maps drawn to scale that have contour lines and the measurement function in Adobe Acrobat calibrated using the map legend scale.

Concentration- The mean TP concentration in the floodplain Pool 1 during periods when higher water flow was expected based on precipitation patterns was 0.22 mg P/L and in the other pools 2–19 during the same period was 0.17 mg P/L (rainfall index >0.7 inch, see Appendix, ***Oakwoods Nutrient Budget Calculation Details***). Researchers assumed that high water levels in Pool 1 occur when Aurand Run and tile drains have recently delivered “new” P loads, and that low water levels reflect times when previously delivered P has settled and been retained within the Pool. Thus, the difference between the mass of P in Pool 1 and the other pools (2–19) at higher water flow was used to indicate the amount of P retained by Pool 1 during that time period, leading to the estimate of 1 lb. P. Researchers are not able to distinguish between P loading coming from Aurand Run and coming from the inflowing tile drain into Pool 1 with current data.

In the four pools that receive drainage from agricultural tiles and have no outlets (“FINFO” pools), the amount of P retained in 2023 is low due to the relatively dry weather conditions in 2023 and the relatively small, combined capacity of these pools of about 56,000 cubic feet relative to the total capacity of all the pools of Oakwoods (>1,000,000 cubic feet per second). The estimate of P retained was generated from the difference of the total P concentration at high water level of 0.37 mg P/L and low water level of 0.16 mg P/L multiplied by the volume of these four pools 50,000 cubic feet per second (1,415,000 L). This initial analysis of P retention by the four FINFO pools indicates that it is unlikely to be large, probably less than 2 lb. per year because of their relatively small size of about 0.1 acre each and the possible flow restriction due to sediment accumulation.

Monitoring Considerations & Future Efforts

Continuously logging water level sensors will be deployed in representative pools throughout Oakwoods East and West to fully capture seasonal and event-driven changes in hydrology and more accurately calculate water balances for the project that can be generated by monthly water level measurements alone. Special attention will be given to observing differences between pools receiving tile drain inputs from those without tile drain inputs to assess the differential contributions of these two different pool types to overall nutrient load reduction.

Because tile outlets are at the bottom of the tile-drain fed pools (Pools 1, 30, 31, 36, and 42), they are quickly submerged when water is flowing and filling the pools. This prevents direct measures of flow rates in the tile drains, but researchers will quantify flow into these pools using water level monitoring data and inferring flow rates from changes in pool volume over time. The installation and sampling from groundwater monitoring wells will aim to assess role of subsurface water inputs to these seemingly isolated depressional wetlands pool.

To measure surface water nutrient concentrations during infrequent but important flooding events, an automated water sampler will be installed to collect water samples from Pool 1 during periods when water is exchanged with Aurand Run and when outflow from the drainage tile is delivered.

Redhorse Bend Preserve Wetland Restoration (REDB)

Overview

Sandusky County | Sandusky River Watershed

Project size: 54 Acres

Partners: Black Swamp Conservancy, Sandusky County Parks, Biohabitats

ODNR Description: “This Project is restoring 54-acres of floodplain habitat along the Sandusky River. Dikes are being removed to enhance access to restored floodplain wetlands increasing the ability to retain floodwaters and treat pollutants. Trees and upland meadow habitat will also be planted. Once the restoration is complete, the property will be managed by Sandusky County Parks and open for public access.”¹⁶

Nutrient Load Reduction Assessment

Monitoring indicates that in 2023, the Redhorse Bend Preserve Wetland Restoration (hereafter Redhorse Bend Project) retained an estimated 13 lbs. Total phosphorus (TP) and 4 lbs. Dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP). When net retention due to the conversion of agricultural land to wetland is incorporated into researchers’ nutrient load reduction accounting, researchers estimate that this Project removed about 0.85 lb. per acre of TP and 0.38 lb. per acre of DRP. Researchers estimate that plant biomass at this Project stores as much as 712 lbs. of P and 2920 lbs. of nitrogen (N) at the peak of the growing season. While soils throughout the Project have moderate to high capacity to sorb phosphate, measures of exchange rates indicated they either had no influence on surface water DRP concentrations or released DRP into surface waters, estimated using field-collected, lab-incubated soil cores. All experimentally incubated soils released nitrate+nitrite (NO_x), and total ammonia (NH₃) into surface waters.

Management Considerations

The Redhorse Project is functioning as floodplain wetland; the Sandusky River floods the wetland area during high flow events and the wetland retains that water until water depths start to recede. Yet, the bank cuts currently only allow for flooding during especially high storm events, and if they were lower more floodwaters could enter the wetland. Many of the pools adjacent to the river rarely hold water, if ever. Pond 6 on the southern half of the wetland is isolated and doesn't capture nutrients from the river. Pond 6 may help reduce stormwater runoff from the adjacent highway US-20, but most of that water bypasses the pool through Ditch 1 (Figure 13.1). Since construction, the wetland pools have received 14 storm events from the Sandusky River, approximately five to six per year. The past few years have had somewhat lower than average flow and 2023 flow was the lowest since 2001 (Figure 2.1). Therefore, the full potential of this Project in retaining nutrients from the river will likely be higher in future years with more typical flow patterns.

¹⁶ “Redhorse Bend Preserve Wetland Restoration.” h2.ohio.gov. Ohio Departments of Natural Resources, Agriculture, and Environmental Protection, March 4, 2024. <https://h2.ohio.gov/Project/redhorse-bend/>

Sampling Approach

Construction was complete at the Redhorse Bend Project in 2021. Routine monitoring began in 2022. The sampling goal is to characterize ambient and storm flow concentrations across each wetland pool, the Sandusky River adjacent to the Project, and the northern ditch (Ditch 2, Figure 13.1). For ambient or low-flow conditions, samples are collected monthly. For storm conditions, samples are collected during flow events over 3,800 cubic feet per second (assessed upstream at the USGS gage Sandusky River near Fremont OH – 04198000¹⁷). For high flow events, samples are collected once, but for extremely high flow events (over 10,000 cubic feet per second) samples are collected multiple times during the “falling limb” of the storm event’s hydrograph (i.e., 9/1/2023, Figure 13.3). Researchers also leverage the Heidelberg University long-term monitoring location upstream to assess storm concentrations in the river.

Vegetation surveys for community composition occurred at the Redhorse Bend Project in late June 2022 and August 2023 (Table C7.1). Sampling of above- and belowground biomass and nutrient concentration occurred during survey periods for 2022 and 2023.

To measure sediment-water nutrient exchange at the Redhorse Bend Project, researchers collected and incubated four intact sediment cores from locations representative of Ponds 1, 3, and 4.

Figure 13.1. Aerial image of approximate location of sampling for water and soil samples and discrete manual measurements of water depth and physicochemical measurements at Redhorse Bend Preserve Wetland Restoration Project. The legend provides the brief description of each sampling location.

¹⁷ “Sandusky River near Fremont OH – 04198000.” [waterdata.usgs.gov](https://waterdata.usgs.gov/monitoring-location/04198000/). U.S. Department of Interior. <https://waterdata.usgs.gov/monitoring-location/04198000/>

Hydrology

During high flow (over ~3,800 cubic feet per second), floodwater from the Sandusky River enters and exits the wetland through the northern Ditch 2 (Figure 13.3) that connects the river to a series of five large wetland pools (Ponds 1–5) and a series of smaller wetland pools (Ponds A–G) that run along the river perpendicular to the larger pools. One depressional isolated pool (Pond 6) in the southern part of the Project receives surface runoff from the highway and the adjacent restored meadow river (Figure 13.1, Figure 13.2). During extremely high flow events (over 12,000 cubic feet per second), the river enters the wetland through the lowered berms and the separate pools become connected into one large pool (Figure 13.4).

During ambient conditions, most of the major pools (Ponds 1–5) contain water from shallow groundwater due to the high water table in the area close to the river and at the bottom of a slight hillslope. Only during drought conditions will the major pools become dry. A groundwater spring with distinct chemistry enters the wetland at Pond 1B containing deep groundwater (Figure 13.2). Because of the high water table and inflow of shallow groundwater, during a storm event, researchers don't expect that much flood water exits the wetland through the subsurface, instead they predict most water exits from the northern ditch (Ditch 2) or is stored in the pools, as the berms between pools help retain the storm water. The smaller pools adjacent to the river (Ponds A–G) are dry during most conditions.

Figure 13.2. Flow schematic for the floodplain wetland at the Redhorse Bend Preserve Wetland Restoration Project. The blue arrow indicates the river flowing north, and the yellow arrows show where river water enters and exits the wetland.

Figure 13.3. Sandusky River streamflow for 2023 (USGS gage Sandusky River near Fremont OH – 04198000) in cubic feet per second (CFS) and million gallons per day. Blue indicates streamflow, the black circles indicate sampling visits. The dashed line is 3,800 cubic feet per second, above which stormflow water will enter the wetland.

Figure 13.4. (Left) Redhorse Bend Preserve on May 10, 2021 when the Sandusky River flow was 12,300 cubic feet per second. (Right) Redhorse Bend Preserve on March 26, 2023. The Sandusky River flow was 10,600 cubic feet per second.

Sampling Location Water Depths

Overall, pool depths varied by sampling location as well as across seasons. Pond 3A had the deepest mean pool depth at 39 cm. Pond 1B and 6 had the shallowest mean depth at 18 cm (Table A7.2). The smaller pools (6, A-G) had fewer measurements because they were dry during

Focal Project Results: Redhorse Bend Preserve Wetland Restoration (REDB)

many of the sampling visits, thereby were functionally shallower than Pond 1B. Additionally, no water has been observed in ponds E-G. Pools were deepest in winter months (34 cm) across the Project from 2021–2023 followed by spring (31 cm), summer (25 cm), and then fall (23 cm, Table A7.3).

It's important to note that the depths for the Sandusky River and the spring were not representative of the true depths for those sampling locations. The Sandusky River was sampled as deep as was safe to access and the depth readings were not consistent across sampling dates. The upstream USGS gage provides better information regarding the variability in river flow. Furthermore, the spring depth was as far as researchers could reach into the opening of the spring with the meter stick to give an indication of inflow volume.

Figure 13.5. Boxplots displaying variability in discrete, manually measured surface water depths (in centimeters) across sampling locations at the Redhorse Bend Preserve Wetland Restoration Project. Depths were measured approximately monthly from 2021–2023. For each boxplot, the thick line represents the median (middle) surface water depth across all measurements. The

boxes indicate the value range for 50% of the measured depths and the whiskers show the spread of depth values that are outside the 50% of the data points. Each overlying point represents individual water depth measurements and colors denote the season in which the measurement was taken, as indicated in the legend.

Surface Water Nutrient Concentrations

Generally, total phosphorus (TP) and dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP) concentrations were highest in the river and ditch compared to the wetland pools. There were no clear trends in DRP or TP concentrations across the wetland pools, except that ponds 1A and 2 tended to be lower than other wetlands pools (Table 4). TP concentrations were above detection limits (0.001 mg P/L) for all but one sample, however a higher proportion of DRP concentration below detection limits (0.001 mg P/L) was found (Table A7.4). The highest mean TP (0.242 mg P/L) and DRP (0.05 mg P/L) was during winter months while fall had the lowest mean TP (0.089 mg P/L) and DRP (0.009 mg P/L) concentrations (Table A7.5). While 97% of the DRP concentrations were above detection limits in winter, only 65% of the samples were above detection limits in the fall (Table A7.5).

Similar to phosphorus, nitrate+nitrite (NO_x) and total nitrogen (TN) concentrations tended to be higher in the Sandusky River and the Ditch compared to the wetland pools (Table 13.1). Total ammonia (NH₃) concentrations were also higher in the Ditch, but not in the river in comparison to the pools. There were no discernible trends across the pools, aside from Pond 1A having lower concentrations compared to other sampling locations. Mean NO_x concentrations were similar across seasons, yet the highest concentrations were found in Fall (12.4 mg N/L) and Spring (12.0 mg N/L, Table A7.7). Total NH₃ concentrations were highest in the Fall on average (0.07 mg N/L), though TN concentrations were highest in Summer (2.3 mg N/L).

Soil Nutrient Status

Soil nutrient concentrations varied greatly by sampling location. Soil pH for all samples were slightly above neutral (7.08–7.72, Table A7.8). Soil conductivity was highly variable but was notably highest in Pond 1B where the spring enters the pool (Table A7.8). The highest Mehlich 3-extractable phosphorus (M3-P) iron (M3-Fe), and aluminum (M3-Al) were in Pond 3A and 3B, yet the lowest Soil Phosphate Sorption Capacity (SPSC) was found in Pond 2 (Table A7.10). All soils sampled indicated capacity to sorb rather than release phosphate implying a high capacity for removal of water column phosphorus (Figure 13.7). In general, Mehlich 3 P was lower than typical agricultural fields (~30 mg P/kg).

Pond 3 had the highest total soil P and N compared to other pools, though some were similar (Pond 1B, Table A7.12). The highest water extractable soil phosphate (PO₄) was found in Pond 3B, but Pond 3A had lower water extractable soil PO₄ even though total P was similar for both (Table A7.12). Water extractable soil nitrate+nitrite and total ammonia were highly variable across the pools with the highest concentrations in Pond 1B and Pond 3 (Table A7.12).

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Figure 13.6. Time series of dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP, top panel) and total phosphorus (TP, bottom panel) concentrations in surface water samples collected at the Redhorse Bend Preserve Wetland Restoration Project from 2021–2023. Each symbol represents one sample point, colors denote the sampling locations, and shapes indicate the general category of the sampling locations, as indicated in the legend. Values below detection limit were replaced with zero. Connected circles represent samples collected within 30 days of each other.

Focal Project Results: Redhorse Bend Preserve Wetland Restoration (REDB)

Table 13.1. Summarized surface water nitrogen concentrations for the Redhorse Bend Preserve Wetland Restoration Project. Values are reported as mean ± standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Nitrate+Nitrite (NO_x), total ammonia (NH₃) and total nitrogen (TN) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	Nitrate+Nitrite (mg N/L)			Total Ammonia (mg N/L)			Total Nitrogen (mg N/L)		
	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
01. Pond 1A	0.087 ± 0.2	26 (2)	0–0.43	0.018 ± 0	26 (4)	0–0.05	0.838 ± 0.5	22 (0)	0.03–2.05
02. Pond 1B	0.295 ± 0.4	12 (3)	0–1.48	0.033 ± 0	12 (0)	0.01–0.08	1.631 ± 1	8 (0)	0.38–2.95
03. Pond 2	0.1 ± 0.1	21 (0)	0–0.49	0.021 ± 0	20 (3)	0–0.11	1.078 ± 0.6	21 (0)	0.23–2.32
04. Pond 3A	0.322 ± 0.9	21 (2)	0–3.88	0.043 ± 0.1	23 (2)	0–0.38	2.12 ± 3.2	19 (0)	0.51–14.27
05. Pond 3B	0.114 ± 0.2	12 (3)	0–0.83	0.099 ± 0.3	13 (1)	0–1.11	1.573 ± 0.8	9 (0)	0.28–2.98
06. Pond 4	0.086 ± 0.1	22 (4)	0–0.51	0.014 ± 0	26 (2)	0–0.04	1.266 ± 1	18 (0)	0.17–3.88
07. Pond 5	0.981 ± 3	17 (0)	0–12.44	0.026 ± 0	17 (3)	0–0.08	2.054 ± 3.2	17 (0)	0.33–14.02
08. Pond 6	0.148 ± 0.4	10 (0)	0–1.14	0.019 ± 0	10 (1)	0–0.06	0.979 ± 0.5	10 (0)	0.44–2.29
09. Sandusky River	2.842 ± 2.7	28 (0)	0–12	0.059 ± 0.1	28 (1)	0–0.36	4.138 ± 3.2	28 (0)	0.42–14.56
10. Ditch 2S	0.274 ± 0.3	6 (0)	0–0.77	0.116 ± 0.1	6 (0)	0–0.31	1.339 ± 0.9	6 (0)	0.16–2.3
11. Ditch 2N	1.013 ± 1.8	13 (0)	0–6.11	0.139 ± 0.3	13 (3)	0–0.83	2.144 ± 2.3	13 (0)	0.27–7.88
12. Spring	0.12 ± 0.3	7 (0)	0–0.84	0.018 ± 0	7 (0)	0–0.04	0.366 ± 0.4	7 (1)	0–1.03

Focal Project Results: Redhorse Bend Preserve Wetland Restoration (REDB)

Sampling Location	Nitrate+Nitrite (mg N/L)			Total Ammonia (mg N/L)			Total Nitrogen (mg N/L)		
	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
13. Pond A	0.357 ± 0.6	15 (0)	0–1.95	0.016 ± 0	15 (4)	0–0.06	1.487 ± 0.8	15 (0)	0.47–3.65
14. Pond B	0.297 ± 0.6	11 (0)	0–2	0.005 ± 0	11 (1)	0–0.02	1.229 ± 1.1	11 (0)	0.11–3.74
15. Pond C	0.212 ± 0.4	7 (0)	0–1.13	0.005 ± 0	7 (1)	0–0.02	1.236 ± 0.8	7 (0)	0.39–2.65
16. Pond D	0.018 ± 0	5 (0)	0–0.09	0.002 ± 0	5 (1)	0–0	1.076 ± 0.7	5 (0)	0.4–2.16

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Figure 13.7. Soil Phosphate Sorption Capacity (SPSC) throughout the Redhorse Bend Preserve Wetland Restoration Project. Each circle denotes an approximate sampling location and is annotated with the mean SPSC for spatially clustered soil samples (0–5 cm). The number of samples in each cluster is shown in white font below the circles. The color of the circle indicates the range of SPSC values, as indicated in the legend. Negative SPSC values indicate potential for soils to release phosphate, while positive values indicate soils have capacity to sorb phosphate, based on Mehlich 3 extractions of P, Fe, and Al.

Vegetation

In the 10.3 acres of vegetation wetland area observed at Redhorse Bend Project by the Vegetation Specialty Crew in 2022 stored an estimated 799 lbs. of P and 3,327 lbs. of N in vegetation at peak biomass (Appendix Table 16.1). This storage was reduced to 378 lbs. of P and 1536 lbs. in 2023 with little change to the total vegetated area studied (Figure 13.9). Despite this reduction in vegetation nutrient stocks, Redhorse Bend Project still was estimated to have

reduced nutrient loads in 2023. Many H2Ohio Focal Projects experienced a drop in vegetation nutrient stocks in 2023 (Figure 6.1). Continued monitoring is recommended to understand potential causes – such as the dry water year – for this reduction as well as understand the relationship between vegetation stocks and total Project nutrient reduction.

As in other Projects, Cattail (*Typha sp.*) and Sedges (*Carex spp.*) contributed greatly to vegetation nutrient stocks. But wetland species such as Devil’s Beggarticks (*Bidens frondosa*), Barnyard Grass (*Echinochloa crus-galli*), Deertongue (*Dichanthelium clandestinum*), and Common Boneset (*Eupatorium perforliatum*) also proved very effective at nutrient storage (Figure 13.11, Figure 13.12). Aboveground biomass observed during sampling at the Project was quite variable with variation between patches almost as high as the mean (827.99 ± 687.02 , sample size = 17, Table C7.3), indicating the Project had patches that were both sparsely and densely vegetated. The mean biomass is in the normal range observed at other H2Ohio Projects. Belowground biomass was also variable and had nutrient concentrations for both N and P (Appendix Figure 16.4) similar to other Projects. Species that had the highest biomass values at Redhorse Bend Project in 2023 included Soft Rush (*Juncus effusus*), Cattail (*Typha sp.*), and Sedges (*Carex spp.*).

Plant Community

Species richness and Simpson’s Index of Diversity remained relatively similar from 2022 to 2023 (Figure 13.13). In contrast, the Floristic Quality Assessment Index (FQAI) increased from 2022 to 2023. FQAI was calculated using Coefficients of Conservatism (C-values) assigned to individual species by expert analysis for the region of Ohio. Higher C-values indicate that a species will only be found in relatively undisturbed or high-quality habitats. As species richness and diversity remained relatively unchanged at Redhorse Bend Project during the period that FQAI increased, the increase is likely due to the higher relative abundance of species less tolerant of disturbance (high C-values). The increase in FQAI is reflected in the descriptive summaries of community composition at Redhorse Bend Project that showed a higher proportion of Facultative Wetland (FACW) and Wetland Obligate (OBL) species compared to Facultative (FAC) and Upland (UPL) species as well as a higher proportion of native species to adventive species (Figure 13.13).

Planting details

Following construction of Redhorse Bend Project, seeding occurred in 2021. Seeds were sourced from Ernst Conservation Seeds including the OBL Wetland Mix (ERNMX-131), Floodplain Seed Mix (ERNMX-154), Riparian Buffer Seed Mix (ERNMX-178), and a Custom Meadow Mix. Seeded species were observed in low abundance starting in 2022 and in higher abundance in 2023 (Table C7.2).

Redhorse Bend Vegetation Patches 2023

Figure 13.8. Drone Imagery of Redhorse Bend Preserve Wetland Restoration taken in 2023 with outlined vegetation patches. Patches are used to calculate wetland vegetation nutrient storage estimates.

Focal Project Results: Redhorse Bend Preserve Wetland Restoration (REDB)

Figure 13.9 (a) Tentative initial estimates of nutrient stocks stored in wetland vegetation at Redhorse Bend Preserve Wetland Restoration in 2022 and 2023. Confidence intervals for these estimates are still in progress. (b) Estimate of total vegetated wetland area made using Expert Patch Maps (see Figure 13.8).

Figure 13.10. Boxplots showing measurements of vegetation nutrient concentration (%) for each species collected in sampling year 2023 at Redhorse Bend Preserve Wetland Restoration. Boxplots show the first quartile, median, and third quartile. A key for Wetland Indicator Status (WIS) codes can be found in Table C1.1.

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Figure 13.11. Estimated mean species P density (g/m^2) from vegetation biomass and nutrient concentration data collected at Redhorse Bend Preserve Wetland Restoration for sampling year 2023. Error bars represent standard error and are only present when more than one sample of a given species was taken. A key for Wetland Indicator Status (WIS) codes can be found in Table C1.1.

Figure 13.12. Estimated mean species N density (g/m^2) from vegetation biomass and nutrient concentration data collected at Redhorse Bend Preserve Wetland Restoration for sampling year 2023. Error bars represent standard error and are only present when more than one sample of a given species was taken. A key for Wetland Indicator Status (WIS) codes can be found in Table C1.1.

Focal Project Results: Redhorse Bend Preserve Wetland Restoration (REDB)

Figure 13.13. Calculated measures of diversity and descriptive statistics for vegetation at Redhorse Bend Preserve Wetland Restoration including (a) species richness (number of species encountered), (b) the Simpson's Index of Diversity (0–1; higher numbers indicate increased diversity), (c) the Floristic Quality Assessment Index (FQAI) which uses the coefficient of conservatism of observed species to quantify habitat quality, (d) Wetland Indicator Status (WIS) in the Midwest region and (e) Ohio vegetation status. Morphospecies fell into the NA or ND category when identifications were not at the species taxonomic level (e.g., when they are immature) or because that species was not defined for either the WIS or OH Status in the Ohio EPA species list. A key for WIS codes can be found in Table C1.1 and further information on these metrics can be found in the Vegetation Method Overview.

Sediment-Surface Water Nutrient Exchange Rates

Measurements of nutrient exchange within representative sediment cores can be used to estimate nutrient retention or release rates across a pool or Project where applicable. Sediments across three of the five large wetland pools at Redhorse Bend (Figure 13.1) had either net zero exchanges or net releases of nutrients between the sediment and overlying water (Figure 13.14). Pond 1 sediments had the highest rates of DRP, NO_x, and sometimes total NH₃ release when compared to other ponds across the Project. Pond 1 receives water directly from Ditch 2 and is the first area to receive flood water when the Sandusky River overflows. Legacy flooding and sediment/organic matter deposition in this area of the Project could be one of the drivers for the higher DRP and NO_x release rates compared to Ponds 3 and 4.

Currently, the intact sediment core incubation protocol is only equipped to sample sediment from inundated areas of the Project. Future development of the methods will expand researchers' ability to estimate nutrient exchange in upland or intermittently dry areas of the Project as well.

Figure 13.14. Sediment-water nutrient exchange in three pools of Redhorse Bend measured via intact sediment core incubations. Bar plots represent nutrient flux at each pond averaged between flux measurements from four cores (black circles) taken within the respective pond. Positive

values indicate release of nutrients from the sediment to the surface water. Negative values indicate retention of nutrients from surface water to the sediment. Error bars represent standard error. Note the change in magnitude and direction of the y-axis across the three nutrient panels.

Nutrient Load Calculation

Result- In 2023, Redhorse Bend on average held 1.27 million gallons of water across the numerous pools. A portion of that water originated from shallow groundwater because the water table is very high next to the river. In total, almost 8 million gallons of Sandusky River water entered the wetland in 2023, of which almost all ultimately returned to the river within a week following the storm. Early estimates of storm event load reduction suggest 13 lbs. P of TP and 4 lbs. P of DRP have been retained from storm events.

Method, Volume- To estimate the loads stored during storm events, researchers used continuous depth measurements from high frequency sensors paired with pool area to calculate each pool's volume. Researchers multiplied the daily change in pool volume by researcher-sampled pool concentrations to quantify the nutrient load into or out of the wetland each day and summed for 2023. Where researchers were missing nutrient concentrations, researchers used the most recent concentrations for ambient conditions and average concentrations for storm events.

Concentration- To calculate storm event loads entering the wetland, researchers used the concentration from the source of water entering the pool and the volume increase to get inflow load. For example, nutrient load in Pond 1 would be the river concentration multiplied by the increase in pool volume, pool 2 load input would use concentrations from pool 1 and so forth. To calculate loads leaving the wetland during the falling limb of the event, researchers used the concentration in the pool multiplied by the volume decrease. For example, pool 1 would use concentrations measured in pool 1 multiplied by the volume decrease. When the actual concentrations during the event were available, researchers used those data. However, for events without concurrent sampling, researchers used the average concentrations based on previous sampling.

Land-Conversion Approach- Researchers are still working on estimating the nutrient load reduction associated with conversion of the land from agriculture to a wetland. Current estimates using a field-scale USDA supported model (the Nutrient Tracking Tool, NTT, <https://ntt.tiaer.tarleton.edu/>) suggest at least 0.39 lb. P/acre of TP and 0.24 lb. P/acre of DRP may be saved simply from this conversion. Altogether, land conversion and storm event retention in 2023 equal 0.85 lb. P/acre of TP and 0.38 lb. P/acre of DRP, which is similar to or exceeds the amount exported by the Sandusky River in 2023 (1.18 lb. P/acre of TP, 0.21 lb. P/acre of DRP).

Monitoring Considerations & Future Efforts

Over the upcoming year, Redhorse Bend will be receiving a real-time sensor network that tracks water depth and turbidity at a high frequency to improve the understanding of how storm event water is processed within the Project. Researchers have already found a good relationship

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between TP and DRP concentrations with turbidity, so these additions should help us better quantify nutrient load reductions. Researchers are also planning to conduct detailed measurements of the pool bathymetry so researchers can have better estimates of pool water volume at different depths. This will also help translate the sensor data into actionable data.

St. Joseph's River Restoration Project (SJRE)

Overview

Williams County | Maumee River Watershed | Inland WLEB

Project size: 93.8 Acres

Partner: Black Swamp Conservancy

ODNR Description: “This Project is restoring 56-acres of wetlands and forest and naturalizing tilled and ditched waterways to create meandering streams through the property. This property also will demonstrate how sustainable farming contributes to improved water quality. H2Ohio funds facilitated the purchase of nearly 94-acres of farmland along the mainstem of the St. Joseph River in Florence Township.”¹⁸

Nutrient Load Reduction Assessment

Monitoring results were used to estimate that in 2023, the main flow path of the St. Joseph's River Restoration Project (hereafter St. Joseph's Restoration Project) removed 20–50 lbs. of P and 600–800 lbs. of N. Researchers estimate that 22 acres of vegetation wetland within this Project store up to 2,263 lbs. of P and 7,447 lbs. of N. Soils throughout the Project have moderate capacity to sorb phosphate as indicated by SPSC values ranging from about 25 to 80 mg P/kg soil (Table 10).

Management Considerations

This Project has the potential to mitigate substantial nutrient loads because of its connectivity to agricultural drainage. However, higher P concentrations were observed at the outlet of the largest pool (Pool B) than at the inlet during hot conditions. Researchers attribute this observation of potential internal sediment P release to Pool B surface waters to transient low-oxygen conditions. Additional assessment is needed to determine whether transiently high P concentrations in this location contribute to net P export from the system.

Sampling Approach

Construction at this Project was completed in 2021. Routine monitoring began soon after. This Project has flow-through, floodplain, and depressional pools. Surface water samples are collected approximately monthly during baseflow conditions. Additional event sampling during high flow focuses on inlets and outlets of flow-through systems.

Routine Sampling

Flow-through- Four pools (A, B, C, G) are flow-through systems that capture water from three incoming tile drains and ultimately output to the St. Joseph River (Figure 14.1) via a drainage ditch (East Ditch, Figure 14.2). Pools A, C, and G are directly connected and form one large flow-through system at times of high flow. Pool B functions more or less separately from the A-

¹⁸ “St. Joseph's River Restoration Project.” h2.ohio.gov. Ohio Departments of Natural Resources, Agriculture, and Environmental Protection, March 4, 2024. <https://h2.ohio.gov/Project/st-joseph-river-wetland-restoration/>

C-G system. It receives only a portion of the water from one of the three tile drains that feed this Project.

Flow-through + Floodplain- While Pools B and G function as flow-through wetlands, they also sometimes receive a large amount of flood water from the St. Joseph River and therefore simultaneously function as floodplain wetlands, contrary to their initial design intention.

Depressional Pool + Floodplain- Pools D, E, and F may receive surface runoff, groundwater, and/or rainfall, but function also as floodplain wetlands at times of high flow when the St. Joseph River is flooding the area.

Hydrology and Sensor-Based Water Quality Monitoring

In 2023, this Project was outfitted with a complete sensor system network intended to provide real-time, continuous water quality and atmospheric data. These sensors have the chief objectives of reporting surface and ground water flow through the Project to supplement nutrient load calculations and support hydrogeophysical models. Water depth sensors were installed at the North, Pools A, B, and C. In addition, Wells 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5 received sensors measuring ground water conductivity, temperature, and depth to the water table. Data are retrieved online in real-time and can be used by researchers to investigate storm events and ambient conditions as water flows through the Project and biogeochemical processes take place.

Until mid-2023, water depths were measured only at discrete locations when and where water and soil samples were collected. In 2023 markers were placed at the deepest locations in pools for more standardized water depth measurements. During mid-summer 2023, sensors were placed in Pools, A, B, and C that measure water levels several times per hour and report those via telemetry.

Vegetation Monitoring

Vegetation surveys for community composition occurred at St. Joseph's Restoration in August 2021, August 2022, and July 2023 (Table C8.1). Sampling of aboveground biomass and nutrient concentration occurred during survey periods in 2022 and 2023, and belowground biomass was sampled in 2023.

Hydrogeophysical Assessments

Hydrogeophysical data helps delineate spatial variability and zones as well as stratigraphic units across the SJRE Project and inform a 3D hydrodynamic model. In 2022, hydrogeophysics researchers conducted ground penetrating radar (GPR), electromagnetic induction (EMI) and electrical resistivity tomography (ERT) surveys and installed three groundwater monitoring wells. During the 2023 field season, two additional groundwater monitoring wells were installed. Additional ERT, GPR, and soil samples are planned for collection in the 2024 field season.

Focal Project Results: St. Joseph's River Restoration Project (SJRE)

Figure 14.1. Aerial image of approximate location of sampling for water and soil samples and discrete manual measurements of water depth and physicochemical measurements at St. Joseph's River Restoration Project. The legend provides a brief description of each sampling location.

Figure 14.2. (Left) East Ditch facing south at moderate water depth on July 20, 2022, and (Right) high water depth on January 19, 2023, at St. Joseph's River Restoration.

Hydrology

Hydrologic data indicated that Pools A and C are functioning as expected as flow-through wetland pools fed by agricultural tile drains (Figure 14.3). However, much more water enters Pool B by flooding of the St. Joseph River via the East Ditch than due to water flowing from the NE tile. This probably accounts for the greater water depth and more consistent inundation of Pool B relative to Pools A and C because these latter two pools do not receive flood water from the river. Visual observations during high water level conditions indicated that Pools E, F, and G also received floodwater from the river and are also functioning as floodplain pools when the stage of the St. Joseph River at Antwerp is above 18 feet. During 2023 this probably only happened once during the January-March period.

Figure 14.3. Water depth (X symbols) and precipitation data (green bars) collected via real-time sensors at St. Joseph’s River Restoration Project in flow-through features Pool A, Pool B, Pool C from July 2023 through December 2023.

Sampling Location Water Depths

Overall, water depths in all pools generally reflected a seasonal flooding regime punctuated by transiently higher water depths in response to rain and flow events (Figure 14.4). In 2023 they were deepest in winter and early spring, then became shallow or dry by fall each year (Table A8.2). Note that 2023 was a drier-than-average year, so 2023 water depths may be atypical. Water depth measurements were generally taken at sampling locations within pools, not always at the deepest point within pools.

Pool B was the largest deepest pool at this Project with depth measurements over 172 cm during the flooding period indicated by recent sensor measurements (Figure 14.3). It held water for a longer time period than any of the other wetland pools (Figure 14.4) likely because it has a large basin and is fed not only by episodic tile drain inflows but also by occasional over-bank flooding from the St. Joseph River. Monitoring Program observations suggest that Pool B received much more water from flooding of the St. Joseph River than the other two large pools A and C.

By contrast, wetland Pool C received the majority of the water input from the three tile drains that enter this Project, yet pool C was not as deep as pool B (50 cm during highest flow) and tended to become dry relatively early in the year (Figure 14.4). Researchers attributed this to protection of Pool C from St. Joseph River flooding by the berm that surrounds it on the east and south sides. Pool G has a smaller and shallower basin than Pool B, and it seasonally flooded (depth of 65 cm during winter and spring, Table A8.2) but became totally dry through summer and fall (Figure 14.4). Pools E, F and D held relatively small amounts of water and tended to be dry for large portions of the year. Pool A also tended to be relatively shallow and had low water levels of only a few cm or less most of the year (Figure 14.4).

Surface Water Nutrient Concentrations

In the wetland pools and stream reaches, high dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP) and total phosphorus (TP) concentrations (> 0.1 mg P/L) were detected episodically. Overall, DRP and TP concentrations were lowest and least variable in winter (0.049 ± 0 and 0.176 ± 0.1 mg P/L, respectively, Table A8.5). Nitrogen concentrations in wetland pools and stream reaches within the wetland complexes were generally lower than concentrations in tile drain effluent.

The highest surface water DRP and TP concentrations were measured in effluent from two of the three drainage tiles that feed the St. Joseph's River Restoration Project (Figure 14.5). The Northwest and Northeast Tiles had the highest average and most variable concentrations of DRP (0.429 ± 0.5 and 0.324 ± 0.6 mg P/L, respectively) and TP (0.628 ± 0.7 and 0.419 ± 0.6 mg P/L, respectively, Table A8.4). The highest surface water TP concentrations measured during the monitoring period were detected in effluent from the Northwest and Northeast Tiles (maximums of 2.689 and 2.241 mg P/L, respectively), which were measured in November 2022 when tiles were exporting water but at a low flow rate. Fall fertilizer application sometimes occurs in November. The TP and DRP concentrations in North Tile effluent were lowest of the three drainage tiles (0.074 ± 0.1 and 0.025 ± 0 mg P/L, respectively, Table A8.4). The North Tile did, however, have high total nitrogen (TN) concentrations similar to the other two tiles (Northwest

Focal Project Results: St. Joseph’s River Restoration Project (SJRE)

Tile: 8.74 ± 4.7 mg N/L, Northwest Tile: 5.398 ± 3.4 mg N/L, North Tile: 4.213 ± 3.1 mg N/L, Table A8.6).

All three tile drains routinely delivered water with high nitrogen concentrations (Nitrate+Nitrite: 3.3–3.38 mg N/L, Total Ammonia: 0.05–2.8 mg N/L, TN: 4.2–8.7 mg N/L, Table 14.1).

Figure 14.4. Boxplots displaying variability in discrete, manually measured surface water depths (in centimeters) across sampling locations at the St. Joseph’s River Restoration project. Depths were measured approximately monthly from 2021–2023. For each boxplot, the thick line represents the median (middle) surface water depth across all measurements. The boxes indicate the value range for 50% of the measured depths and the whiskers show the spread of depth values that are outside the 50% of the data points. Each overlying point represents individual water depth measurements and colors denote the season in which the measurement was taken, as indicated in the legend.

Focal Project Results: St. Joseph's River Restoration Project (SJRE)

Figure 14.5. Time series of dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP, top panel) and total phosphorus (TP, bottom panel) concentrations in surface water samples collected at the St. Joseph's River Restoration project from 2021–2023. Each symbol represents one sample point, colors denote the sampling locations, and shapes indicate the general category of the sampling locations, as indicated in the legend. Values below detection limit were replaced with zero. Connected circles represent samples collected within 30 days of each other.

Focal Project Results: St. Joseph's River Restoration Project (SJRE)

Table 14.1. Summarized surface water nitrogen concentrations for the St. Joseph's River Restoration Project. Values are reported as mean ± standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Nitrate+Nitrite (NO_x), total ammonia (NH₃) and total nitrogen (TN) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	Nitrate+Nitrite (mg N/L)			Total Ammonia (mg N/L)			Total Nitrogen (mg N/L)		
	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
01. North Tile	3.329 ± 2.6	13 (1)	0–8.88	0.015 ± 0	13 (9)	0–0.07	4.213 ± 3.1	13 (3)	0–9.58
02. Northwest Tile	3.812 ± 2.2	21 (0)	0.44–8.57	2.792 ± 3.7	21 (1)	0–10.17	8.74 ± 4.7	20 (0)	3.87–21.79
03. Northeast Tile	3.379 ± 2.3	18 (0)	0.59–10.35	0.759 ± 1.6	18 (5)	0–6.28	5.398 ± 3.4	18 (0)	2.03–15.63
04. Wetland Pool A	1.127 ± 2.4	11 (5)	0–7.07	0.006 ± 0	11 (8)	0–0.03	2.324 ± 2.6	11 (1)	0–8.66
05. Wetland Pool B	0.42 ± 0.7	60 (28)	0–2.59	0.037 ± 0.1	60 (38)	0–0.64	1.925 ± 1.9	58 (0)	0.47–13.97
06. Wetland Pool C	1.729 ± 2.3	17 (3)	0–7.33	0.038 ± 0	17 (8)	0–0.1	3.604 ± 2.1	17 (0)	0.94–7.19
07. Wetland Pool D	0.155 ± 0.2	4 (1)	0–0.4	0.08 ± 0.2	4 (3)	0–0.32	0.752 ± 0.1	4 (0)	0.64–0.9
08. Wetland Pool E	0.126 ± 0.2	9 (3)	0–0.44	0.01 ± 0	9 (6)	0–0.04	1.315 ± 0.5	9 (0)	0.87–2.53
09. Wetland Pool F	0.29 ± 0.3	2 (0)	0.05–0.53	0.009 ± 0	2 (1)	0–0.02	0.974 ± 0.2	2 (0)	0.83–1.12
10. Wetland Pool G	1.154 ± 1.5	7 (2)	0–3.48	0.05 ± 0.1	7 (3)	0–0.18	1.992 ± 1.5	7 (0)	0.55–4.47
11. Reach b/w NoT & WA	4.718 ± 4.5	3 (1)	0–8.88	0.038 ± 0	3 (0)	0.02–0.05	7.056 ± 5.9	3 (0)	0.38–11.42
12. Reach b/w WA & Int. w/ NWT outlet	0.457 ± 0.6	2 (1)	0–0.91	0.15 ± 0.2	2 (1)	0–0.3	1.289 ± 0.8	2 (0)	0.73–1.85

Focal Project Results: St. Joseph's River Restoration Project (SJRE)

Sampling Location	Nitrate+Nitrite (mg N/L)			Total Ammonia (mg N/L)			Total Nitrogen (mg N/L)		
	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
13. Reach b/w NW tile junction & WC	3.078 ± 2.7	14 (0)	0.05–9.08	0.35 ± 1	14 (7)	0–3.83	4.399 ± 2.8	14 (0)	0.7–9.13
14. Reach b/w WC & WG	0.098 ± NA	1 (0)	0.1–0.1	0.077 ± NA	1 (0)	0.08–0.08	0.59 ± NA	1 (0)	0.59–0.59
15. Reach b/w WG & East Ditch	0.461 ± 0.8	12 (6)	0–2.17	0.048 ± 0.1	12 (8)	0–0.36	1.462 ± 1.2	11 (0)	0.24–3.39
16. Swale connecting WB tile to WB	1.512 ± 1.4	18 (2)	0–4.54	0.038 ± 0.1	18 (12)	0–0.34	2.303 ± 1.5	18 (1)	0–5.48
17. East Ditch	0.601 ± 1	25 (8)	0–3.3	0.123 ± 0.1	25 (5)	0–0.55	1.289 ± 1.4	25 (0)	0.25–4.81
18. Ditch Extension	0 ± NA	1 (1)	0–0	0 ± NA	1 (1)	0–0	2.132 ± NA	1 (0)	2.13–2.13
19. St. Joseph River	0.632 ± 0.7	12 (1)	0–2.13	0.04 ± 0.1	12 (8)	0–0.34	1.385 ± 1	11 (0)	0.35–3.29
22. Existing Wetland	0.029 ± 0	2 (1)	0–0.06	0.017 ± 0	2 (1)	0–0.03	1.563 ± 0	2 (0)	1.54–1.59

Soil Nutrient Status

Soil conductivity was highest in Pool B (1260 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$), the swale that delivers drainage water to Pool B (1480 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$), and the three tile outlets (500–1260 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$) whereas other wetland pools were in the range 100–300 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ (Table A8.8). Higher conductivity indicates higher concentrations of ions in the agricultural effluent delivered by drain tiles. For the most part, this aligns with hydrogeophysics mapping of the electrical conductivity at St. Joseph's Restoration Project (Figure 14.13), which indicated pockets of high conductivity around the northwest portion of the Project site. Soil pH was highest in soils from the St. Joseph River (7.512 ± 0.1) and the Northeast and Northwest tiles (7.383 ± 0.3 and 7.382 ± 0.4 , respectively, Table A8.8). Overall, soil pH tended to be slightly lower in summer than other seasons (6.214 ± 0.6 , Table A8.9). Soil Phosphate Sorption Capacity (SPSC) levels across the Project remained positive, indicating an ability to sorb phosphate (Figure 14.6). However, some of the SPSC values were low, such as at the outlet of Pool C (36.312 ± 23.7 mg P/kg, Table A8.10). All values from wetland pools and stream reaches were higher than that of samples taken from the St. Joseph River (10 ± 12.15 mg P/kg, Table A8.10).

Figure 14.6. Soil Phosphate Sorption Capacity (SPSC) throughout the St. Joseph’s River Restoration project. Each circle denotes an approximate sampling location and is annotated with the mean SPSC for spatially clustered soil samples (0–5 cm). The number of samples in each cluster is shown in white font below the circles. The color of the circle indicates the range of SPSC values, as indicated in the legend. Negative SPSC values indicate potential for soils to release phosphate, while positive values indicate soils have capacity to sorb phosphate, based on Mehlich 3 extractions of P, Fe, and Al.

Vegetation

Nutrient Storage

Approximately 22 acres of vegetated wetland area stored about 1,806 lbs. of P and 6,142 lbs. of N at peak biomass in 2022 at St Joseph’s Restoration Project (Figure 14.8, Appendix Table 16.1). This was an increase of 1,293 lbs. P and 4,444 lbs. of N since 2021, in part due to an

increase in the surveyed wetland area from 15 acres to 26 acres but also due a doubling of the mean per acre storage from 2021 to 2023 (Figure 6.1). Like in many other Projects, in 2023 there was a slight decrease in vegetation nutrient storage from the peak levels in 2022 possibly due to the dry water year but further monitoring will be required to fully understand these trends.

Soft Rush (*Juncus effusus*), a native wetland obligate species, was the species with the highest observed biomass in 2022 and 2023 (Figure C8.2) followed by facultative wetland species Virginia Wild Rye (*Elymus virginicus*) and Blue Vervain (*Verbena hastata*). All these species had relatively low concentrations of nutrients in their tissues in comparison to others (Figure 14.9). Despite low nutrient concentrations, high biomass and relative abundance across the site meant Virginia Wild Rye (*Elymus virginicus*), Blue Vervain (*Verbena hastata*), and Soft Rush (*Juncus effusus*) were the species which had the highest nutrient densities (Figure 14.10, Figure 14.12) and contributed significantly to nutrient storage at St. Joseph's Restoration in 2023. Arrowhead (*Sagittaria sp.*) had the highest concentration of nutrients in its tissues (Figure 14.9), and despite having lower biomass (Figure C8.2) contained some of the most phosphorus and nitrogen per m² (Figure 14.10, Figure 14.12) making it a significant contributor to nutrient stocks.

St. Joseph's Restoration Project was unique in that Cattails (*Typha spp.*) did not dominate the nutrient budget. Cattails (*Typha spp.*) tend to crowd out other species and may be undesirable across large areas. The overall abundance of Cattails (*Typha spp.*) at St. Joseph's Restoration Project remained low from 2021–2023 (Table C8.2), allowing for other wetland plants to appear in higher abundance, while maintaining high nutrient storage.

Plant Diversity

Although species richness observed at the Project has decreased since 2021, other diversity measures, including Simpson's Diversity Index and FQAI, have increased (Figure 14.12). The decrease in the total number of species is likely a result of perennial wetland-typical species establishing and replacing weedy and adventive species. Native species became more established at the Project, from 18% of observed species in 2021, to 52% of observed species in 2023 (Figure 14.12).

Planting Details

Following construction at St. Joseph's Restoration Project, seeding occurred in Spring 2021. Seeds were sourced from Ernst Conservation Seeds and Spence Restoration Nursery including the Wetland Seed Mix (Ernst FACW), Floodplain Seed Mix (Ernst seasonally flooded wildlife food mix), Upland Seed Mix (Ernst Deer Resistant Meadow Mix), Prairie Seed Mix (Spence Basic Prairie Mix) as well as upland, floodplain, and containerized trees and shrubs. Seeded species were seen in low abundances during the 2021 vegetation survey and in higher abundances in the following years (Table C8.2).

2023 Vegetation Patches at St. Joseph's River Restoration Project

Figure 14.7. Drone imagery of St. Joseph's River Restoration Project taken in 2022 with outlined vegetation patches. Patches are used to calculate wetland vegetation nutrient storage estimates.

Focal Project Results: St. Joseph’s River Restoration Project (SJRE)

Figure 14.8. (a) Tentative initial estimates of nutrient stocks stored in wetland vegetation at St. Joseph’s River Restoration Project from 2021–2023, (b) Estimates of total vegetated wetland area made using Expert Patch Maps (Figure 14.7) are shown in acres.

Figure 14.9. Boxplots showing vegetation nutrient concentration (%) measurements for each species collected during the 2021–2023 period at St. Joseph’s River Restoration Project. Boxplots show the first quartile, median, and third quartile. A key for Wetland Indicator Status (WIS) codes can be found in Table C1.1.

Focal Project Results: St. Joseph's River Restoration Project (SJRE)

Figure 14.10. Estimated mean species P density (g/m^2) from vegetation biomass and nutrient concentration data collected at St. Joseph's River Restoration Project between 2021 and 2023. Error bars represent standard error and are only present when more than one sample of a given species was taken. A key for Wetland Indicator Status (WIS) codes can be found in Table C1.1.

Figure 14.11. Estimated mean species N density (g/m^2) from vegetation biomass and nutrient concentration data collected at St. Joseph's River Restoration Project between 2021 and 2023. Error bars represent standard error and are only present when more than one sample of a given species was taken. A key for Wetland Indicator Status (WIS) codes can be found in Table C1.1.

Focal Project Results: St. Joseph’s River Restoration Project (SJRE)

Figure 14.12. Calculated measures of diversity and descriptive statistics for vegetation at St. Joseph’s River Restoration Project including (a) species richness (number of species encountered), (b) the Simpson’s Index of Diversity (0–1; higher numbers indicate increased diversity), (c) the Floristic Quality Assessment Index (FQAI) which uses the coefficient of conservatism of observed species to quantify habitat quality, (d) Wetland Indicator Status (WIS) in the Midwest region and (e) Ohio vegetation status. Morphospecies fell into the NA or ND category when identifications were not at the species taxonomic level (e.g., when they are immature) or because that species was not defined for either the WIS or OH Status in the Ohio EPA species list. A key for WIS codes can be found in Table C1.1 and further information on these metrics can be found in the Vegetation Method Overview.

Hydrogeophysics Results

Soil Physical Properties: Soil Electrical Conductivity

Electromagnetic induction (EMI) survey results (Figure 13.13) represent apparent conductivity (ECa) at a depth of approximately 1.5 m. ECa values were higher near the tile inlets at the northern portion of the site, as well as in the streambed that connects pools to one another. ECa values were lower in the mid- to- southern portion of the site. While deep soil samples for subsurface texture characterization have yet not been collected at this site by the hydrogeophysics team, ECa data, combined with an ODNR well log (#693968) and Monitoring Program geophysical groundwater well logs can reveal soil heterogeneity throughout the site. Though the streambed was dry at the surface during the survey, higher moisture content in the soil near these areas is likely a large contributor to the higher conductivity values. Excluding high values from the streambed, soils were lower conductivity closer to the river (Figure 14.13) and higher towards the north. Monitoring Program geophysical groundwater well logs confirmed that the sediments represented by the EMI survey coarsen towards the river, potentially due to variations in sediment transport distances during flood events based on particle size.

Soil Structure: Ground Penetrating Radar and Electrical Resistivity Tomography

Electrical resistivity tomography (ERT) surveys, combined with ODNR well logs (#693968, #948095, and #84460¹⁹), indicate that there is no bedrock visible in the profiles (Figure 13.16). This is further supported by Ohio Geological Survey drift thickness maps, which show that glacial sediments across nearly all of Williams County (where SJRE is located) can range from 161 –330 feet (~ 49 –100 m). More likely, as seen in the ODNR well log #693968, this layer is a mixture of sand and gravel ranging from 2.5 to at least 20 m. Groundwater monitoring well logs (#1 and #3) show that between 0–2.5 meters there is clay or silty clay. Between 2.5–3.6 meters these logs showed a mixture between sand, clay and gravel consistent with the ODNR well log #693968. These results are also confirmed by the GPR results (Figure 13.14). The high amount of sand and gravel at this site indicates there is potential for surface and subsurface groundwater interaction. Resistivity differences between the upland and the lowland are likely due to the coarsening of sediments towards the southern portion of the site. Groundwater monitoring well logs indicate upland soils are dominated by clays, whereas lowland soils contain a higher proportion of silt-clay mixtures (Figure 13.15).

¹⁹ “Water Well Database.” waterwells.ohiodnr.gov. Ohio Department of Natural Resources Division of Geological Survey. <https://waterwells.ohiodnr.gov/>

Figure 14.13. Soil conductivity (ECa) map for St. Joseph's River Restoration Project ranging from 1–110 mS/m. ECa results show higher conductivity sediments at tile drain inlets in the north-eastern portion of the site. The stream that runs throughout the site and connects the pools was dry during the survey, allowing ECa data collection over the dry streambed. The streambed shows higher values for conductivity than surrounding sediments.

Selected SJRE GPR Profiles

Figure 14.14. Select ground penetrating radar (GPR) profiles from St. Joseph’s River Restoration Project (#1 and #3, denoted in yellow on map). GPR profiles from this site show a very high contrast surface reflector even after background subtraction filters have been applied. This feature could be due to a gap between the radar and the ground surface. Most signals dissipate after approximately two meters (m) due to a clay layer recorded in well logs #1 and #3. The end of profile 1 showed a highly reflective signal between 430–480m that is distinctly different from the surrounding facies. This feature is recorded again at the same depth throughout profile 3, which runs perpendicular to profile 1. Monitoring Program geophysical groundwater well log #2, located near GPR profile 3, indicates that this layer could be a mix of silty clay with gravel.

Figure 14.15. Select resistivity profiles from St. Joseph’s River Restoration Project. Both profiles indicate a thinner layer of sediment (generally less than 10 m) underlain by a thicker layer (generally around 10–15 m). The upland areas (Profile A2) show the thin layer has lower resistivity than the thicker layer. However, the lowland areas (Profile C4) show higher resistivity in the sediments closer to the surface than in the bottom layer. According to the Monitoring Program geophysical groundwater well logs, the top thinner layer was made up of silty clay and clay sediments. For location of the profile transects, see Figure 14.16.

Figure 14.16. Resistivity profile from St. Joseph’s River Restoration Project (Profile C6). ODNR well log #693968²⁰ was used to interpret the deeper thicker layer as sand and gravel which was seen to be continuous throughout the site.

Table 14.2. Hydrogeophysics sampling at St. Joseph’s River Restoration. Red indicates sampling not started, yellow indicates sampling has begun and is not complete, green indicates sampling is complete. X indicates a survey of respective survey-transect-collected data for Ground Penetrating Radar (GPR) and Electromagnetic Induction (EMI).

	2022	2023	2024
Ground Penetrating Radar	X		Planned
Electrical Resistivity Tomography	X		Planned
Electromagnetic Induction	X		
Soil Samples			Planned
Groundwater Monitoring Wells	3	2	

Nutrient Load Calculation

In 2023, the main flow path of the St. Joseph’s Restoration Project retained an estimated 20–50 lbs. P, and 600–800 lbs. N and prevented these loads from entering the St. Joseph River. Researchers directly measured surface water P concentrations and filled gaps using the range of concentrations measured at specific sampling sites. Researchers estimated inflow discharge from drainage area estimates and rainfall data.

²⁰ “Water Well Database.” waterwells.ohiodnr.gov. Ohio Department of Natural Resources Division of Geological Survey. <https://waterwells.ohiodnr.gov/>

Concentrations and Volumes

The nutrient load reduction was calculated by estimating the amount of rainfall that flowed through the main flow paths and multiplying by concentrations taken every month at the various inlets and outlets of the wetland (Tables 4–7). Rainfall data before June 2023 was estimated based on rainfall data collected near Fort Wayne, IN, the closest available rain gage with available data (Weather Underground²¹), and after June 2023 rainfall data at the site was measured using the weather station installed as part of the sensor network. Surface drainage was estimated for the topographic area that drains into the wetland, while sub-surface drainage was estimated based on the area drained by the three tile drains that serve as the inlets to the wetland. The effect of all wetland pools along the flow path were assumed to be captured by the change in concentration between the three tile drained inlets and the East Ditch that serves as the outflow for the wetland. However, the East Ditch also receives substantial drainage from the agricultural field lying east of the Project that is untreated, so this likely underestimates the retention.

Monitoring Considerations & Future Efforts

The complex network of tile drain inputs, partial transport of influent in buried tile within the Project, and occasional influence of overbank flooding from the St. Joseph River makes it particularly challenging to monitor this Project for comprehensive accounting of nutrient retention. The complex hydrology of the as-built St. Joseph River Restoration Project was in part shaped by concerns regarding flooding and drainage of neighboring properties, which is a common constraint on wetland restoration design, and thus commonly impacts monitoring efforts at constructed and restored wetland systems.

At the end of 2023, a sensor network was installed to monitor weather and hydrologic conditions at the site. In 2024, additional sensors will be deployed to directly measure flow at key locations, along with at least one automated water sampler to collect water samples during transient high flow events. Special attention will be given to quantifying flow rates at the three tile drain inputs to the site. Data and samples collected by these autonomous sensors will help us characterize how the system functions during storm events when researchers have limited capacity to be present to collect samples and take measurements.

In addition, hydrologic and hydrogeophysical data will be integrated into a 3D hydrodynamic model to more precisely estimate water and nutrient budgets.

²¹ <https://www.wunderground.com/history/daily/us/in/fort-wayne/KFWA>

Appendix

Project List

Appendix Table 15.1. H2Ohio Initiative Projects routinely monitored in 2023. Geographic Base Crew, Four-letter Project Code, Project Name, and Monitoring Phase in 2022 and 2023.

Intensively monitored focal projects are indicated in bold. Char = characterization; (Pre) = pre-construction; (Post) = post-construction, Y1 = 1st Year, Y2 = 2nd Year. BG = Bowling Green State University, HU = Heidelberg University, KS = Kent State University, UT = University of Toledo, WS = Wright State University.

Geographic Base Crew	Project Code	Project Name	2022 Monitoring Phase			2023 Monitoring Phase	
			Char. (Pre)	Char. (Post)	Routine Y1	Routine Y1	Routine Y2
Northwest Inland (BG)	FORB	Forder Bridge			•		•
	OAKE	Oakwoods East			•		•
	OAKW	Oakwoods West			•		•
	OOPR	Oak Openings Preserve			•		•
	OTSS	Otsego Schools	•			•	
	SJCO	St. Joseph Confluence			•		•
	SJRE	St. Joseph's Restoration			•		•
	VANO	Van Order			•		•
	WEIP	Weisgerber-Pohlman			•		•
Northwest Central (HU)	FRUW	Fruth Wetland			•		•
	REDB	Redhorse Bend			•		•
	SPRM	Springville Marsh		•		•	
	SRHE	Sandusky River Headwaters			•		•
	SUGB	Sugarcamp 7		•		•	
Northeast (KS)	TRUC	Trumbull Creek		•		•	
Northwest Coastal (UT)	DARR	Darby Refuge			•		•
	MAGM	Magee Marsh			•		•
	NORR	North Ridge			•		•
	OTTN	Ottawa National Wildlife Refuge			•		•
Southwest and Central (WS)	BROP	Brooks Park			•		•
	BWLK	Burntwood-Langenkamp			•		•
	MERW	Mercer Wetland	•			•	
	SPRC	Springcreek Confluence			•		•
	TIPC	Tipp City		•		•	
	WALC	Walnut Creek	•			•	

Additional Data*Vegetation Program-Level Results*

Vegetation Sampling Method Note: In 2022, the Vegetation Specialty Crew selected Forder Bridge for oversampling in an effort to estimate the ideal sampling size for an H2Ohio wetland Project. This oversampling has been accounted for in the dataset by excluding the extra sampling in June 2022 in favor of the sampling conducted in July 2022 as well as through rarefaction of species observations for all Projects. Diversity and FQAI at Forder Bridge remain higher in 2023 than in 2021 however, so while the year 2022 is an outlier that needs further investigation, the overall trajectory of vegetation development at the Project is similar to other H2Ohio Focal Projects.

Appendix Table 16.1. Project-scale nutrient stock (lbs.) stored in vegetation at H2Ohio Focal Projects from 2021–2023. Dashes indicate that vegetation was not sampled for a given Project in a given year and the asterisk indicates results still in progress. A key connecting the four-letter codes to full Project Names can be found in Appendix.

Project	2021			2022			2023		
	Acres	P (lbs.)	N (lbs.)	Acres	P (lbs.)	N (lbs.)	Acres	P (lbs.)	N (lbs.)
BROP	3	92	365	*	*	*	2	66	339
BWLK	–	–	–	–	–	–	5	49	161
FORB	2	34	131	3	230	900	2	78	300
MAGM	–	–	–	–	–	–	170	10,124	40,097
OAKE	39	443	1,699	41	810	2,264	40	470	1,399
OAKW	25	222	853	24	899	2,425	25	413	1,385
REDB	–	–	–	10	799	3,327	11	378	1,536
SJRE	15	513	1,698	22	2,263	7,462	26	1,806	6,142

Appendix: Vegetation Program-Level Results

Appendix Figure 16.1. Nutrient stocks in vegetation at all H2Ohio Focal Projects plotted on a logarithmic scale. ND signifies where no data were collected. Analysis of Brooks Park 2022 data is still in progress.

a.

b.

Appendix Figure 16.2. Boxplots display the vegetation percent concentration (%) of N and P for all samples measured in each species. Morphospecies measured for nutrient concentration but not identified to the species taxonomic level were excluded. Boxplots show the first quartile, median, and third quartile.

Appendix: Vegetation Program-Level Results

Appendix Figure 16.3. Mean aboveground dry biomass (g/m²) for vegetation in H2Ohio Focal Projects sampled in 2022 and 2023. Error bars represent one standard deviation from the mean. ND indicates that a project was not sampled for aboveground biomass in that year.

Appendix: Vegetation Program-Level Results

Appendix Figure 16.4. Mean belowground dry biomass (g/m^2) for vegetation in H2Ohio Focal Projects sampled in 2022 and 2023. Error bars represent one standard error from the mean. ND indicates projects or depth intervals that were not sampled for belowground biomass in that year.

Appendix: Vegetation Program-Level Results

Appendix Figure 16.5. Mean biomass per square meter in vegetation for genera across all projects. Y-axis scales are variable to best represent variability in biomass across projects for individual genera, therefore differences between genera are not always accurately depicted across the plots. Error bars represent one standard error and are only present when there is more than one sample in the group.

Appendix: Vegetation Program-Level Results

Appendix Figure 16.6. Variability of vegetation P concentration (%) in genera observed across all H2Ohio Focal Projects. Error bars represent one standard error and are only present when there is more than one sample in the group.

Appendix: Vegetation Program-Level Results

Appendix Figure 16.7. Variability of vegetation N concentration (%) among genera observed across all H2Ohio Focal Projects. Error bars represent one standard deviation and are only present when there is more than one sample in the group.

Appendix: Soil and Water Chemistry Project Level Results

Soil and Water Chemistry Project Level Results

For each Focal Project, supplemental tables and figures are presented in an accompanying *Water and Soil Chemistry at Focal Projects Appendix (Appendix A)*, including the Sampling Locations, Sampling Location Water Depths, Surface Water Chemistry, and Soil Characteristics. Some elements within this document may be repeated in the Appendix.

Vegetation Project Level Results

For each Focal Project, supplemental tables and figures are presented in an accompanying *Vegetation Data at Focal Projects Appendix (Appendix C)*.

Technical Methods

3D Hydrodynamic Model Method Overview

To assist water and nutrient budget quantification, the Monitoring Program uses a three-dimensional (3D) modeling approach based on HydroGeoSphere or HGS^{22,23}. The fully integrated HGS numerical model is capable of simulating surface-subsurface flow and transport processes in a 3D framework. A 3D hydrologic model is developed for each Focal Project to simulate water movement and nutrient transport within the wetland domain in a physically based manner that relies on coupled differential equations. The model, driven by real weather data, allows researchers to integrate various other Monitoring Program data collected from the field (e.g., hydrogeophysics data, vegetation data, water depths, nutrient concentrations, drone imagery, etc.) to make more accurate quantification of mass balance and better assessment of wetland Projects’ nutrient removal efficiency.

Appendix Figure 19.1 summarizes the modeling approach and displays how data and information from different H2Ohio WMP teams are integrated into the 3D models being developed. Key steps include developing conceptual model, creating 3D grid for the model domain, preparing and formatting input data, running the model, calibrating and validating the model, and post-processing, visualizing, and analyzing modeling outputs.

Appendix Figure 19.1. Flowchart showing 1) key steps of developing and calibrating 3D models for the H2Ohio WMP focal wetland sites and 2) how data from various sources/teams are integrated into the modeling scheme.

²² Aquanty (2018). HGS Theory Manual. Aquanty Inc., Waterloo, Ontario, Canada.

²³ Liu, G., Schwartz, F.W., Wright, C. K., & McIntyre, N. E. (2016). Characterizing the Climate-Driven Collapses and Expansions of Wetland Habitats with a Fully Integrated Surface–Subsurface Hydrologic Model. *Wetlands*, 36, 287-297, <https://10.1007/s13157-016-0817-9>.

Vegetation Method Overview

Background Information

The different wetland types, restoration designs, and management practices of H2Ohio wetland Focal Projects provide important context for understanding how vegetation sequesters nutrients in wetlands. All H2Ohio Focal projects, except Magee Marsh Turtle Creek Bay Wetland are inland wetlands in which construction of wetland features occurred. Therefore, restoration typically resulted in at least partial removal of existing vegetation, surface elevation changes, and then seeding and planting of wetland vegetation. For specific details on seeding and planting lists, refer to the vegetation section of each focal project.

In terms of wetland types and restoration design, Magee Marsh Turtle Creek Bay Wetland Reconnection (hereafter Magee Marsh) is unique in the set of Focal projects; it is a coastal wetland with relatively stable water depths that is drawn down seasonally as a management practice to promote waterfowl habitat. But the stable water depths exclude wetland vegetation types not adapted to flooded conditions (such as facultative wetland species) and allow for deeply-rooted, floating, and submerged aquatic vegetation. Additionally, Magee Marsh is the only Focal Project that is a wetland reconnection rather than a newly constructed wetland; consequently, the wetland vegetation has been established long before H2Ohio restoration activities took place. As such, no seeding, planting, major soil disturbances, or change in vegetation management practices occurred (aside from the reconnection to the creek, which was not effectively connected during 2023).

Sampling Approach

In 2021, biomass sampling was limited while methods were in development. In 2022, sampling for aboveground biomass took place at all completed Focal projects, except Magee Marsh, and belowground biomass was limited to Forder Bridge and Oakwoods East and Oakwoods West. In 2023, above- and belowground biomass sampling took place at all project sites except Forder Bridge, following ODNR changes in priorities. Methods for sampling biomass in the coastal wetland Magee Marsh were under development in 2022 and the first sampling at Magee Marsh occurred in 2023.

H2Ohio Focal Projects vegetation sampling occurs exclusively in wetland areas (excluding any areas of the projects with upland vegetation) and consists of community composition surveys and destructive sampling of above- and belowground plant tissues (biomass). Community composition surveys are distributed across Project areas using a stratified random sampling design to capture species richness and diversity.

Above- and belowground vegetation sampling occurs in a subset of the community composition survey locations, with some samples targeting monoculture patches of key morphospecies that contribute to nutrient storage in wetlands to enable clear identification of belowground biomass. Because destructive sampling of plant biomass is labor-intensive both in the field and in the lab, particularly for belowground biomass, not all Focal Projects were sampled for biomass in all

monitoring years (2021–2023). Sampling biomass in coastal wetland projects is an additional labor challenge requiring adaptation of methods used in inland wetland projects.

Measuring Vegetation Diversity and Habitat Quality

For all observed species, Species Wetland Indicator Status (Table C1.1), Ohio Vegetation Status (Native, Cryptic, or Adventive), and Coefficients of Conservatism (C-values) are taken from the Ohio Vascular Plant Database²⁴ first published in 2004 and updated in 2014. Diversity estimates are made as species richness (number of morphospecies observed) and Simpson's Index of Diversity²⁵. Because species richness and diversity are sensitive to sample size, comparison of richness and diversity across Projects was done following a simple method of rarefaction²⁶ which standardizes the number of samples analyzed in each Project to the lowest number of samples taken across all Projects and years.

Calculating Project-Scale Vegetation Nutrient Stock

Project-scale vegetation nutrient stocks (kg or lbs.) are the sum of nutrient mass estimates for all wetland vegetation patches within each project. Researchers calculate these values using community composition, biomass, and nutrient concentration data.

Community composition surveys and drone imagery are used to identify vegetation species, their abundances, and the total project area they occupy. Project wetland areas are delineated into vegetation patches made of distinct vegetation communities in two ways: remote vegetation classifications of drone imagery ground-truthed by community composition surveys or expert classification of drone imagery informed by community composition and expert knowledge of projects.

Measurements of biomass (g/m^2) and nutrient concentration (%P, %N) are collected for individual morphospecies. Multiplying mean biomass times nutrient concentration for each species results in mean estimates of nutrient density for that species ($\text{g P}/\text{m}^2$, $\text{g N}/\text{m}^2$) used in the final calculation. However, biomass and nutrient estimates are not available for every species, project, or year. To estimate nutrient masses with incomplete information, researchers used a tiered system of data sourcing for biomass and nutrient concentration data, where researchers used the most specific data available in their estimates (Appendix). For instance, when researchers are missing nutrient or biomass estimates for a species at a particular project in a particular year (Tier 1), but researchers have those estimates from the same project in a different year (Tier 2), researchers combine biomass and nutrient estimates from the other year with percent cover and patch delineations from the current year. In cases where researchers are missing estimates from a particular project, researchers use the means for that species from other

²⁴ Andreas, Barbara K., John J. Mack, and James S. McCormac. 2004. Floristic Quality Assessment Index (FQAI) for vascular plants and mosses for the State of Ohio. Ohio Environmental Protection Agency, Division of Surface Water, Wetland Ecology Group, Columbus, Ohio. 219 p.

²⁵ Simpson, E. Measurement of Diversity. *Nature* **163**, 688 (1949). <https://doi.org/10.1038/163688a0>

²⁶ Willis, A. D. (2019). Rarefaction, alpha diversity, and statistics. *Frontiers in microbiology*, 10, 492464. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2019.02407>

projects (Tier 3). In cases where researchers have no estimates, researchers use the mean from all species across all projects (Tier 4).

To get the nutrient mass of a patch (gP|gN) researchers first calculate the species' abundance as the mean percent cover (%) observed across the whole patch. Researchers multiply species' abundance by its mean nutrient density (g/m²), and then add each species' nutrient mass together (a weighted average of species nutrient masses). Researchers then multiply by the area of each patch (km²) and sum the total of all patches, resulting in a project-scale nutrient stock (kgP|kgN).

$$Project\ Nutrient\ Stock\ (kgP) = \sum_{Patch_1}^{n\ Patches} Patch\ Nutrient\ Stock\ (gP) = \sum_{Species_1}^{n\ Species} Patch\ Area\ (m^2) \times Species\ Abundance\ (mean\ \% \ cover) \times Nutrient\ Density\ \left(mean\ \frac{gP}{m^2} \right)$$

Appendix Figure 20.1. Flow-diagram illustrating vegetation project-scale nutrient stock calculation. The top portion outlines the tiers of data sources, based on availability of Project-specific, annual-resolution species biomass and nutrient data. The next level illustrates how biomass and nutrient concentration data are combined to estimate species-specific nutrient densities for a Project. Then, using community composition survey data, nutrient densities for multi-species patches within the Project are calculated. Ultimately the nutrient densities of these patches are scaled up using estimates of wetland area covered by individual patch types to get a total mass of nutrient stock at the project-level.

Hydrogeophysics Methods Overview

Hydrogeophysics data are collected at Focal Projects. The following three goals guide the location, frequency, and type of data collection at each Project.

Goal 1- Characterize the Project's subsurface structure and function

Hydrogeophysics data reveal vital information about soil composition, groundwater/surface water interaction, and geologic structures that provide a more in-depth understanding of wetland structure and function than single-point soil samples alone.

Goal 2- Guide sampling designs for effective monitoring

Wetland soils, water, and vegetation are highly heterogeneous. To ensure that sampling teams capture as much site heterogeneity as efficiently as possible, the hydrogeophysics team provides guidance of where to sample based on geophysical measurements. For example, apparent conductivity (ECa) can be correlated with several soil parameters; ECa maps can aid sampling crews interested in measuring these parameters in designing targeted campaigns rather than random sampling.

Goal 3- Provide 3D models of subsurface geology

Interactions with groundwater can be important to wetland function and nutrient retention capabilities but are often invisible and challenging to assess with surface water and soil sampling alone. Integrated geophysical data and information from groundwater monitoring wells create 3D pictures of the subsurface geologic structure and stratigraphy of wetland Projects. Such 3D geologic models are then directly integrated into hydrodynamic models, allowing better quantification of water and nutrient flux exchanges between the subsurface and surface domains.

Guide to Hydrogeophysics Data Types

For detailed descriptions of these methods, please see Reynolds, J. M. (2011). *An introduction to applied and Environmental Geophysics, 2nd edition*. John Wiley & Sons.

Ground Penetrating Radar

Ground Penetrating Radar (GPR) indicates soil layer boundaries, buried objects, and moisture changes and is collected along transects with equipment that sends electromagnetic waves into the ground that are reflected back to a receiver in a pattern that indicates the type of subsurface materials from which they are bouncing.

Electromagnetic Induction

Electromagnetic Induction (EMI) uses alternating current from a transmitter to induce a primary magnetic field that in turn, creates very small “eddy currents” in the subsurface. A secondary magnetic field is subsequently generated from the eddy currents. Both the primary and the secondary fields are measured by the receiver. The in-phase and quad-phase components of the

secondary EM field can be related to the soil's apparent magnetic susceptibility (MSa) and apparent electrical conductivity (ECa). ECa can be correlated to different soil parameters and therefore indicate the distribution of soil heterogeneity across the wetland. This information guides soil sampling campaigns, site management decisions, and hydro-dynamic modeling.

Electrical Resistivity Tomography (ERT)

Differences in the electrical resistivity below the soil surface allow researchers to map subsurface soil stratigraphy and properties. Electrical Resistivity Tomography (ERT) injects an electrical current into the subsurface with a pair of electrodes and measures the difference in electrical potential that arises using a second pair of electrodes.

Soil Physical Properties

Mapping soil parameters across a Project allows geographic base crews to ensure their sampling campaigns are covering site heterogeneity while being as resource-efficient as possible. Wetland soils are highly heterogeneous in space, and soil properties vary greatly from site to site. Therefore, soil samples are used for ground-truthing geophysical measurements, such as EMI (electromagnetic imaging), so that the reported instrument values have context within the site. Once established, this relationship can be used as a proxy for estimating other parameters such as the soil texture, organic matter, and water contents at the site-wide scale.

Nutrient Load Calculation Details

Forder Bridge Wetland Nutrient Budget Calculation

The Forder Bridge Project is a restoration project in the Upper Maumee watershed that was constructed in 2021. The Project consists of five acres of wetlands including both a series of isolated pools, and a main treatment train that collects water from a culvert with an uncertain drainage area. The main treatment train is likely responsible for a majority of nutrient retention at the Project site, but uncertainty around the amount of water flowing through the culvert has led to a wide variability in predictions of phosphorus retention. Based on a variety of estimation methods, **the main flow path of the Forder Bridge Project removed between 4 and 45 lbs. of phosphorus and 21–180 lbs. nitrogen in 2023**, dependent on how much water flowed through the main treatment train, while the **isolated pools removed between 1 and 2 lbs. of phosphorus in 2023**.

Nutrient Retention Estimation Methods

To date, the H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program has measured surface water nutrient concentrations at the Forder Bridge Project, but water level and flow monitoring sensors have not been installed meaning **calculating nutrient loading for this wetland relies on estimates of water flow from other available data**. This Project site is an excellent example of the importance of measuring the difference between the topographic and the hydrological drainage area (for details, see *Improving Wetland Drainage Area Estimation*). As researchers collect more data, it will inform their future approach to estimating the drainage for wetlands with complex hydrology. Due to the uncertainty of the drainage area that flows into the treatment train, researchers compared multiple approaches to estimating the drainage of the main treatment train and nutrient retention in the Forder Bridge Project in 2023.

All methods estimating the reduction of phosphorus (P) by the treatment train use monthly P concentrations from water samples collected at the culvert as the “inlet” to the system, and stream 1 as the “outlet” to the system, and the difference between the inlet and outlet is used to calculate the proportion of P that was retained by the wetland system. However, P concentrations usually vary considerably during high flow events and are highest soon after flow begins. Because those concentrations have not yet been fully measured, the present load reduction estimates are likely below the actual values.

Multiplying the concentration by the volume of water estimated to flow through the system during the month the water sample was collected yields a load of P that was retained by the system for that month. To estimate the amount of water that flowed through the system during each month of 2023 researchers employed **five different methods** of estimating the drainage area and rainfall to the system:

- The baseline ODNR estimate (USGS Stream Stats and SPARROW modeling)
- Method 1 (M1: rainfall data, the NRCS curve number method, and a high-resolution digital elevation model)

- Method 2 (M2: rainfall data, the NRCS curve number method, and an expert estimate of drainage area)
- Method 3 (M3: rainfall data, literature estimates of the proportion of rainfall as discharge, and an expert estimate of drainage area)
- Method 4 (M4: rainfall data, the NRCS curve number method and a high-resolution digital elevation model to calculate surface water runoff, but an expert estimate and literature estimates to estimate the proportion of rainfall as subsurface runoff).

Researchers then separately estimated the effect of the isolated pools (MI). **The estimates provided by each method are presented in Appendix.** Estimating the amount of water entering the isolated pools is much easier than estimating the amount flowing through the main flow path, however, there is uncertainty related to P concentrations of runoff into the isolated pools because the isolated pools do not have clear inlets and outlets at which concentrations can be measured.

ODNR Estimate

The current ODNR estimate requires no site-specific data. Drainage area is estimated using USGS StreamStats, and P loading is estimated with USGS SPARROW modeling. The low estimate of percent retention is 18% removal, and the high-end estimate is 78% removal of P, with that range of retention rates estimated based on literature values.

M1: Rainfall + High-res DEM

To more accurately calculate the topographic drainage area for the site than StreamStats, researchers used a high-resolution digital elevation model (DEM) obtained from USGS National Map Downloader to estimate the area that is upslope from the wetland treatment train and where surface water runoff will drain to. Researchers do not have rainfall data from the site, so researchers downloaded publicly available rainfall data from WeatherUnderground, at the Ft. Wayne weather station, which was the nearest one available. Ft. Wayne is ~30 miles away from the site, and researchers expect that rainfall at the site will be fairly similar to rainfall at Ft. Wayne. To predict the proportion of rainfall that runs off across the landscape researchers used the NRCS curve number method (USDA-NRCS, 2004). The majority cover type of the drainage area of the site are row crops so for this estimate researchers used a curve number of 85, erring on the higher end of suggested curve number for row crops to account for the effect of subsurface flow, because researchers know there are tile drains within the drainage area and a culvert delivering water to the site.

M2: Rainfall + Expert Estimate of drainage area

Researchers communicated with the District Administrator of the Paulding County Soil and Water Conservation District who inspected the site and based on his maps and his understanding of the site, he predicts that only 16.5 acres are drained by the site, as another culvert drains a majority of the potential topographic drainage area away from the site. This estimate accounts for both surface and sub-surface drainage through the culvert into the site and suggests that there is tile drainage within the drained area of the site. Researchers used the same rainfall data and NRCS curve number method to estimate runoff for this drainage area.

M3: Rainfall (literature runoff) + Expert Estimate of drainage area

To address the potential for subsurface runoff more clearly, researchers used literature estimates of the proportion of rainfall that becomes surface runoff (~7%) and subsurface runoff (~31%) in northeastern Ohio watersheds (Pease et al. 2018). For this estimate instead of using the NRCS curve number method to estimate runoff, researchers assumed runoff was 38% (7% from surface, and 31% from subsurface) of the total rainfall for the drainage area with tile drains present, and 7% from the rest. Here researchers used the expert estimate of drainage, considering surface and subsurface drainage.

M4: Hybrid estimate. Surface runoff: Rainfall (curve number) and DEM. Subsurface runoff: Rainfall (literature runoff) and Expert Estimate

While it is likely that the second culvert drains much of the sub-surface drainage from the larger farmland area, it is very possible that a good proportion of surface runoff still flows as predicted by the digital elevation model from the entire topographical wetland drainage area. To consider this, researchers calculated sub-surface and surface water drainage with separate areas, and methods. For surface water drainage researchers used the NRCS curve number method but reduced the curve number to 80 so now the estimate is at the lower end of what researchers would predict for the soil type as researchers are separately accounting for sub-surface drainage. In this calculation researchers assume that the field does not have structures in place to divert surface water runoff that the DEM cannot detect. This gives us surface water runoff that is 7% of the total rainfall, which also agrees with literature estimates of the proportion of surface water runoff to rainfall in northeastern Ohio watersheds (Pease et al. 2018). Researchers calculated subsurface runoff only for the smaller drainage area estimated by expert opinion, and researchers calculated it as 31% of the rainfall as suggested by Pease et al. (2018).

Addressing Further Assumptions and Applying to Non-Focal Sites:

In the coming months, researchers will install sensors at the Forder Bridge wetland and test these different methods of estimating water flow with real measures of flow through the system. The point of these budgets is to address uncertainties in drainage to the treatment, and to use this focal site to highlight how assumptions about drainage area will affect P retention estimates in non-focal sites being monitored throughout the H2Ohio network. The main assumptions that this case study will help us address are that both surface water and subsurface drainage areas are accurate, that nearby rainfall is a decent proxy for site specific rainfall, that curve number choices are accurate, and that tile drains are accounted for in the predicted drainage. However, all these assumptions are focused on the hydrology of the site. Researchers are also planning to collect further data to address two major assumptions about P retention: 1) P loss through groundwater is negligible, and 2) Storm events do not change P retention dynamics.

M1: Isolated pools:

For the combination of isolated pools in wetland complex 1 and 3 researchers predict that the two complexes **stored between 0.7 and 2.3 lbs. P in 2023**, however this is likely a somewhat conservative estimate. For each pool, researchers have data on the total area of the pool, as well

Appendix: Forder Bridge Wetland Nutrient Budget Calculation

as water depths and P concentrations for 7 time points from June 2022-June 2023 (each sample is representative of a single month). Water depths were not collected at standardized locations and researchers do not yet have bathymetry data so here researchers assume that collected water depth is constant across the pool area.

There are no inlets or outlets for isolated pools, so researchers only have concentrations within the pool to estimate P retention. For this method researchers assumed that runoff entering the isolated pools is delivering P to the wetlands, and as that water dries or leaves through groundwater the P remains. To calculate the amount of P stored in each pool, researchers first calculated the volume of water in the pool at each time point by multiplying depth at collection by the area of the pool. Researchers then calculated the total mass of P in the water column at each time point by multiplying the volume at each time point by the concentration. For each pool researchers estimated the minimum retention of P was the month with the highest mass of P in the pool. Here researchers are assuming that as water dries, P is left behind, and at their minimum estimate, researchers assume that P was only deposited once, and other months are measurements of the same pool of P as it is slowly stored in soils. To make their higher end estimate, researchers instead assume that the pool dries out in between each sampling event, and that no P is resuspended when new water floods the pool. For their high estimate, researchers added the mass of P at each timepoint together. Researchers did not include wetland complex 2 because it has never been observed to have water and there are no water samples from the site. For the combination of isolated pools in wetland complex 1 and 3 researchers predict that the two complexes stored between 0.7 and 2.3 lbs. P in 2023. This is likely an underestimate because it is not capturing runoff events when the pools received P but did not retain surface water and fully dried out before monthly sampling. It is also possible that a proportion of the P in the water column of each pool has been released from the sediment, even in the minimum estimate, however high SPSC values from the isolated wetlands suggest that this may not be a large proportion of P. As researchers collect more sediment data, researchers can better predict the effect of these isolated pools on P retention of the site.

Appendix: Oakwoods Nutrient Budget Calculation Details

Appendix Table 22.1. Phosphorus (P) retention at Forder Bridge Wetland. The variation in the estimates is due to missing P data when water levels are too low to sample during monthly sampling but there is still predicted discharge through the system. Drainage area by expert estimate varies where subsurface drainage is predicted compared to full drainage (7.3 acres subsurface, 16.5 surface).

Forder Bridge P retention	Drainage area (acres)	Rainfall (l)	Discharge (l)	Proportion rainfall	P retention (lbs. in 2023)	N retention (lbs. in 2023)
M0: ODNR Estimate	63	NA	NA	NA	7–51	NA
M1: Rainfall + high-res DEM	164	570,028,366	71,443,877	13%	36–45	162–290
M2: Rainfall (curve number) + Expert Estimate	16.5	57,207,396	7,170,026	13%	3.6–4.5	21–26
M3: Rainfall (literature runoff) + Expert Estimate	16.5/7.3	57,207,396	11,802,059	13–38%	4.7–8.5	22–44
M4: Surface runoff: Rainfall + DEM	164	570,028,366	40,783,055	7%	21–25	128–150
M4: Subsurface runoff: Rainfall + Expert estimate	7.3	25,309,939	7,846,081	31%	3–6	15–28
M4: Total	164 + 7.3	NA	NA	NA	24–31	143–178
Isolated Pools	NA	NA	NA	NA	1–2	NA

Oakwoods Nutrient Budget Calculation Details

No surface runoff from the wetlands Project area into Aurand Run, which is the collection water body for this watershed, was observed during times of highest water level. The absence of surface runoff was confirmed by calculating the amount of rainfall using historical weather records of the Findlay Airport 1.5 miles east of Oakwoods (71 cm in 2022) and calculating the area of Oakwoods (45 ha), the volume of the pools (29,450 m³), the rate of soil permeation (soil infiltration rates were measured at three locations across the Project by Dr. Kennedy Doro’s hydrogeophysics team as an average of 0.0052 cm/s) and estimating the rate of evaporation using published methods (Linacre 1977). A 2022 annual average evaporation rate of 5.44 mm/day was calculated using the equation below.

To calculate E_0 , the evaporation rate (mm/day), the equation is:

$$E_0 = \frac{\left[\frac{700T_m}{(100 - A)} + 15(T - T_d) \right]}{(80 - T)}$$

Where:

- T = Mean annual temperature: 11.66°C for 2022
- T_m = Mean annual temperature adjusted for elevation (h): $T + 0.006h$, where $h = 237$ m
- A = Latitude in degrees: 41.0°
- T_d = Mean annual dewpoint

Appendix: Oakwoods Nutrient Budget Calculation Details

When dewpoint data is not available, $(T - T_d)$ can be estimated as $0.0023h + 0.37T + 0.53R + 0.35Rann - 10.9^\circ\text{C}$, where R is the mean daily temperature range (19.5°C for 2022), and $Rann$ is the difference of the mean temperatures of the hottest and coldest months (29.3°C for 2022).

The evaporation rate of 5.44 mm/day was applied to the entire area of the Oakwoods wetlands and yielded an estimated volume of 890,000 m³ evaporating in 2022 which is considerably more than the 319,000 m³ of rain that fell on Oakwoods during 2022. A two-inch rainstorm would only deliver 2,275 m³ water to the Project area and that can easily be accommodated by the pools volume of 29,450 m³. The vegetation growing throughout this site will increase the rate of evaporation due to plant transpiration. So, unless more than 10 inches of rain falls over a relatively brief time, there is no expectation of any surface runoff occurring.

It's more challenging to estimate the amount of water that permeates into the soil because that depends not only on soil permeability but also on the depth of the water table and soil moisture level. The mean soil infiltration rate measured by the Doro geophysics team at Oakwoods is 0.0052 cm/s. That would indicate a very rapid permeation of water into the soil such that, if all of the pools were filled with water, the water would fully permeate into the soil within a day. However, that is for dry soil and a water table sufficiently low to accommodate that much water. Researchers have insufficient measurement of the water table level and hydraulic head to estimate the volume of water that would permeate the soil, but it is certain that the volume is significant, and this further reduces the possibility of surface water runoff.

While export of nutrients to groundwater cannot be ruled out, geophysical surveys revealing shallow clay confining layers and shallow bedrock (<0.5 meters to bedrock in some locations) suggest minimal exchange with groundwater at this location. In addition, soil P concentrations are relatively low, and soils have relatively high capacity to sorb phosphate based on the SPSC metric, meaning mobilization of phosphate in soil leachate to groundwater is unlikely. The validity of this assumption will be checked using groundwater monitoring wells that are being installed to directly assess rates of surface water-groundwater exchange and nutrient concentrations in groundwater.

The amount of P and N exported from the farm fields prior to wetland conversion was estimated using the findings of edge-of-field studies of farm fields that had similar soil type, slope, and soil P content (Pease et al. 2018). The USDA NRCS Web Soil Survey shows that nearly all of the soil in the locations of the wetland pools is soil type Pewamo silty clay loam with 0 to 1 percent slope. Analysis of soil samples from upland areas at Oakwoods that had not been disturbed during wetlands construction was used to estimate M3P soil content prior to construction as 26 mg P/kg dry soil.

The best edge-of-field data found for similar farm fields was in a report published by a team led by Kevin King (Pease, King et al. 2018). They monitored 38 fields and 10 of these had silty clay loam soil texture with soil test P in the range 20–46 and slopes in the range 0–3% most similar to the Oakwoods fields (Appendix Table 23.1). The average annual total P (dissolved reactive phosphate (DRP) + particulate phosphorus (PP)) load export for these fields was 0.83 kg P/ha with a standard deviation of 0.49 kg P/ha and a 10–90 percentile range of 0.35–1.5 kg P/ha.

Appendix: St. Joseph’s River Restoration Wetland Nutrient Budget Calculation

Appendix Table 23.1. Estimated TP loads kg/ha from Pease, et al. 2018 for 10 fields most similar to the Oakwoods farm fields.

Field ID	TP export load
L1	0.35
L2	0.32
M1	0.4
M2	0.3
N1	1.5
N2	1.25
Q1	0.9
Q2	0.65
R1	1.5
R2	1.15
Mean	0.832
Median	0.775
Std Dev	0.491

The total area of the Oakwoods farm fields was 45 ha. This gives an estimate of the annual P export from the farm fields of 37 ± 22 kg P and a 10–90 percentile range of 14–67 kg P. While this is a somewhat large range, it nevertheless gives an order of magnitude estimate of the minimum P retention by this Project.

Reduction of “New” P loads in 2023 details

To differentiate times of higher water flow and assumed inputs from tile drains into pools from times of lower flow and assume time periods of nutrient processing and storage, researchers calculated a rainfall index to account both for current and antecedent precipitation conditions. For each date on which a water sample was collected and a nutrient concentration measured, the days prior to that were counted sequentially going back in time: day 1 is the day prior to sample collection, day 2 is two days before sample collection and so on. The rainfall index is the sum of rain (measured at the Findlay Airport) on Day 1, 80% of Day 2, 50% of Day 3, and 10% of the 5 days before that to estimate the effect of soil moisture and antecedent conditions on runoff. The means were then calculated for analyte concentrations of samples collected when the rainfall index was >0.7 inch and compared for Pool 1 (mean = 0.216 mg P/L) to the means for Pools 2–19 (mean = 0.169 mg P/L). The difference in TP between Pool 1 at high flows and unconnected pools (2–19) at low flows, times the volume of this Pool ($10,000,000 \text{ L} \times 0.05 \text{ mg/L} = 500 \text{ g}$) gives an estimate of about 1.1 lb. P.

St. Joseph’s River Restoration Wetland Nutrient Budget Calculation

St. Joseph’s River Restoration is a restoration project in the Upper Maumee watershed that was constructed in 2021 and water and soil samples have been taken since its construction. The sensor network for St. Joseph’s River Restoration first started collecting data in June 2023. This Project site with its newly active sensor network highlights the value of direct sensor data over

remote sensing and is an excellent example of a wetland with complex hydrology. Researchers estimate that **St. Joseph’s River Restoration stored between 20 and 50 lbs. of phosphorus and between 600 and 800 lbs. of nitrogen in 2023.**

St. Joseph’s River Restoration is made up of 56 acres of restored farm fields and has a series of tiled and ditched drainage pathways leading to a mix of flow-through and isolated wetland pools. Near where the East Ditch flows into the St. Joseph River, the southeast area of this project is flooded by water from the large ditch on the east side of the project when the St. Joseph River level rises. The mixture of flow-through, isolated, and floodplain pools makes phosphorus (P) budgeting especially challenging at this site, because different wetland features require different methods to calculate the amount of P they remove. Here researchers present budgets for the main flow path and present the data collection in progress to measure P retention by the isolated pools and floodplain wetlands.

Appendix Figure 24.1. Comparison of 2023 sensor network data from WeatherUnderground at the Ft. Wayne weather station (~36 miles away from the site), and satellite data from the NASA Global Precipitation Measurement (GPM) mission.

Rainfall Data Comparison

The main flow path of St. Joseph’s River Restoration begins with three tile drains (Sampling Locations SJRE01, SJRE02, SJRE03, Figure 14.1) that are the main source of water to the site. The flow from these drains moves through pools A, B, C, and G to eventually flow into the East Ditch (SJRE 17) and into the St. Joseph River. To estimate P retention by the main flow path, researchers used rainfall data collected with a tipping bucket rain gage from June–December 2023. This presents an excellent opportunity to compare directly collected rainfall data with remotely sensed rainfall data. Researchers compared their directly collected sensor data with data

sources from WeatherUnderground at the Ft. Wayne weather station (~37 miles away), which provides daily measurements of rainfall data, and the NASA Global Precipitation Measurement (GPM) mission which uses satellite imagery to estimate rainfall at half-hour increments. The comparison shows that Ft. Wayne provides a much more reliable estimate of monthly rainfall at the Project site (Appendix). The P data is collected at the monthly timescale, so while the NASA GPM data is higher temporal resolution, and may better approximate sub-daily rainfall, the budgeting is already constrained by the monthly P measurements, so the nearby weather station at Ft. Wayne is the better choice for the purposes for the time period prior to installation of the on-site rain gage.

Main Flow Path Budget

Researchers collected water samples once a month for the three inlets (Sampling Locations, SJRE 01–SJRE 03) and the outlet in the east ditch (Sampling Location SJRE17). Researchers measured the concentration of P for each month at each site. Researchers estimated the topographical wetland drainage area of the site using a high-resolution digital elevation model (DEM) and estimated sub-surface runoff through the tile-drain network based on an expert estimate of the extent of the surrounding area drained through tile. To predict the proportion of rainfall that runs off across the landscape and into the wetland as surface water researchers used the NRCS curve number method (USDA-NRCS, 2004). The majority cover type of the drainage area of the site are row crops so for this estimate researchers used a curve number of 75 to arrive more in line with measured curve numbers for NW Ohio tile drained fields (Wessel et al. 2022). To account for subsurface drainage researchers used total rainfall from the area drained by each tile drain and calculated it as 31% of the rainfall as is typical for tile drainage from Ohio farmlands (Pease et al. 2018).

This budget comes with a series of important assumptions including: 1. Drainage area is accurate, 2. All water entering the wetland leaves the wetland, 3. P is not lost through subsurface flow, 4. Baseflow P reduction is the same as storm flow P reduction, 5. The variation in P concentrations when water samples can be taken can account for when they cannot be taken, 6. The average of tile drain inlet P concentrations represents the average concentration of P in tile drain runoff, and these assumptions may affect the load estimates. Note that P concentrations in water during high flow are often higher than during baseflow. Since nearly all of the concentrations used for this estimate were collected during baseflow conditions, most likely P load inflowing to the Project is substantively underestimated. Also note that the East Ditch receives tile drainage from the agricultural field east of the project. That water is not treated so likely has higher concentrations of P than water coming from the wetland. Using measurements of P concentrations in the East Ditch may overestimate the P concentration in the outflow water. It is very uncertain how this affects the estimates reported but those should be considered tentative and very likely to change as better and more complete data are obtained.

Researchers estimated the retention of P by SJRE in 2023 using a mix of rainfall data from WeatherUnderground and sensor network data. The sensor network first came online on June 28th, 2023, so from that date forward researchers used sensor network rainfall data, and before

Appendix: St. Joseph’s River Restoration Wetland Nutrient Budget Calculation

that date researchers used publicly available data from the Ft. Wayne weather station. For each month researchers multiplied the predicted discharge through each tile drain by the concentration of that month; for surface water researchers multiplied flow by the average concentration from all 3 tile drains entering the system. For some months there was not enough flowing or standing water during monthly sampling to collect surface water samples at some, or all inlets and outlets, however, storm events still delivered water and nutrients to the wetland. To estimate the amount of nutrients delivered where researchers do not have measured concentration, researchers estimated an upper and lower range of P concentrations entering the wetland by using the maximum and minimum concentration for each other month that researchers do have data for. Researchers similarly estimated an upper and lower range of P retention by the system by using the maximum and minimum percent retention at the site for each other month.

With this method researchers estimate that **SJRE stored 20–50 lbs. of phosphorus and 600–800 lbs. of nitrogen in 2023**. This site is especially useful as an example of the importance of calculating nutrient load, as opposed to relying on concentrations alone. The sites’ ability to retain P varies throughout the year, and as a result the average % P retention at the site for 2023 is -50%, but if you calculate the total retention of P (scaled by the amount of water flowing through the site) it **retained 50% of the phosphorus it received in 2023**. This is because months where the site is releasing P correspond with both low concentrations of P flowing into the site, and low flow rates, whereas the wetland is retaining P when concentrations are higher, and there is more water flowing through the site.

Appendix Figure 24.2. Estimated phosphorus retention in each month of 2023 at St. Joseph’s River Restoration. Researchers combined estimates of drainage area, rainfall, and monthly phosphorus concentrations to estimate the lbs. phosphorus retained at the site for each month. There was no water to collect from Sep-Dec 2023, so researchers made a high- and low- end estimate based on measured flow and phosphorus concentrations in previous months. These estimates may change as more data is collected, especially during high flow events.

Addressing assumptions

While the topographic drainage area of SJRE is likely accurate, researchers are missing the hydrologic drainage area, and accounting for the impacts of tile drainage to the system. Tile drainage in northern Ohio can lead to more than 31% of rainfall leaving the system through subsurface drainage, which could significantly increase the estimates of retention from the 13% of rainfall that researchers are currently predicting for the overall drainage area of the site (Pease et al. 2018). At the same time, the budget does not account for water evaporation and water storage by the wetland, or groundwater. Groundwater has the potential to decrease estimates of retention by acting as another outflow, but water storage by the system likely reduces the volume of water leaving the wetland and will likely increase estimates of phosphorous storage (Krasnostein & Oldham, 2004, Meinikmann et al., 2015).

Similarly, the measurements of monthly P concentration require assumptions. The current budget uses an average of P concentration at the 3 tile drains to represent the concentration entering the wetland, but researchers know that some tile drains are more active than others. This could affect the estimates of the amount of P entering the system, but these effects would likely not be extremely large. What is more important is storm events. Currently the budget assumes that P retention is the same during normal flow and storm events, but previous research shows that storm flow can cause major shifts in the retention of P in wetlands (McClaine et al. 2003). The data also supports it but is limited to a single data point where researchers see a shift from 96% P reduction during baseflow to 51% P reduction during storm flow as water moves through the wetland. Collection of more data will allow us to address the potential for storm flow to alter nutrient retention and may also contribute to the last assumption: that variation in P concentration can account for periods when samples cannot be taken. There are long periods of the year when SJRE dries out, but researchers still predict runoff into the system, which will carry P with it, but will not fill the pools. Without measures of concentration, researchers need to rely on other months to predict that range of possible concentrations entering the system. Researchers can calculate a range of P loading when there are no samples taken by multiplying the predicted flow with the lowest concentration in a previous month, and then the highest concentration in a previous month. This provides us with a range of possible retention by the system, when water samples cannot be taken.

Isolated pools and floodplain

Researchers are currently in the early stage of estimating the impact of isolated pools and the floodplain wetlands for SJRE. Researchers **deployed sediment accretion markers to all the major pools at the site** in November 2023. These markers are a brilliant white feldspar that forms a cohesive layer in the sediment. As sediment is deposited in the wetland researchers can measure the depth of new sediment being deposited, and then measure the concentration of P in that sediment. In this way researchers can estimate for the total area of the pool, how much new P has been deposited, while comparing the change in P concentration below the accretion layer to better understand how deeper soil P storage has been affected.

Improving Wetland Drainage Area Estimation

Drainage area is a key feature in estimating the amount of water entering a wetland. The water can come through various sources such as surface runoff from land surface, and other subsurface water sources such as tile drains and groundwater flow. Knowledge of drainage area is vital especially for unmonitored wetlands, or wetlands where inflow monitoring is not feasible, or for planning new constructed wetlands where exact inflow measurements are not available.

Wetland drainage area can be classified under two categories: topographical wetland drainage area (TOWDA) and hydrological wetland drainage area (HOWDA). As evident in the term, TOWDA is defined as the area draining into a wetland with respect to only the elevation or topography of the land surface. TOWDA does not consider other cryptic sources of water that enter a wetland, for example: water from tile drains, and groundwater flow. So, to consider all the sources of water entering a wetland, HOWDA is introduced and is defined as the actual wetland drainage area that drains into a wetland which includes topography of a land surface and other cryptic water sources.

Although the estimation of HOWDA requires more information, it is more representative of the drainage area of a wetland. Once researchers gain more information on tile drains and groundwater data, researchers will include them to estimate HOWDA for different wetland projects. However, first researchers use finer resolution DEM (1 meter) to estimate TOWDA of different wetland based on land surface elevation only.

Current method of estimation by ODNR and associated drawbacks

ODNR is currently using drainage area to estimate approximate nutrient removal of a wetland. The nutrient removal is estimated based on P loading obtained from the USGS SPARROW model. This model considers P loading to be directly proportional to the drainage area. The drainage area used by ODNR is obtained from USGS StreamStats. Although StreamStats is a great tool for estimating drainage area of stream networks, it may not be as precise for the wetland drainage area. The use of StreamStats is based on delineation of drainage area by clicking a point in a stream network generated by Streamstats. It does not allow users to select a random wetland to estimate the area draining into that wetland. Furthermore, the DEM resolution used by StreamStats is 10m x 10m currently, which may not be able to capture some wetlands that are less than the size of this grid. These are the primary reasons the drainage area obtained from StreamStats may not always be true. So, it is always better to find a solution that works best for most cases. In most cases, the drainage area provided by StreamStats is TOWDA. Hence, it is better to estimate the TOWDA based on DEM with better resolution, and with a tool where one can select the actual wetland pool rather than a single point for drainage area estimation.

Suggested method to estimate topographical wetland drainage area (TOWDA)

To estimate TOWDA, 1 meter DEM for the sites were obtained from The National Map of the US Geological Survey (USGS). The ArcHydro tool in ArcGIS Pro was used to estimate the drainage area of wetlands. This method used better resolution of DEM compared to the

StreamStats, and this method was able to delineate drainage area of each wetland pool rather than a single point in stream networks compared to StreamStats.

Wetland drainage area for St. Joseph Restoration Project (SJRE)

The TOWDA for SJRE is shown in Figure 1. There are seven different wetland pools at SJRE. The drainage areas for two of these pools (A and B) represent the majority of TOWDA for SJRE wetland. The total TOWDA obtained using 1m DEM (~150 acres) is three times the area reported by ODNR (~50 acres), which was obtained from StreamStats. Although TOWDA is not a representative of the actual water entering a wetland, it gives a general overview of the area that might be contributing to a wetland considering no anthropogenic disturbances.

To address the anthropogenic disturbances and other natural flows that may affect the drainage area of a wetland, HOWDA estimation is important. For now, researchers have relied upon expert estimates of area drained by tiles into SJRE (as provided by Melanie Coulter, through Dr. W. Robert Midden: NE tile drainage area = 16.8 acres, N tile drainage area = 25.9 acres, and NW tile drainage area = 38.5 acres) for nutrient budget calculation. For the total water discharge required for P budget estimation, researchers used discharge to precipitation ratio of 7% for surface runoff from the TOWDA, and 31% for subsurface flow from the tile drains, obtained from Pease et al. (2018). For details, see *St. Joseph's River Restoration Wetland Nutrient Budget Calculation*.

Appendix Figure 25.1. Topographical wetland drainage area for SJRE. The polygons in orange are individual wetland pools in the SJRE. The light-yellow polygon is the combined topographical drainage area for all the pools.

Wetland drainage area for Forder Bridge (FORB)

There are many wetland pools in FORB. The drainage area was mapped for pool 4A since the majority of water entering FORB wetland is from a culvert which drains water into the pool 4A. The TOWDA for FORB obtained from 1m DEM (~164 acres) was more than twice the area as estimated by ODNR (~63 acres). This TOWDA is based entirely on the land surface elevation alone obtained from the DEM. According to expert's information about the site, only 16.5 acres of area drains into the FORB (see *Forder Bridge Wetland Nutrient Budget Calculation*) which is far less than the estimates from the DEM. This may be a case where the TOWDA is greater than HOWDA since the actual area draining into the wetland is less than the TOWDA estimated from the high-resolution DEM.

Appendix Figure 25.2. Topographical wetland drainage area for FORB. The polygons in orange are individual wetland pools. The light-yellow polygon is the topographical drainage area for only Pool 4A.

Future work

Future work includes estimation of HOWDA for SJRE and other focal projects. This will be done by getting information on tile drains and any other sources of water entering these wetlands. For areas where the exact tile drain maps are not available, the plan is to leverage remote sensing techniques to map the tile drain extent to estimate the HOWDA of wetland.

Nutrient Load Calculation Details, Literature cited:

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